

Online Supplementary Material to “Fit First and Detect Later: A Unified Decoupled Framework for Change Detection in High Dimensions”

Bin Liu LIUBIN1045@GMAIL.COM
*Department of Statistics and Data Science, School of Management
 Fudan University*

Yufeng Liu YUFLIU@UMICH.EDU
*Department of Statistics
 University of Michigan*

Zhi Yang YANGZHI_SUFE@OUTLOOK.COM
*School of Statistics and Data Science
 Shanghai University of Finance and Economics*

Liwen Zhang ZHANG.LIWEN@SHUFE.EDU.CN
*School of Statistics and Data Science
 Shanghai University of Finance and Economics*

Editor:

Contents

S0 Theoretical Proof Overview and Notation Summary	2
S0.1 Overview of the Theoretical Proof	2
S0.2 Notation summary	4
S1 Proofs of auxiliary lemmas for examples of Model (1)	6
S1.1 Proof for the Example Involving Changes in Means	6
S1.2 Proof for the Example Involving Changes in Regression Coefficients	10
S2 Detailed proof for change point estimators	14
S2.1 Proof for Theorem 4	15
S2.2 Proof for Theorem 7	26
S2.3 Proof for Lemma 36	30
S3 Several prerequisite results	34
S3.1 Prerequisite results for optimization problem (8)	35
S3.2 Proof of Lemmas in Section S3.1	42
S3.3 Prerequisite results for optimization problem (13)	58
S3.4 Proof of Lemmas in Section S3.3	60

S0 Theoretical Proof Overview and Notation Summary

Since the theoretical proofs make up a substantial portion of the supplementary material, we first present an overview of the proof framework in Section S0.1 to facilitate understanding of our technical approach. Section S0.2 then summarizes the main notations used in the proofs.

S0.1 Overview of the Theoretical Proof

The proof overview is divided into two main components: Section S0.1.1 focuses on parameter estimation across different model setups, while Section S0.1.2 addresses change point localization within a unified analytical framework. To guide the reader through the structure of our arguments, we provide proof roadmaps for Theorems 3–7 in Figures S0.1–S0.4. In these figures, rectangular blocks are color-coded as follows: blue indicates assumptions or conditions, red marks the main conclusions, and green denotes supporting lemmas. Arrows reflect logical flow: the tail represents the input conditions, and the head points to the conclusion. Solid arrows indicate steps with detailed proofs, while dashed arrows highlight either self-evident results or steps whose proofs are omitted or left open.

S0.1.1 PARAMETER ESTIMATION

We separately provide the proofs for the mean model (2) and the regression model (3), as shown in Figures S0.1 and S0.2, respectively. Note that Theorems 3 and 6 are special cases of Theorem 29 under the mean model and Theorem 32 under the regression model, respectively.

Figure S0.1: Proof roadmap for parameter estimation under the mean model (2).

Figure S0.2: Proof roadmap for parameter estimation under the linear regression model (3).

Figure S0.3: Roadmap of the proof for the preliminary change point estimators $\hat{\mathcal{T}}_k$.

Figure S0.4: Roadmap of the proof for the refined change point estimators $\widehat{\mathcal{T}}_k^r$.

S0.1.2 CHANGE POINT ESTIMATION

We apply a unified proof framework to establish the preliminary estimators $\widehat{\mathcal{T}}_k$ and the refined estimators $\widehat{\mathcal{T}}_k^r$ for change points, as shown in Figures S0.3 and S0.4, respectively. The dashed box indicates the generic change point proof technique, which is model-agnostic. In the proof of Theorem 4, several model-agnostic results are required, which are established using lemmas shown outside the box under either the mean model (2) (left side) or the regression model (3) (right side).

S0.2 Notation summary

We use C_0, C_1, C_2, \dots and c_0, c_1, c_2, \dots to denote constants that may vary from line to line. For any integer $x > 0$, let $[x] := \{1, \dots, x\}$ and $[x]^- := \{x, \dots, 1\}$. For any matrix $\mathbf{M} \in \mathbb{R}^{p \times p}$, define $\mathbf{M}(a, b)$ as the entry of matrix \mathbf{M} that lies in the a -th row and b -th column. For a real-valued random variable Z and $q > 0$, define $\|Z\|_{L^q} := (\mathbb{E}[|Z|^q])^{1/q}$ if the expectation exists. For any set \mathcal{S} , let $|\mathcal{S}|$ denote its cardinality. The convergences in distribution is denoted by $\xrightarrow{\mathcal{D}}$. For any generic interval $\mathcal{I} = (u, v]$ such that $0 \leq u \leq v \leq n$ and a given parameter $\boldsymbol{\theta}$, the loss function $\mathcal{L}(u, v; \boldsymbol{\theta})$ can also be expressed as $\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{I}, \boldsymbol{\theta})$. Both representations are equivalent in the proof. We denote $\text{Dist}(\mu, \sigma^2)$ is some continuous distribution with finite mean μ and variance σ^2 .

Symbol declarations Throughout this paper, we maintain the convention that symbol j is assumed to belong to the index set $[k^*]$ or $[\hat{k}]$, while symbol \tilde{j} denotes an element of \mathcal{G}_j

or index set $[\tilde{k} + 1]$. Recall the Assumption 1, for the symbol

$$\tilde{\mathfrak{r}} = \frac{C_{\mathfrak{r}} \Delta \kappa}{(s^{1/2} \Upsilon_n^i)}, \quad (\text{S0.1})$$

it represents the maximum distance between a change point and its corresponding marker initializer. The symbol

$$\hat{\mathfrak{t}} = \frac{C_{\epsilon} s \log(np)}{\kappa^2}, \quad (\text{S0.2})$$

denotes the maximum distance between a change point and its corresponding preliminary change point estimator.

Location space Fix an integer $v \in [n]$ and any integer $k \geq 1$ such that $v > k$. The space of candidate change point locations is defined as

$$\mathbb{T}_k(v) := \left\{ \{t_1, \dots, t_k\} : 0 = t_0 < t_1 < \dots < t_k < t_{k+1} = v \right\}, \quad (\text{S0.3})$$

along with a relaxed version of the space:

$$\mathbb{U}_k(v) := \left\{ \{u_1, \dots, u_k\} : 0 = u_0 \leq u_1 \leq \dots \leq u_k \leq u_{k+1} = v \right\}. \quad (\text{S0.4})$$

Index Groups Recalling the definition of the *index group* \mathcal{G}_j in (16), we now define the first index of \mathcal{G}_j as $\mathfrak{h}(j)$, i.e.,

$$\mathcal{G}_j = \left\{ \tilde{j} \in [\tilde{k} + 1] \mid \mathfrak{h}(j) \leq \tilde{j} \leq m(j) \right\}, \quad \text{for } j \in [k^* + 1]. \quad (\text{S0.5})$$

Note that $m(j) + 1 = \mathfrak{h}(j + 1)$ for any $j \in [k^*]$. The index group definitions in (16) and (S0.5) are equivalent, and for clarity and consistency, the proof will primarily adopt the formulation given by (S0.5). For indices lying outside this range (i.e., $j \notin [k^* + 1]$), the corresponding sets \mathcal{G}_j are defined as empty collections, i.e., $\mathcal{G}_j = \emptyset$. We further define the cardinality of the j -th index group as $\mathfrak{g}_j := |\mathcal{G}_j|$. It is straightforward to observe that if $\mathfrak{g}_j = 1$, indicating that this group includes only the *marker* $m(j)$. That is, there are no indices corresponding additional initializers in this group, implying that $\mathfrak{h}(j) = m(j)$ holds. A more intuitive way to represent the indices of the initializers $\{1, 2, \dots, \tilde{k}, \tilde{k} + 1\}$ is, namely,

$$\begin{aligned} \{1, 2, \dots, \tilde{k}, \tilde{k} + 1\} &= \bigcup_{j=1}^{k^*+1} \mathcal{G}_j \\ &= \left\{ 1 = \underbrace{\mathfrak{h}(1), \mathfrak{h}(2), \dots, m(1)}_{\mathfrak{g}_1}, \dots, \underbrace{\mathfrak{h}(j), \dots, m(j)}_{\mathfrak{g}_k}, \dots, \underbrace{\mathfrak{h}(k^* + 1), \dots, m(k^* + 1)}_{\mathfrak{g}_{k^*+1}} = \tilde{k} + 1 \right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S0.6})$$

Raw True Locations Besides, the *raw true locations* $\mathfrak{u}_k^* = \{u_j^*\}_{j=1}^{\tilde{k}} \in \mathbb{U}_{\tilde{k}}(n)$ is now defined as follow,

$$u_{\tilde{j}}^* = t_j^* \quad \text{for any } \tilde{j} \in \mathcal{G}_j, \quad j \in [k^* + 1]. \quad (\text{S0.7})$$

In simpler terms, for every $j \in [k^* + 1]$, the (S0.7) can be equivalently written as

$$u_{\mathfrak{h}(j)}^* = u_{\mathfrak{h}(j)+1}^* = \dots = u_{m(j)-1}^* = u_{m(j)}^* = t_j^*.$$

Notably, when $j = k^* + 1$, for any \tilde{j} belongs to the index group \mathcal{G}_{k^*+1} , it follows that $u_{\tilde{j}}^* = n$.

S1 Proofs of auxiliary lemmas for examples of Model (1)

S1.1 Proof for the Example Involving Changes in Means

S1.1.1 INDEPENDENT SETTING

Proof [Proof for Lemma 20] Since ε_i 's are sub-Exponential random vectors with variance proxy σ_ε^2 , applying Bernstein's inequality for each $a = 1, \dots, p$, we obtain

$$\mathbb{P} \left\{ \left\| \frac{1}{|\mathcal{I}|} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \varepsilon_i \right\|_\infty > t \right\} \leq 2p \exp \left(-c_1 |\mathcal{I}| \min \left(\frac{t^2}{\sigma_\varepsilon^2}, \frac{t}{\sigma_\varepsilon} \right) \right).$$

Choosing

$$t = c_0 \sigma_\varepsilon \left(\sqrt{\frac{\log(np)}{|\mathcal{I}|}} + \frac{\log(np)}{|\mathcal{I}|} \right),$$

from Remark S1.1 yields,

$$\left\| \frac{1}{|\mathcal{I}|} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \varepsilon_i \right\|_\infty \leq C_1 \left(\sqrt{\frac{\log(np)}{|\mathcal{I}|}} + \frac{\log(np)}{|\mathcal{I}|} \right).$$

with probability at least $1 - n^{-5}$. ■

Remark S1.1 Consider the quantity

$$t = c_0 \left(\sqrt{\frac{\log(np)}{|\mathcal{I}|}} + \frac{\log(np)}{|\mathcal{I}|} \right),$$

where $c_0 > 0$ is a constant. Observe the following two cases:

Case 1: $|\mathcal{I}| \leq \log(np)$. In this case, the second term dominates, leading to $\log(np)/|\mathcal{I}| \geq 1$. Consequently, we have

$$\min(t^2, t) = \min(c_0^2, c_0) \frac{\log(np)}{|\mathcal{I}|}.$$

Case 2: $|\mathcal{I}| > \log(np)$. Here, the first term dominates, and we find $\log(np)/|\mathcal{I}| < 1$. As a result,

$$\min(t^2, t) = \min(c_0^2, c_0) \frac{\log(np)}{|\mathcal{I}|}.$$

Proof [Proof for Lemma 21] By Lemma 20 (Appendix), for any $r \in \{3, \dots, n\}$, it holds that

$$\mathbb{P} \left\{ \left\| \sum_{i=1}^r \varepsilon_i \right\|_\infty > C_1 \left(\sqrt{r \log(np)} + \log(np) \right) \right\} \leq n^{-5}.$$

Then by a union bound,

$$\mathbb{P} \left\{ \left\| \sum_{i=1}^r \varepsilon_i \right\|_\infty > C_1 \left(\sqrt{r \log(np)} + \log(np) \right) \text{ for all } 3 \leq r \leq n \right\} \leq n^{-4}.$$

■

Proof [Proof for Lemma 22] For $m \in \mathbb{Z}_+$, define intervals $\mathcal{T}_m = [2^m/\nu, 2^{m+1}/\nu]$. By Lemma S1.2 with $\alpha = 1$ and $d = 2^m/\nu$, $\forall x > 0$:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{P}\left(\max_{r \in \mathcal{T}_m} \frac{|\sum_{i=1}^r Z_i|}{\sqrt{r}} \geq x\right) &\leq 2 \exp\left(-\frac{x^2}{4}\right) + 2 \exp\left(-\frac{\sqrt{2^m/\nu}x}{2}\right) \\ &\leq 2 \exp\left(-\frac{x^2}{4}\right) + 2 \exp\left(-\frac{x}{2\sqrt{\nu}}\right) \\ &\leq 8x^{-2} + 4\sqrt{\nu}x^{-1}, \end{aligned}$$

where the last inequality follows from $e^{-t} \leq (1+t)^{-1} \leq t^{-1}$ for $t > 0$. For any $1 < a < 1$, union bound over $m \geq 0$ gives:

$$\begin{aligned} &\mathbb{P}\left(\exists m \geq 0 : \max_{r \in \mathcal{T}_m} \frac{|\sum_{i=1}^r Z_i|}{\sqrt{r}} \geq \frac{2\sqrt{2}\pi}{\sqrt{6a}}(m+1) + \frac{4\sqrt{\nu}\pi^2}{6a}(m+1)^2\right) \\ &\leq \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{6a^2}{\pi^2(m+1)^2} + \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{6a}{\pi^2(m+1)^2} = a^2 + a. \end{aligned}$$

For $r \geq 2^m/\nu$, $m \leq \log_2(\nu r)$ implies:

$$\mathbb{P}\left(\exists m \geq 0 : \max_{r \in \mathcal{T}_m} \frac{|\sum_{i=1}^r Z_i|}{\sqrt{r}} \geq \frac{C_1}{a}(\sqrt{\nu} \vee 1) \left\{ \frac{\log(\nu r)}{\log 2} + 1 \right\}^2\right) \leq a^2 + a$$

This completes the proof. ■

The following lemma plays a dual role in our analysis: it is crucial not only for deriving the optimal rate of change point estimation in mean models and the linear regression model (3).

Lemma S1.2 *Suppose $\{Z_i\}_{i=1}^{\infty}$ is a collection of independent centered sub-exponential random variables with $\sup_{1 \leq i < \infty} \sigma_i^2 \leq \sigma^2 = 1$, where σ_i^2 is the variance proxy for Z_i . Then for any integer $d > 0$, $\alpha > 0$, and $x > 0$,*

$$\mathbb{P}\left(\max_{l \in [d, (1+\alpha)d]} \frac{|\sum_{i=1}^l Z_i|}{\sqrt{l}} \geq x\right) \leq 2 \exp\left(-\frac{x^2}{2(1+\alpha)}\right) + 2 \exp\left(-\frac{\sqrt{dx}}{2}\right).$$

Proof Let $S_n = \sum_{i=1}^n Z_i$. By the variance proxy condition, for any $|t| \leq 1/\sigma$, we have:

$$\mathbb{E}[\exp(tZ_i)] \leq \exp\left(\frac{t^2\sigma^2}{2}\right).$$

Step 1: Supermartingale construction

Let \mathcal{F}_n denote the sigma-algebra generated by (Z_1, \dots, Z_n) . Define $M_n = \exp\left(tS_n - \frac{t^2\sigma^2 n}{2}\right)$. For $|t| \leq 1/\sigma$, independence implies:

$$\mathbb{E}[M_n | \mathcal{F}_{n-1}] = M_{n-1} \cdot \mathbb{E}[\exp(tZ_n)] \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{t^2\sigma^2}{2}\right) \leq M_{n-1}.$$

Thus $\{M_n\}$ is a supermartingale.

Step 2: Stopping time analysis

Define the stopping time:

$$T = \inf \{n \geq d : S_n \geq \sqrt{nx}\}.$$

On $\{T \leq (1 + \alpha)d\}$, we have $S_T \geq \sqrt{Tx} \geq \sqrt{dx}$. By the supermartingale property and Optional Stopping Theorem:

$$\mathbb{E} \left[\exp \left(tS_T - \frac{t^2\sigma^2 T}{2} \right) \right] \leq 1.$$

Substitute $S_T \geq \sqrt{dx}$ into the exponential:

$$\mathbb{E} \left[\exp \left(t\sqrt{dx} - \frac{t^2\sigma^2 T}{2} \right) \right] \leq 1.$$

Apply Markov's inequality to the non-negative random variable $\exp \left(t\sqrt{dx} - \frac{t^2\sigma^2 T}{2} \right)$:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{P}(T \leq (1 + \alpha)d) &\leq \mathbb{E} \left[\exp \left(t\sqrt{dx} - \frac{t^2\sigma^2 T}{2} \right) \right] \exp \left(-t\sqrt{dx} + \frac{t^2\sigma^2(1 + \alpha)d}{2} \right) \\ &\leq \exp \left(-t\sqrt{dx} + \frac{t^2\sigma^2(1 + \alpha)d}{2} \right). \end{aligned}$$

Step 3.

Choose $t > 0$ to minimize the exponent:

$$t = \min \left\{ \frac{1}{\sigma}, \frac{x}{\sigma^2(1 + \alpha)\sqrt{d}} \right\}.$$

Case 1: If $\frac{1}{\sigma} \geq \frac{x}{\sigma^2(1 + \alpha)\sqrt{d}}$,

Set $t = \frac{x}{\sigma^2(1 + \alpha)\sqrt{d}}$:

$$\begin{aligned} -t\sqrt{dx} + \frac{t^2\sigma^2(1 + \alpha)d}{2} &= -\frac{x^2}{\sigma^2(1 + \alpha)} + \frac{x^2}{2\sigma^2(1 + \alpha)} \\ &= -\frac{x^2}{2\sigma^2(1 + \alpha)}. \end{aligned}$$

Thus:

$$\mathbb{P}(T \leq (1 + \alpha)d) \leq \exp \left(-\frac{x^2}{2\sigma^2(1 + \alpha)} \right).$$

Case 2: If $\frac{1}{\sigma} \leq \frac{x}{\sigma^2(1 + \alpha)\sqrt{d}}$,

Set $t = \frac{1}{\sigma}$:

$$-t\sqrt{dx} + \frac{t^2\sigma^2(1 + \alpha)d}{2} = -\frac{\sqrt{dx}}{\sigma} + \frac{(1 + \alpha)d}{2}.$$

From $t = \frac{1}{\sigma} \leq \frac{x}{\sigma^2(1+\alpha)\sqrt{d}}$, we get $\sqrt{d} \leq x/\{\sigma(1+\alpha)\}$. Hence:

$$-\frac{\sqrt{d}x}{\sigma} + \frac{(1+\alpha)d}{2} \leq -\frac{\sqrt{d}x}{2\sigma}.$$

Thus:

$$\mathbb{P}(T \leq (1+\alpha)d) \leq \exp\left(-\frac{\sqrt{d}x}{2\sigma}\right).$$

Combining both cases:

$$\mathbb{P}\left(\max_{l \in [d, (1+\alpha)d]} \frac{S_l}{\sqrt{l}} \geq x\right) \leq \exp\left(-\frac{x^2}{2\sigma^2(1+\alpha)}\right) + \exp\left(-\frac{\sqrt{d}x}{2\sigma}\right).$$

For the two-sided bound, observe that

$$\mathbb{P}\left(\max_l \left|\frac{S_l}{\sqrt{l}}\right| \geq x\right) \leq \mathbb{P}\left(\max_l \frac{S_l}{\sqrt{l}} \geq x\right) + \mathbb{P}\left(\max_l \frac{-S_l}{\sqrt{l}} \geq x\right).$$

The second term satisfies identical bounds by considering $\{-Z_i\}$, which preserves the variance proxy condition. Thus doubling the original bound completes the proof. \blacksquare

S1.1.2 TEMPORAL DEPENDENCE SETTING

Proof [Proof for Lemma 20'] For any $a \in [p]$, let $Z_i = \varepsilon_{i,a}$. Note that $\{Z_i\}_{i \in \mathbb{Z}}$ is a stationary process. For any $i \in \mathbb{Z}$, we have that

$$\delta_{i,2}^Z = \|Z_i - Z_{i,\{i-t\}}\|_{L_2} = \|\varepsilon_{i,a} - \varepsilon_{ia,\{i-t\}}\|_{L_2} \leq \delta_{i,4}^\varepsilon.$$

As a result, it holds that

$$\Delta_{m,2}^Z = \sum_{t=m}^{\infty} \delta_{t,2}^Z \leq \Delta_{m,4}^\varepsilon.$$

Consequently,

$$\sup_{m \geq 0} \exp(c_0 m^{\zeta_1}) \Delta_{m,2}^Z < \infty.$$

By Lemma 17, it holds that for any $x \geq 1$ and interger $n \geq 3$,

$$\mathbb{P}\left(\left|\sum_{i \in [n]} \varepsilon_{i,a}\right| \geq x\right) = \mathbb{P}\left(\left|\sum_{i \in [n]} Z_i\right| \geq x\right) \leq n \exp(-c_1 x^\zeta) + 2 \exp\left(-\frac{c_2 x^2}{n}\right).$$

By the union bound argument, it follows that for any $\tau \geq 1$,

$$\mathbb{P}\left(\left\|\sum_{i=1}^n \varepsilon_i\right\|_\infty \geq x\right) \leq np \exp(-c_1 x^\zeta) + 2p \exp\left(-\frac{c_2 x^2}{n}\right).$$

Therefore, with sufficiently large constant C_1 ,

$$\mathbb{P}\left(\left\|\frac{1}{n}\sum_{i\in[n]}\varepsilon_i\right\|_{\infty}\geq C_1\left\{\frac{\log^{1/\zeta}(np)}{n}+\sqrt{\frac{\log(np)}{n}}\right\}\right)\leq n^{-5}.$$

■

Proof [Proof for Lemma 21'] By Lemma 20', for any $r\in\{3,\dots,n\}$, it holds that

$$\mathbb{P}\left\{\left\|\sum_{i=1}^r\varepsilon_i\right\|_{\infty}>C_1\left(\sqrt{r\log(np)}+\log^{1/\zeta}(np)\right)\right\}\leq n^{-5}.$$

Then by a union bound,

$$\mathbb{P}\left\{\left\|\sum_{i=1}^r\varepsilon_i\right\|_{\infty}>C_1\left(\sqrt{r\log(np)}+\log^{1/\zeta}(np)\right)\text{ for all }3\leq r\leq n\right\}\leq n^{-4}.$$

■

S1.2 Proof for the Example Involving Changes in Regression Coefficients

S1.2.1 INDEPENDENT SETTING

Proof [Proof for Lemma 25]

Step 1. Since ε_i 's are sub-Gaussian random variables and \mathbf{X}_i 's are sub-Gaussian random vectors, we have that $\varepsilon_i\mathbf{X}_i$ are sub-Exponential random vectors with parameter $\sigma_x^2\sigma_{\varepsilon}^2$ (see e.g. Lemma 2.7.7 in Vershynin, 2018). It then follows from Bernstein's inequality (see e.g. Corollary 2.8.3 in Vershynin, 2018) that for any $t>0$,

$$\mathbb{P}\left\{\left\|\frac{1}{|\mathcal{I}|}\sum_{i\in\mathcal{I}}\mathbf{X}_i\varepsilon_i\right\|_{\infty}>t\right\}\leq 2p\exp\left(-c|\mathcal{I}|\min\left(\frac{t^2}{\sigma_x^2\sigma_{\varepsilon}^2},\frac{t}{\sigma_x\sigma_{\varepsilon}}\right)\right)$$

where $c>0$ is an absolute constant. Upon choosing,

$$t=c_0\sigma_x\sigma_{\varepsilon}\left(\sqrt{\frac{\log(np)}{|\mathcal{I}|}}+\frac{\log(np)}{|\mathcal{I}|}\right),$$

for absolute constant $c_0>0$, it holds that

$$c|\mathcal{I}|\min\left(\frac{t^2}{\sigma_x^2\sigma_{\varepsilon}^2},\frac{t}{\sigma_x\sigma_{\varepsilon}}\right)=c\min(c_0^2,c_0)\log(np),$$

from Remark S1.1. Using these relations the above probability bound yields

$$\left\|\frac{1}{|\mathcal{I}|}\sum_{i\in\mathcal{I}}\mathbf{X}_i\varepsilon_i\right\|_{\infty}\leq C_1\left(\sqrt{\frac{\log(np)}{|\mathcal{I}|}}+\frac{\log(np)}{|\mathcal{I}|}\right),$$

with probability at least $1 - n^{-5}$ for some sufficiently large constant C_1 depending on c_0, σ_x and σ_ε .

Step 2. Note that the RHS of the inequality in (ii) is normalized by the ℓ_2 norm of \mathbf{w} . Hence, without loss of generality we can assume $\|\mathbf{w}\|_2 = 1$. To prove the second bound, first note that $\mathbf{w}^\top \mathbf{X}_i \mathbf{X}_i^\top - \mathbf{w}^\top \boldsymbol{\Sigma}$ is sub-Exponential random vector with parameter σ_x^4 . Therefore applying Bernstein's inequality, yields the following probability bound,

$$\mathbb{P} \left\{ \left\| \frac{1}{|\mathcal{I}|} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (\mathbf{w}^\top \mathbf{X}_i \mathbf{X}_i^\top - \mathbf{w}^\top \boldsymbol{\Sigma}) \right\|_\infty > t \right\} \leq 2p \exp \left(-c|\mathcal{I}| \min \left(\frac{t^2}{\sigma_x^4}, \frac{t}{\sigma_x^2} \right) \right).$$

Now upon choosing,

$$t = c_0 \sigma_x^2 \left(\sqrt{\frac{\log(np)}{|\mathcal{I}|}} + \frac{\log(np)}{|\mathcal{I}|} \right),$$

From Remark S1.1, it can be verified that,

$$c|\mathcal{I}| \min \left(\frac{t^2}{\sigma_x^4}, \frac{t}{\sigma_x^2} \right) = c \min(c_0^2, c_0) \log(np).$$

Thus, it holds with probability at least of $1 - n^{-5}$ that,

$$\left\| \frac{1}{|\mathcal{I}|} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (\mathbf{w}^\top \mathbf{X}_i \mathbf{X}_i^\top - \mathbf{w}^\top \boldsymbol{\Sigma}) \right\|_\infty \leq c_0 \sigma_x^2 \left(\sqrt{\frac{\log(np)}{|\mathcal{I}|}} + \frac{\log(np)}{|\mathcal{I}|} \right).$$

Step 3. Note that $\mathbf{w}^\top \mathbf{X}_i \mathbf{X}_i^\top \mathbf{w} - \mathbf{w}^\top \boldsymbol{\Sigma} \mathbf{w}$ is sub-Exponential random vector with parameter σ_x^4 with condition $\|\mathbf{w}\|_2 = 1$. The rest proof of part (iii) is similar to the **Step 2**. ■

Proof [Proof for Lemma 26] For any set \mathcal{S} , $\text{Cl}(\mathcal{S})$ denote the closure of \mathcal{S} and $\text{conv}(\mathcal{S})$ denote the convex hull of \mathcal{S} . Let

$$\mathbb{K}(s) = \mathbb{B}_0(s) \cup \mathbb{B}_2(1),$$

where

$$\mathbb{B}_q(x) = \{\mathbf{w} \in \mathbb{R}^p : \|\mathbf{w}\|_q \leq x\},$$

for $q \in \{0, 1, 2\}$ and any $x > 0$.

Step 1. By Lemma 12 in the supplementary material of Loh and Wainwright (2012), for any $t > 0$, there exists a constant c such that

$$\mathbb{P} \left\{ \sup_{\boldsymbol{\delta} \in \mathbb{K}(2s)} \left| \boldsymbol{\delta}^\top \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbf{X}_i \mathbf{X}_i^\top - \boldsymbol{\Sigma} \right) \boldsymbol{\delta} \right| \geq t \right\} \leq 2 \exp \left\{ -cn \min \left(\frac{t^2}{\sigma_x^4}, \frac{t}{\sigma_x^2} \right) + 2s \log p \right\}. \quad (\text{S1.1})$$

Moreover, by Lemma F.1 in the supplementary material of Basu and Michailidis (2015),

$$\mathbb{A} \cup \mathbb{B}_2(1) \subset (\alpha + 2) \text{Cl}\{\text{conv}(\mathbb{K}(s))\},$$

it follows that

$$\sup_{\delta \in \mathbb{A} \cup \mathbb{B}_2(1)} \left| \delta^\top \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbf{X}_i \mathbf{X}_i^\top - \Sigma \right) \delta \right| \leq \sup_{\delta \in (\alpha+2) \text{Cl}\{\text{conv}(\mathbb{K}(s))\}} \left| \delta^\top \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbf{X}_i \mathbf{X}_i^\top - \Sigma \right) \delta \right|.$$

By Lemma F.3 in the supplementary material of Basu and Michailidis (2015), we have

$$\sup_{\delta \in \text{Cl}\{\text{conv}(\mathbb{K}(s))\}} \left| \delta^\top \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbf{X}_i \mathbf{X}_i^\top - \Sigma \right) \delta \right| \leq 3 \sup_{\delta \in \mathbb{K}(2s)} \left| \delta^\top \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbf{X}_i \mathbf{X}_i^\top - \Sigma \right) \delta \right|.$$

Therefore

$$\sup_{\delta \in (\alpha+2) \text{Cl}\{\text{conv}(\mathbb{K}(s))\}} \left| \delta^\top \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbf{X}_i \mathbf{X}_i^\top - \Sigma \right) \delta \right| \leq 3(\alpha+2)^2 \sup_{\delta \in \mathbb{K}(2s)} \left| \delta^\top \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbf{X}_i \mathbf{X}_i^\top - \Sigma \right) \delta \right|.$$

Thus

$$\frac{1}{3(\alpha+2)^2} \sup_{\delta \in \mathbb{A} \cup \mathbb{B}_2(1)} \left| \delta^\top \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbf{X}_i \mathbf{X}_i^\top - \Sigma \right) \delta \right| \leq \sup_{\delta \in \mathbb{K}(2s)} \left| \delta^\top \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbf{X}_i \mathbf{X}_i^\top - \Sigma \right) \delta \right|. \quad (\text{S1.2})$$

By expressions (S1.1) and (S1.2), it follows that

$$\mathbb{P} \left\{ \sup_{\delta \in \mathbb{A} \cup \mathbb{B}_2(1)} \left| \delta^\top \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbf{X}_i \mathbf{X}_i^\top - \Sigma \right) \delta \right| \geq c_1 t \right\} \leq 2 \exp \left\{ -cn \min \left(\frac{t^2}{\sigma_x^4}, \frac{t}{\sigma_x^2} \right) + 2s \log p \right\},$$

where $c_1 = 3(\alpha+2)^2$. Now upon choosing,

$$t = c_0 \sigma_x^2 \left(\sqrt{\frac{s \log(np)}{n}} + \frac{s \log(np)}{n} \right),$$

where c_0 is a sufficiently large constant, and using similar arguments in Remark S1.1, we verify that

$$cn \min \left(\frac{t^2}{\sigma_x^4}, \frac{t}{\sigma_x^2} \right) = c \min(c_0^2, c_0) s \log(np).$$

Hence, with probability at least $1 - n^{-5}$,

$$\sup_{\delta \in \mathbb{A} \cup \mathbb{B}_2(1)} \left| \delta^\top \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbf{X}_i \mathbf{X}_i^\top - \Sigma \right) \delta \right| \leq C_1 \left(\sqrt{\frac{s \log(np)}{n}} + \frac{s \log(np)}{n} \right),$$

where $C_1 > 0$ is a sufficiently large constant depending on constants $c_0, c_1, \sigma_x > 0$.

Step 2. In addition, if $n \geq C_I s \log(np)$, then

$$t = c_0 \sigma_x^2 \left(\sqrt{\frac{s \log(np)}{n}} + \frac{s \log(np)}{n} \right) \leq 2c_0 c_1 \sigma_x^2 \sqrt{\frac{s \log(np)}{n}},$$

and therefore

$$\mathbb{P} \left\{ \sup_{\boldsymbol{\delta} \in \text{AU}\mathbb{B}_2(1)} \left| \boldsymbol{\delta}^\top \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbf{X}_i \mathbf{X}_i^\top - \boldsymbol{\Sigma} \right) \boldsymbol{\delta} \right| \geq C_2 \sqrt{\frac{s \log(np)}{n}} \right\} \leq n^{-5}.$$

Finally,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \boldsymbol{\delta}^\top \mathbf{X}_i \mathbf{X}_i^\top \boldsymbol{\delta} &\geq \boldsymbol{\delta}^\top \boldsymbol{\Sigma} \boldsymbol{\delta} - \left| \boldsymbol{\delta}^\top \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbf{X}_i \mathbf{X}_i^\top - \boldsymbol{\Sigma} \right) \boldsymbol{\delta} \right| \\ &\geq \underline{\rho}_x \|\boldsymbol{\delta}\|_2^2 - C_2 \sqrt{\frac{s \log(np)}{n}} \|\boldsymbol{\delta}\|_2^2 \\ &\geq \frac{\underline{\rho}_x}{2} \|\boldsymbol{\delta}\|_2^2. \end{aligned}$$

Step 3. By Lemma 15 in the supplementary material of Loh and Wainwright (2012), it can be shown that the expression (S1.1) in turn implies that for all $\boldsymbol{\delta} \in \mathbb{R}^p$,

$$\left| \boldsymbol{\delta}^\top \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbf{X}_i \mathbf{X}_i^\top - \boldsymbol{\Sigma} \right) \boldsymbol{\delta} \right| \leq 27t \left(\|\boldsymbol{\delta}\|_2^2 + \frac{1}{s} \|\boldsymbol{\delta}\|_1^2 \right)$$

with probability at least

$$1 - 2 \exp \left\{ -cn \min \left(\frac{t^2}{\sigma_x^4}, \frac{t}{\sigma_x^2} \right) + 2s \log p \right\}.$$

The rest of the proof is similar to the proof of **Step 1-2** and is omitted for brevity.

This completes the proof. ■

Proof [Proof for Lemma 27] The part (i) follows from a union bound by Lemma 25(i).

For the part (ii), for any fixed $a \in [p]$, let

$$Z_i = \mathbf{w}^\top \mathbf{X}_i X_{i,a} - \mathbf{w}^\top \boldsymbol{\Sigma}(\cdot, a),$$

where $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}(\cdot, a)$ denote the a -th column of $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}$. Note that Z_i is sub-Exponential random variable. Using similar arguments as for proof of Lemma 25's part(ii), we have that with probability at least $1 - n^{-5}$ that

$$\left| \sum_{i=1}^r (\mathbf{w}^\top \mathbf{X}_i X_{i,a} - \mathbf{w}^\top \boldsymbol{\Sigma}(\cdot, a)) \right| \leq C_1 \left(\sqrt{r \log(np)} + \log(np) \right).$$

Then by another union bound, we can get desired result. ■

Proof [Proof for Lemma 28] The desired result follows from a union bound by Lemma 26(i)(Appendix). ■

S1.2.2 TEMPORAL DEPENDENCE SETTING

Proof [Proof for Lemma 25']

While part (i) directly restates Lemma 30 of Xu et al. (2024), parts (ii)-(iii) present mild extensions to Lemma 31 in the same reference. The omitted proofs for these extensions follow similar but simplified logical structures compared to the original arguments. ■

Proof [Proof for Lemma 26'] Parts (i)-(ii) restate Lemma 33 from Xu et al. (2024). The proof of part (iii) follows similar arguments to Step 3 in the proof of Lemma 26 and is therefore omitted. ■

Proof [Proof for Lemma 28'] The desired result follows from a union bound by Lemma 26'(i)(Appendix). ■

S2 Detailed proof for change point estimators

This section provides the proofs of the main change point estimation results in Theorems 4 (Main Paper) and 7 (Main Paper).

We begin with the first-step output $\widehat{\mathcal{T}}_k = \{\hat{t}_1, \dots, \hat{t}_k\}$, whose full proof is presented in Section S2.1 (Main Paper). Specifically, we first reformulate the recursive problem (11) (Main Paper) into a grouped structure. Then, for any $j \in [k^* + 1]$, based on Proposition 5, we show that (i) $\hat{k} = k$ with high probability and (ii) the raw estimated locations $\{\hat{u}_j\}_{j \in \mathcal{G}_j}$ whose index belong the same index group coincide and are not far from the corresponding true change point t_j^* . Using this grouping structure (S0.5), we recursively sharpen the raw estimated locations from a $\Delta/4$ -level neighborhood of the true change points to a near-optimal rate. The recursion proceeds in reverse order: starting from \mathcal{G}_{k^*+1} (Section S2.1.1), then \mathcal{G}_{k^*} (Section S2.1.2), \mathcal{G}_{k^*-1} (Section S2.1.3), and continuing down to the remaining groups $\mathcal{G}_{k^*-2}, \dots, \mathcal{G}_1$. The proof employs a fundamentally different strategy from prior literature on change point estimation via DP. Instead of jointly analyzing all change points globally (e.g., Rinaldo et al., 2021), we convert the multi-change-point problem into a backward recursive scheme that sharpens one change point at a time to achieve a suboptimal convergence rate. This key result is presented in Section S2.1.4.

The proof of the second-step estimators $\widehat{\mathcal{T}}_k^r = \{\hat{t}_1^r, \dots, \hat{t}_k^r\}$, which attain optimal convergence rates, is presented in Section S2.2. This argument closely follows the backward recursive structure introduced in Section S2.1, and is even more streamlined since it is developed under the high-probability event (19). In Section S2.2.1, we establish the convergence of the final change point \hat{t}_k^r , and then in Section S2.2.2, through the backward recurrence relation (S2.34), we similarly show the convergence of $\hat{t}_{k-1}^r, \dots, \hat{t}_1^r$. Once again, this reduction from simultaneous multiple change point estimation to sequential single change point optimization forms the central idea of proof, and is highlighted in Section S2.2.2. The supporting Lemma 36 (Appendix) used in Theorem 7 (Main Paper) is proved under two different model settings in Section S2.3.

S2.1 Proof for Theorem 4

Recall the DP recursion in (10) (Main Paper) for any $v \in [n]$:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{F}(v; \tilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_1) &= \mathcal{L}(0, v; \tilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_1) + \gamma, \\ \mathcal{F}(v; \tilde{\boldsymbol{\Theta}}(k+1)) &= \min_{u \leq v} \left\{ \underbrace{\mathcal{F}(u; \tilde{\boldsymbol{\Theta}}(k)) + \mathcal{L}(u, v; \tilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{k+1})}_{\mathcal{Q}_k(u, v)} + \gamma \mathbb{I}(u \neq v) \right\}, \quad k \in [\tilde{k}], \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S2.1})$$

Based on , we can obtain $\{\mathcal{F}(v; \tilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_1), v \in [n]\}$, $\{\mathcal{F}(v; \tilde{\boldsymbol{\Theta}}(2)), v \in [n]\}$, \dots , and $\{\mathcal{F}(v; \tilde{\boldsymbol{\Theta}}(\tilde{k}+1)), v \in [n]\}$, where \tilde{k} is number of the initializers. In other words, for any fixed point $v \in [n]$ and given *initial estimated parameters* $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\Theta}}(k+1)$, assume that there are $k \in [\tilde{k}]$ raw estimated locations (which may be equal), then $\mathcal{F}(v; \tilde{\boldsymbol{\Theta}}(k+1))$ represent the optimal loss value over the data \mathcal{Z}_0^v from (9) (Main Paper), i.e.,

$$\mathcal{F}(v; \tilde{\boldsymbol{\Theta}}(k+1)) = \min_{u \in \mathbb{U}_k(v)} \left\{ \sum_{\tilde{j}=1}^{k+1} \left[\mathcal{L}(u_{\tilde{j}-1}, u_{\tilde{j}}; \tilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{\tilde{j}}) + \gamma \mathbb{I}(u_{\tilde{j}-1} \neq u_{\tilde{j}}) \right] \right\}.$$

Then the *raw estimated locations* $\hat{\mathcal{U}}_{\tilde{k}} = \{\hat{u}_j\}_{j=1}^{\tilde{k}} \in \mathbb{U}_{\tilde{k}}(n)$ results from solving the following optimization problem by a simplified DP procedure:

$$\hat{u}_{\tilde{j}} = \arg \min_{u \leq \hat{u}_{\tilde{j}+1}} \left\{ \mathcal{Q}_{\tilde{j}}(u, \hat{u}_{\tilde{j}+1}) + \mathbb{I}(u \neq \hat{u}_{\tilde{j}+1}) \right\}, \quad \tilde{j} \in [\tilde{k}]^-,$$

where $\mathcal{Q}_{\tilde{j}}(u, v)$ defined in (S2.1). This is a recursive process moving from back to front. For greater clarity, the process can be expanded into the following form:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{u}_{\tilde{k}+1} &= n, & \text{when } \tilde{j} &= \tilde{k} + 1; \\ \hat{u}_{\tilde{k}} &= \arg \min_{u \leq \hat{u}_{\tilde{k}+1}} \left\{ \mathcal{Q}_{\tilde{k}}(u, n) + \gamma \mathbb{I}(u \neq n) \right\}, & \text{when } \tilde{j} &= \tilde{k}; \\ \hat{u}_{\tilde{k}-1} &= \arg \min_{u \leq \hat{u}_{\tilde{k}}} \left\{ \mathcal{Q}_{\tilde{k}-1}(u, \hat{u}_{\tilde{k}}) + \gamma \mathbb{I}(u \neq \hat{u}_{\tilde{k}}) \right\}, & \text{when } \tilde{j} &= \tilde{k} - 1; \\ &\vdots & &\vdots \\ \hat{u}_2 &= \arg \min_{u \leq \hat{u}_3} \left\{ \mathcal{Q}_2(u, \hat{u}_3) + \gamma \mathbb{I}(u \neq \hat{u}_3) \right\}, & \text{when } \tilde{j} &= 2; \\ \hat{u}_1 &= \arg \min_{u \leq \hat{u}_2} \left\{ \mathcal{Q}_1(u, \hat{u}_2) + \gamma \mathbb{I}(u \neq \hat{u}_2) \right\}, & \text{when } \tilde{j} &= 1. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S2.2})$$

It can be observed that the above recursive process is the mathematical explicit expression in Algorithm 1.

With any given set of \tilde{k} locations $\mathcal{U} \in \mathbb{U}_{\tilde{k}}(n)$, they can all be classified into $k^* + 1$ groups based on their indices, following the index group definition (S0.5). Obviously, the raw estimated locations $\hat{\mathcal{U}}_{\tilde{k}} = \{\hat{u}_j\}_{j=1}^{\tilde{k}} \in \mathbb{U}_{\tilde{k}}(n)$ can be further expressed as

$$\underbrace{\hat{u}_{\hat{h}(1)} \leq \dots \leq \hat{u}_{m(1)}}_{\mathfrak{g}_1} \leq \dots \leq \underbrace{\hat{u}_{\hat{h}(j)} \leq \dots \leq \hat{u}_{m(j)}}_{\mathfrak{g}_j} \leq \dots \leq \underbrace{\hat{u}_{\hat{h}(k^*+1)} \leq \dots \leq \hat{u}_{m(k^*+1)}}_{\mathfrak{g}_{k^*+1}} = n.$$

Based on the aforementioned group discussion, the previous recursive process (S2.2) can be innovatively rewritten in the following grouped form.

$$\tilde{j} \in \mathcal{G}_{k^*+1} \left\{ \begin{array}{ll} \hat{u}_{m(k^*+1)} = \hat{u}_{\tilde{k}+1} = n, & \tilde{j} = m(k^*+1) = \tilde{k}+1; \\ \hat{u}_{m(k^*+1)-1} = \arg \min_{u \leq \hat{u}_{m(k^*+1)}=n} \left\{ \mathcal{Q}_{m(k^*+1)-1}(u, n) + \gamma \mathbb{I}(u \neq n) \right\}, & \tilde{j} = m(k^*+1) - 1; \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ \hat{u}_{\tilde{h}(k^*+1)} = \arg \min_{u \leq \hat{u}_{\tilde{h}(k^*+1)+1}} \left\{ \mathcal{Q}_{\tilde{h}(k^*+1)}(u, \hat{u}_{\tilde{h}(k^*+1)+1}) + \gamma \mathbb{I}(u \neq \hat{u}_{\tilde{h}(k^*+1)+1}) \right\}, & \tilde{j} = \tilde{h}(k^*+1); \end{array} \right. \quad (\text{S2.3})$$

$$\tilde{j} \in \mathcal{G}_{k^*} \left\{ \begin{array}{ll} \hat{u}_{m(k^*)} = \arg \min_{u \leq \hat{u}_{\tilde{h}(k^*+1)}} \left\{ \mathcal{Q}_{m(k^*)}(u, \hat{u}_{\tilde{h}(k^*+1)}) + \gamma \mathbb{I}(u \neq \hat{u}_{\tilde{h}(k^*+1)}) \right\}, & \tilde{j} = m(k^*); \\ \hat{u}_{m(k^*)-1} = \arg \min_{u \leq \hat{u}_{m(k^*)}} \left\{ \mathcal{Q}_{m(k^*)-1}(u, \hat{u}_{m(k^*)}) + \gamma \mathbb{I}(u \neq \hat{u}_{m(k^*)}) \right\}, & \tilde{j} = m(k^*) - 1; \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ \hat{u}_{\tilde{h}(k^*)} = \arg \min_{u \leq \hat{u}_{\tilde{h}(k^*)+1}} \left\{ \mathcal{Q}_{\tilde{h}(k^*)}(u, \hat{u}_{\tilde{h}(k^*)+1}) + \gamma \mathbb{I}(u \neq \hat{u}_{\tilde{h}(k^*)+1}) \right\}, & \tilde{j} = \tilde{h}(k^*); \end{array} \right. \quad (\text{S2.4})$$

$$\begin{array}{ll} \vdots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ \tilde{j} \in \mathcal{G}_1 \left\{ \begin{array}{ll} \hat{u}_{m(1)} = \arg \min_{u \leq \hat{u}_{\tilde{h}(2)}} \left\{ \mathcal{Q}_{m(1)}(u, \hat{u}_{\tilde{h}(2)}) + \gamma \mathbb{I}(u \neq \hat{u}_{\tilde{h}(2)}) \right\}, & \tilde{j} = m(1); \\ \hat{u}_{m(1)-1} = \arg \min_{u \leq \hat{u}_{m(1)}} \left\{ \mathcal{Q}_{m(1)-1}(u, \hat{u}_{m(1)}) + \gamma \mathbb{I}(u \neq \hat{u}_{m(1)}) \right\}, & \tilde{j} = m(1) - 1; \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ \hat{u}_{\tilde{h}(1)} = \arg \min_{u \leq \hat{u}_{\tilde{h}(1)+1}} \left\{ \mathcal{Q}_{\tilde{h}(1)}(u, \hat{u}_{\tilde{h}(1)+1}) + \gamma \mathbb{I}(u \neq \hat{u}_{\tilde{h}(1)+1}) \right\}, & \tilde{j} = \tilde{h}(1); \end{array} \right. \end{array}$$

In this section, we will establish that the following two statements hold with high probability. In particular, it holds that

$$(a) \quad \hat{u}_{\tilde{h}(j)} = \hat{u}_{\tilde{h}(j)+1} = \cdots = \hat{u}_{m(j)-1} = \hat{u}_{m(j)}, \quad \text{for any } j \in [k^*+1]; \quad (\text{S2.5})$$

$$(b) \quad |\hat{u}_{m(j)} - t_j^*| \leq C_\epsilon s \log(np) / \kappa_j^2, \quad \text{for any } j \in [k^*]. \quad (\text{S2.6})$$

where $C_\epsilon > 0$ is an absolute constant. Regarding statement (a), this indicates that if the indices of the raw estimated locations belong to the same index group, they will share the same location. Simply put, the raw estimated locations within the same group will be **right-merged** to $\hat{u}_{m(j)}$. Since the raw estimated location $\hat{u}_{m(k^*+1)} = n$ corresponding to the

last index group \mathcal{G}_{k^*+1} , it indirectly leads to the conclusion that $\hat{k} = k^*$. Subsequently, (b) implies that the merged raw estimated location for each group will lie within a neighborhood of the true change point at a near-optimal rate. We emphasize that the premise for proving the above two conclusions (a) and (b) relies on the technical results of Proposition 5 (Main Paper). According to Proposition 5 (Main Paper), the raw estimated locations $\{\hat{u}_{\tilde{j}}^{\tilde{k}}\}_{\tilde{j}}$ generated by the ℓ_0 -regularized problem (8) (Main Paper) must satisfy condition (a) and $|\hat{u}_{m(j)} - t_j^*| < \Delta/4$. Therefore, the proof of Theorem 4(i) (Main Paper) is complete. The following discussion is conducted under the event

$$\mathcal{E}_2 = \{\hat{k} = k^*\}, \quad (\text{S2.7})$$

which holds with probability at least $1 - n^{-5}$.

In the remaining part of this section, we discuss statements (b) separately based on the index groups. Given that the above recursive process operates in reverse order, we begin by analyzing \mathcal{G}_{k^*+1} .

S2.1.1 INDEX GROUP \mathcal{G}_{k^*+1}

This group's proof is remarkably straightforward. Given that $\hat{u}_{m(k^*+1)} = n$, Proposition 5(ii) ensures that

$$\hat{u}_{\hat{h}(k^*+1)} = \hat{u}_{\hat{h}(k^*+1)+1} = \cdots = \hat{u}_{m(k^*+1)-1} = \hat{u}_{m(k^*+1)} = n. \quad (\text{S2.8})$$

In other words, we have $\hat{u}_{\tilde{j}} = n$ for any $\tilde{j} \in \mathcal{G}_{k^*+1}$.

S2.1.2 INDEX GROUP \mathcal{G}_{k^*}

In this subsection, we simplify the notation

$$\begin{aligned} \{\hat{h}(k^* - 1), \dots, m(k^* - 1)\} &\Rightarrow \{\hat{h}_-, \dots, m_-\}; \\ \{\hat{h}(k^*), \dots, m(k^*)\} &\Rightarrow \{\hat{h}, \dots, m\}; \\ \{\hat{h}(k^* + 1), \dots, m(k^* + 1)\} &\Rightarrow \{\hat{h}_+, \dots, m_+\}. \end{aligned}$$

Besides this, all other index notations remain unchanged. In the index group \mathcal{G}_{k^*} , our goal is to prove that

$$|\hat{u}_m - t_{k^*}^*| \leq \frac{C_\epsilon s \log(np)}{\kappa_{k^*}^2}, \quad (\text{S2.9})$$

with high probability. By Proposition 5(ii), we have

$$\hat{u}_{\hat{h}} = \hat{u}_{\hat{h}+1} = \cdots = \hat{u}_{m-1} = \hat{u}_m. \quad (\text{S2.10})$$

In addition, from Proposition 5(i), we have that

$$|\hat{u}_m - t_{k^*}^*| < \Delta/4.$$

We consider the case of $\hat{u}_m > t_{k^*}^*$, the symmetric case is similar.

Step 1: conversion to single change point minimization. Naturally, we set

$$u_{\hat{f}_+}^* = \cdots = u_m^* = t_{k^*}^*. \quad (\text{S2.11})$$

Given that the recursive process (S2.3) proceeds in reverse, and we have confirmed in (S2.8) that $\hat{u}_{\hat{f}_+} = n$, it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{u}_m &= \arg \min_{u \leq \hat{u}_{\hat{f}_+} = n} \left\{ \mathcal{Q}_m(u, \hat{u}_{\hat{f}_+}) + \gamma \mathbb{I}(u \neq \hat{u}_{\hat{f}_+}) \right\} \\ &= \arg \min_{u \leq n} \left\{ \mathcal{Q}_m(u, n) + \gamma \mathbb{I}(u \neq n) \right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S2.12})$$

Let's define that

$$\mathcal{R}(\hat{u}_m) = \mathcal{Q}_m(\hat{u}_m, n) - \mathcal{Q}_m(u_m^*, n), \quad (\text{S2.13})$$

$$\mathcal{S}(\hat{u}_m) = \mathcal{R}(\hat{u}_m) + \gamma \left(\mathbb{I}(\hat{u}_m \neq n) - \mathbb{I}(u_m^* \neq n) \right). \quad (\text{S2.14})$$

where $\mathcal{Q}(\cdot, \cdot)$ as defined in (S2.1), that is,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Estimated } \mathcal{Q}\text{-function:} \quad & \mathcal{Q}_m(\hat{u}_m, n) = \mathcal{F}(\hat{u}_m; \tilde{\Theta}(m)) + \mathcal{L}(\hat{u}_m, n; \tilde{\theta}_{\hat{f}_+}), \\ \text{Oracle } \mathcal{Q}\text{-function:} \quad & \mathcal{Q}_m(u_m^*, n) = \mathcal{F}(u_m^*; \tilde{\Theta}(m)) + \mathcal{L}(u_m^*, n; \tilde{\theta}_{\hat{f}_+}). \end{aligned}$$

Thus, given that u_m^* is fixed, combining (S2.12) and (S2.14), we have that

$$\hat{u}_m = \arg \min_{u_m \leq n} \mathcal{S}(u_m), \quad \text{and} \quad \mathcal{S}(\hat{u}_m) \leq 0. \quad (\text{S2.15})$$

Recall that $\mathcal{H}(\mathfrak{l}, \mathfrak{r}; u_m^*)$ is defined in (30) for any \mathfrak{l} and \mathfrak{r} satisfying $0 \leq \mathfrak{l} \leq \mathfrak{r} \leq n$, in relation to the true change point u_m^* . Our goal is to establish that for any sequence satisfying

$$\mathfrak{l} > C_\epsilon \frac{s \log(np)}{\kappa_{k^*}^2},$$

the inequality

$$\inf_{u_m \in \mathcal{H}(\mathfrak{l}, \mathfrak{r}; u_m^*)} \mathcal{S}(u_m) > 0$$

holds, thereby yielding a contradiction to (S2.15).

Step 2: risk function $\mathcal{R}(\cdot)$ simplification. Recall (9), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{F}(\hat{u}_m; \tilde{\Theta}(m)) &= \min_{u \in \mathbb{U}_{m-1}(\hat{u}_m)} \left\{ \sum_{\tilde{j}=1}^{m-1} \mathcal{L}(u_{\tilde{j}-1}, u_{\tilde{j}}; \tilde{\theta}_{\tilde{j}}) + \gamma \sum_{\tilde{j}=1}^{m-1} \mathbb{I}(u_{\tilde{j}-1} \neq u_{\tilde{j}}) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \mathcal{L}(u_{m-1}, \hat{u}_m; \tilde{\theta}_m) + \gamma \mathbb{I}(u_{m-1} \neq \hat{u}_m) \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S2.16})$$

Rewriting (S2.16) in a grouped form, it can be observed that

$$\mathcal{F}(\hat{u}_m; \tilde{\Theta}(m))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \min_{\substack{0 < u_{\hat{h}(1)} \leq \dots \leq u_{m(1)} \leq \dots \\ \dots \leq u_{\hat{h}_-} \leq \dots \leq u_{m_-} \leq u_{\hat{h}} \leq \dots \leq u_{m-1} \leq \hat{u}_m}} \left\{ \sum_{j=1}^{k^*-1} \sum_{\tilde{j}=\hat{h}(j)}^{m(j)} \mathcal{L}(u_{\tilde{j}-1}, u_{\tilde{j}}; \tilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{\tilde{j}}) + \gamma \sum_{j=1}^{k^*-1} \sum_{\tilde{j}=\hat{h}(j)}^{m(j)} \mathbb{I}(u_{\tilde{j}-1} \neq u_{\tilde{j}}) \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + \sum_{\tilde{j}=\hat{h}}^{m-1} \mathcal{L}(u_{\tilde{j}-1}, u_{\tilde{j}}; \tilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{\tilde{j}}) + \gamma \sum_{\tilde{j}=\hat{h}}^{m-1} \mathbb{I}(u_{\tilde{j}-1} \neq u_{\tilde{j}}) \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + \mathcal{L}(u_{m-1}, \hat{u}_m; \tilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_m) + \gamma \mathbb{I}(u_{m-1} \neq \hat{u}_m) \right\} \\
 &= \min_{\substack{0 < u_{\hat{h}(1)} \leq \dots \leq u_{m(1)} \leq \dots \\ \dots \leq u_{\hat{h}_-} \leq \dots \leq u_{m_-} \leq \hat{u}_{\hat{h}} \leq \dots \leq \hat{u}_{m-1} \leq \hat{u}_m}} \left\{ \sum_{j=1}^{k^*-1} \sum_{\tilde{j}=\hat{h}(j)}^{m(j)} \mathcal{L}(u_{\tilde{j}-1}, u_{\tilde{j}}; \tilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{\tilde{j}}) + \gamma \sum_{j=1}^{k^*-1} \sum_{\tilde{j}=\hat{h}(j)}^{m(j)} \mathbb{I}(u_{\tilde{j}-1} \neq u_{\tilde{j}}) \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + \mathcal{L}(u_{m_-}, \hat{u}_{\hat{h}}; \tilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{\hat{h}}) + \gamma \mathbb{I}(u_{m_-} \neq \hat{u}_{\hat{h}}) + \sum_{\tilde{j}=\hat{h}+1}^{m-1} \mathcal{L}(\hat{u}_{\tilde{j}-1}, \hat{u}_{\tilde{j}}; \tilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{\tilde{j}}) + \gamma \sum_{\tilde{j}=\hat{h}+1}^{m-1} \mathbb{I}(\hat{u}_{\tilde{j}-1} \neq \hat{u}_{\tilde{j}}) \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + \mathcal{L}(\hat{u}_{m-1}, \hat{u}_m; \tilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_m) + \gamma \mathbb{I}(\hat{u}_{m-1} \neq \hat{u}_m) \right\} \\
 &= \min_{\substack{0 < u_{\hat{h}(1)} \leq \dots \leq u_{m(1)} \leq \dots \\ \dots \leq u_{\hat{h}_-} \leq \dots \leq u_{m_-} \leq \hat{u}_{\hat{h}}}} \left\{ \sum_{j=1}^{k^*-1} \sum_{\tilde{j}=\hat{h}(j)}^{m(j)} \mathcal{L}(u_{\tilde{j}-1}, u_{\tilde{j}}; \tilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{\tilde{j}}) + \gamma \sum_{j=1}^{k^*-1} \sum_{\tilde{j}=\hat{h}(j)}^{m(j)} \mathbb{I}(u_{\tilde{j}-1} \neq u_{\tilde{j}}) \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + \mathcal{L}(u_{m_-}, \hat{u}_{\hat{h}}; \tilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{\hat{h}}) + \gamma \mathbb{I}(u_{m_-} \neq \hat{u}_{\hat{h}}) \right\} \tag{S2.17} \\
 &= \mathcal{F}(\hat{u}_{\hat{h}}; \tilde{\boldsymbol{\Theta}}(\hat{h})),
 \end{aligned}$$

where the first equality follows from grouped form of (9) (Main Paper), the second equality comes from the facts that equivalence between (S2.2) and (8) (Main Paper), and the penultimate equality follows from equation (S2.10) by Proposition 5(ii) (Main Paper).

Note that $u_m^* = t_{k^*}^*$, which implies that the solution $\hat{u}' = \{\hat{u}'_{\tilde{j}}\}_{\tilde{j}=1}^{m-1} \in \mathbb{U}_{m-1}(u_m^*)$ of $\mathcal{F}(u_m^*, \tilde{\boldsymbol{\Theta}}(m))$ must satisfy $\hat{u}'_{\hat{h}} = \dots = \hat{u}'_{m-1} = u_m^*$ from Proposition 5'. By the similar arguments, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\mathcal{F}(u_m^*, \tilde{\boldsymbol{\Theta}}(m)) \\
 &= \min_{\substack{0 < u_{\hat{h}(1)} \leq \dots \leq u_{m(1)} \leq \dots \\ \dots \leq u_{\hat{h}_-} \leq \dots \leq u_{m_-} \leq u_{\hat{h}}^*}} \left\{ \sum_{j=1}^{k^*-2} \sum_{\tilde{j}=\hat{h}(j)}^{m(j)} \mathcal{L}(u_{\tilde{j}-1}, u_{\tilde{j}}; \tilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{\tilde{j}}) + \gamma \sum_{j=1}^{k^*-2} \sum_{\tilde{j}=\hat{h}(j)}^{m(j)} \mathbb{I}(u_{\tilde{j}-1} \neq u_{\tilde{j}}) \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + \sum_{\tilde{j}=\hat{h}_-}^{m-} \mathcal{L}(u_{\tilde{j}-1}, u_{\tilde{j}}; \tilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{\tilde{j}}) + \gamma \sum_{\tilde{j}=\hat{h}_-}^{m-} \mathbb{I}(u_{\tilde{j}-1} \neq u_{\tilde{j}}) \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + \mathcal{L}(u_{m_-}, u_{\hat{h}}^*; \tilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{\hat{h}}) + \gamma \mathbb{I}(u_{m_-} \neq u_{\hat{h}}^*) \right\} \tag{S2.18} \\
 &= \mathcal{F}(u_{\hat{h}}^*, \tilde{\boldsymbol{\Theta}}(\hat{h})).
 \end{aligned}$$

Then, it holds with at least probability $1 - n^{-5}$

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{F}(\hat{u}_m; \tilde{\Theta}(m)) &= \mathcal{F}(\hat{u}_h; \tilde{\Theta}(h)), \\ \mathcal{F}(u_m^*; \tilde{\Theta}(m)) &= \mathcal{F}(u_h^*; \tilde{\Theta}(h)),\end{aligned}$$

which leads to

$$\mathcal{F}(\hat{u}_m; \tilde{\Theta}(m)) - \mathcal{F}(u_m^*; \tilde{\Theta}(m)) = \mathcal{F}(\hat{u}_h; \tilde{\Theta}(h)) - \mathcal{F}(u_h^*; \tilde{\Theta}(h)). \quad (\text{S2.19})$$

Since $\hat{u}_h > u_h^*$ from the fact $\hat{u}_m > u_m^*$, we further have that

$$\begin{aligned}(\text{S2.17}) &= \min_{\substack{0 < u_{h(1)} \leq \dots \leq u_{m(1)} \leq \dots \\ \dots \leq u_{h_-} \leq \dots \leq u_{m_-} \leq \hat{u}_h}} \left\{ \sum_{j=1}^{k^*-1} \sum_{\tilde{j}=h(j)}^{m(j)} \mathcal{L}(u_{\tilde{j}-1}, u_{\tilde{j}}; \tilde{\theta}_{\tilde{j}}) + \gamma \sum_{j=1}^{k^*-1} \sum_{\tilde{j}=h(j)}^{m(j)} \mathbb{I}(u_{\tilde{j}-1} \neq u_{\tilde{j}}) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \mathcal{L}(u_{m_-}, u_{h_-}^*; \tilde{\theta}_{h_-}) + \mathcal{L}(u_{h_-}^*, \hat{u}_h; \tilde{\theta}_{h_-}) + \gamma \mathbb{I}(u_{m_-} \neq \hat{u}_h) \right\}\end{aligned} \quad (\text{S2.20})$$

$$\begin{aligned}&= \min_{\substack{0 < u_{h(1)} \leq \dots \leq u_{m(1)} \leq \dots \\ \dots \leq u_{h_-} \leq \dots \leq u_{m_-} \leq \hat{u}_h}} \left\{ \sum_{j=1}^{k^*-1} \sum_{\tilde{j}=h(j)}^{m(j)} \mathcal{L}(u_{\tilde{j}-1}, u_{\tilde{j}}; \tilde{\theta}_{\tilde{j}}) + \gamma \sum_{j=1}^{k^*-1} \sum_{\tilde{j}=h(j)}^{m(j)} \mathbb{I}(u_{\tilde{j}-1} \neq u_{\tilde{j}}) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \mathcal{L}(u_{m_-}, u_{h_-}^*; \tilde{\theta}_{h_-}) + \gamma \mathbb{I}(u_{m_-} \neq u_{h_-}^*) \right\} + \mathcal{L}(u_{h_-}^*, \hat{u}_h; \tilde{\theta}_{h_-})\end{aligned} \quad (\text{S2.21})$$

$$= \mathcal{F}(u_{h_-}^*; \tilde{\Theta}(h)) + \mathcal{L}(u_{h_-}^*, \hat{u}_h; \tilde{\theta}_{h_-}) \quad (\text{S2.22})$$

$$= \mathcal{F}(u_{h_-}^*; \tilde{\Theta}(h)) + \mathcal{L}(u_m^*, \hat{u}_m; \tilde{\theta}_{h_-}). \quad (\text{S2.23})$$

Here, based on the Proposition 5, as the m_- elements in the solution $\{\hat{u}_{\tilde{j}}\}_{\tilde{j}=1}^{m_-}$ cannot fall within the interval $(u_{h_-}^*, \hat{u}_h]$, this naturally leads to (S2.20). Both $u_{h_-}^*$ and \hat{u}_h are fixed endpoints, the term $\mathcal{L}(u_{h_-}^*, \hat{u}_h; \tilde{\theta}_{h_-})$ can be extracted from the minimum optimization problem. Additionally, the last indicator function $\mathbb{I}(u_{m_-} \neq \hat{u}_h)$ of (S2.20) should be modified to $\mathbb{I}(u_{m_-} \neq u_{h_-}^*)$. Since the search range for the solution of (S2.20) has been redefined as $0 < u_{h(1)} \leq \dots \leq u_{m_-} \leq u_{h_-}^* \leq \hat{u}_h$, the determination of whether the final solution equals the right endpoint will now focus on the relationship between u_{m_-} and $u_{h_-}^*$, rather than between u_{m_-} and \hat{u}_h . The aforementioned two reasons form the basis for the validity of expression (S2.21). Expression (S2.22) holds due to the results of (S2.18) and (S2.21). By utilizing symbolic transformations derived from (S2.10) and (S2.11), it can verify that (S2.23). Combing (S2.19) and (S2.23), we have

$$\mathcal{F}(\hat{u}_m; \tilde{\Theta}(m)) - \mathcal{F}(u_m^*; \tilde{\Theta}(m)) = \mathcal{L}(u_m^*, \hat{u}_m; \tilde{\theta}_h), \quad (\text{S2.24})$$

and this equality holds with probability at least $1 - n^{-5}$. Hence, combining expression (S2.24) and the fact

$$\mathcal{L}(\hat{u}_m, n; \tilde{\theta}_{h_+}) - \mathcal{L}(u_m^*, n; \tilde{\theta}_{h_+}) = -\mathcal{L}(u_m^*, \hat{u}_m; \tilde{\theta}_{h_+}), \quad (\text{S2.25})$$

we have

$$\mathcal{R}(\hat{u}_m) = \mathcal{L}(u_m^*, \hat{u}_m; \tilde{\theta}_h) - \mathcal{L}(u_m^*, \hat{u}_m; \tilde{\theta}_{h_+}), \quad (\text{S2.26})$$

where $\mathcal{R}(\hat{u}_m)$ defined in (S2.13).

Some parts of the process from expressions (S2.13) to (S2.25) are illustrated in a simplified loss segmentation form in Figure S2.5. The loss segmentation illustrated with a

Figure S2.5: Intuitive explanation of construct $\mathcal{R}(\hat{u}_m)$ for case $\hat{u}_m > t_{k^*}^*$. The red triangles represent the true change points (u_j^* as defined in (S2.11)), while the blue rectangles represent the marker raw estimated locations (repeated locations are displayed in small parenthesis above the line). The brackets around the true change point $t_{k^*-1}^*$ and $t_{k^*}^*$ represent the upper bound of a neighborhood with a radius of $\Delta/4$. Only the part related to the index groups $\mathcal{G}_{k^*-1}, \mathcal{G}_{k^*}$ are shown here.

red horizontal brace below the line corresponds to the oracle \mathcal{Q} -function, while the blue horizontal brace above the line represents the estimated \mathcal{Q} -function, as defined in (S2.13). Subtracting the lower dashed red brace from the upper dashed blue brace yields equation (S2.24), while subtracting the lower solid red brace from the upper solid blue brace yields equation (S2.25). Hence, by subtracting the lower red brace parts from the upper blue brace parts, we obtain the risk function $\mathcal{R}(\hat{u}_m)$ in (S2.26).

Thus, (S2.15) can be further rewritten as the following optimization problem, which plays a crucial role in the proof:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{u}_m &= \arg \min_{u_m \leq n} \mathcal{S}(u_m) \\ &= \arg \min_{u_m \leq n} \left\{ \mathcal{L}(u_m^*, u_m; \tilde{\theta}_f) - \mathcal{L}(u_m^*, u_m; \tilde{\theta}_{f+}) \right\}, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S2.27})$$

where the last inequality follows from the fact that

$$\gamma \left(\mathbb{I}(u_m \neq n) - \mathbb{I}(u_m^* \neq n) \right) = \gamma(1 - 1) = 0,$$

from $|u_m - u_m^*| < \Delta/4$ by Proposition 5(i). It is worth noting that the mirroring case $\hat{u}_m \leq u_m^*$ results in an expression analogous to (S2.27), specifically $\mathcal{L}(u_m, u_m^*; \tilde{\theta}_f) - \mathcal{L}(u_m, u_m^*; \tilde{\theta}_{f+})$, derived using symmetric arguments.

Step 3: locating \hat{u}_m via risk function $\mathcal{S}(\cdot)$. Now we introduce the following lemma, which establishes a uniform lower bound for the expression $\mathcal{S}(\cdot)$ over the collection $\mathcal{H}(\mathfrak{l}, \mathfrak{r}; u_m^*)$, as defined in (30), with high probability.

Lemma S2.3 *Suppose Assumptions 2 and 3a hold, and the initial parameter estimator $\tilde{\theta}_{\hat{\kappa}}$ and $\tilde{\theta}_{\hat{\kappa}_+}$ satisfy the results of Theorem 3 under their respective models. Let $0 \leq \mathfrak{l}_n \leq \mathfrak{r}_n \leq \Delta_n/4$ be any non-negative sequences, where $\mathfrak{l}_n = \mathfrak{l}/n$ and $\mathfrak{r}_n = \mathfrak{r}/n$. Then for absolute constant $c_1, c_2 > 0$, it holds with probability at least $1 - o(1)$.*

$$\inf_{u_m \in \mathcal{H}(\mathfrak{l}, \mathfrak{r}; u_m^*)} \mathcal{S}_n(u_m) \geq c_1 \kappa_{k^*}^2 \left(\mathfrak{l}_n - \frac{c_2}{\kappa_{k^*}} \sqrt{\frac{\mathfrak{r}_n s \log(np)}{n}} \right),$$

where $\mathcal{S}_n(\cdot) = \mathcal{S}(\cdot)/n$.

Proof [Proof of Lemma S2.3] Throughout this proof, we denote $\mathcal{I} = (u_m^*, u_m] \subset (t_{k^*}^*, n]$, where $u_m^* < u_m \leq u_m^* + \Delta/4$. If $u_m - u_m^* \leq C_\epsilon s \log(np)/\kappa_{k^*}^2$, then there is nothing to show. Assuming without loss of generality that $\mathfrak{l} > C_\epsilon s \log(np)/\kappa_{k^*}^2$.

We now discuss lower bound for $\mathcal{S}(u_m)$ under two models. Following an argument parallel to

- (S3.19) presented in the Proof of Lemma S3.5(ii) under model (2) (Main Paper),
- (S3.27) presented in the Proof of Lemma S3.7(ii) under model (3) (Main Paper),

we derive the following result, which holds with probability at least $1 - n^{-5}$:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{S}(u_m) &= \mathcal{L}(u_m^*, u_m; \tilde{\theta}_{\hat{\kappa}}) - \mathcal{L}(u_m^*, u_m; \tilde{\theta}_{\hat{\kappa}_+}) \\ &\geq C_1 |\mathcal{I}| \kappa_{k^*}^2 - C_2 \sqrt{|\mathcal{I}| s \log(np)} \kappa_{k^*}. \end{aligned}$$

By the fact that $\mathfrak{l} \leq |\mathcal{I}| \leq \mathfrak{r}$ for collection $\mathcal{H}(\mathfrak{l}, \mathfrak{r}; u_m^*)$, we obtain,

$$\begin{aligned} \inf_{u_m \in \mathcal{H}(\mathfrak{l}, \mathfrak{r}; u_m^*)} \mathcal{S}_n(u_m) &\geq C_1 \mathfrak{l}_n \kappa_{k^*}^2 - C_2 \kappa_{k^*} \sqrt{\frac{\mathfrak{r}_n s \log(np)}{n}} \\ &\geq C_1 \kappa_{k^*}^2 \left(\mathfrak{l}_n - \frac{C_2}{C_1 \kappa_{k^*}} \sqrt{\frac{\mathfrak{r}_n s \log(np)}{n}} \right). \end{aligned}$$

■

The proof of (S2.9) uses a recursive approach based on Lemma S2.3, where the rate of convergence is improved step by step through repeated recursions. We begin by considering any $\mathfrak{l} > 0$ and applying Lemma S2.3 on the set $\mathcal{H}(\mathfrak{l}, \Delta/4; u_m^*)$ to obtain,

$$\begin{aligned} \inf_{u_m \in \mathcal{H}(\mathfrak{l}, \Delta/4; u_m^*)} \mathcal{S}_n(u_m) &\geq c_1 \kappa_{k^*}^2 \left(\mathfrak{l}_n - \frac{c_2}{\kappa_{k^*}} \sqrt{\frac{\Delta_n s \log(np)}{4n}} \right) \\ &\geq c_1 \kappa_{k^*}^2 \left(\mathfrak{l}_n - \underbrace{\frac{c_2}{\kappa_{k^*}} \sqrt{\frac{s \log(np)}{n}}}_{\mathfrak{l}_n^*} \right), \end{aligned}$$

with probability at least $1 - n^{-5}$, where the last inequality follows from $\Delta_n/4 < 1$. By selecting any

$$\mathfrak{l}_n > \mathfrak{l}_n^* := \frac{c_2}{\kappa_{k^*}} \sqrt{\frac{s \log(np)}{n}},$$

while ensuring that $\mathfrak{l}_n \leq \Delta_n/4$, it follows that $\inf_{u \in \mathcal{H}(\mathfrak{l}, \Delta/4; u_m^*)} \mathcal{S}_n(u_m) > 0$ for sufficiently large n . This leads to the condition that $\hat{u}_m \notin \mathcal{H}(\mathfrak{l}, \Delta/4; u_m^*)$. Additionally, by Proposition 5(i) (Main Paper), where $|\hat{u}_m - u_m^*| < \Delta/4$, it can be deduced that $|\hat{u}_m - u_m^*| \leq n\mathfrak{l}_n^*$. Now reset $\mathfrak{r}_n = \mathfrak{l}_n^*$ and reapply Lemma S2.3 for any $\mathfrak{l}_n > 0$ to obtain,

$$\inf_{u_m \in \mathcal{H}(\mathfrak{l}, \mathfrak{r}; u_m^*)} \mathcal{S}_n(u_m) \geq c_1 \kappa_{k^*}^2 \underbrace{\left\{ \mathfrak{l}_n - \left(\frac{c_2}{\kappa_{k^*}} \right)^{1+\frac{1}{2}} \left(\frac{s \log(np)}{n} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}+\frac{1}{4}} \right\}}_{\mathfrak{l}_n^*}$$

with probability at least $1 - n^{-5}$. By selecting

$$\mathfrak{l}_n \geq \mathfrak{l}_n^* := \left(\frac{c_2}{\kappa_{k^*}} \right)^{1+\frac{1}{2}} \left(\frac{s \log(np)}{n} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}+\frac{1}{4}},$$

it follows that $\inf_{u \in \mathcal{H}(\mathfrak{l}, \mathfrak{r}; u_m^*)} \mathcal{S}_n(u_m) > 0$ with probability at least $1 - n^{-5}$. Consequently, we have $\hat{u}_m \notin \mathcal{H}(\mathfrak{l}^*, \mathfrak{r}; u_m^*)$, which further implies that $|\hat{u}_m - u_m^*| \leq n\mathfrak{l}_n^*$. Note that the recursive discussions defined above enable the progressive refinement of the desired rate at each step. Next, By resetting \mathfrak{r}_n according to the bounds derived from the preceding recursion and employing Lemma S2.3 to continue this recursive process, we obtain the j -th recursion

$$|\hat{u}_m - u_m^*| \leq n \left(\frac{c_2}{\kappa_{k^*}} \right)^{a_j} \left(\frac{s \log(np)}{n} \right)^{b_j},$$

with probability at least $1 - n^{-5}$, where

$$a_j = \sum_{i=1}^j \frac{1}{2^{i-1}}, \quad \text{and} \quad b_j = \sum_{i=1}^j \frac{1}{2^i}.$$

Repeating these recursions an infinite number of times and noting that $a_\infty = 2$ and $b_\infty = 1$, it holds with probability at least $1 - n^{-5}$,

$$|\hat{u}_m - u_m^*| \leq n \left(\frac{c_2}{\kappa_{k^*}} \right)^2 \left(\frac{s \log(np)}{n} \right)^1 = \frac{C_\epsilon s \log(np)}{\kappa_{k^*}^2}.$$

This completes the proof of result (S2.9).

S2.1.3 INDEX GROUP \mathcal{G}_{k^*-1}

In this subsection, we simplify the notation

$$\begin{aligned} \{\mathfrak{h}(k^* - 2), \dots, m(k^* - 2)\} &\Rightarrow \{\mathfrak{h}_-, \dots, m_-\}; \\ \{\mathfrak{h}(k^* - 1), \dots, m(k^* - 1)\} &\Rightarrow \{\mathfrak{h}, \dots, m\}; \\ \{\mathfrak{h}(k^*), \dots, m(k^*)\} &\Rightarrow \{\mathfrak{h}_+, \dots, m_+\}. \end{aligned}$$

Besides this, all other index notations remain unchanged. In the index group \mathcal{G}_{k^*-1} , our goal is to prove that

$$|\hat{u}_m - t_{k^*-1}^*| \leq \frac{C_\epsilon s \log(np)}{\kappa_{k^*-1}^2}, \quad (\text{S2.28})$$

with high probability. By Proposition 5, we have

$$\hat{u}_{\hat{h}} = \hat{u}_{\hat{h}+1} = \cdots = \hat{u}_{m-1} = \hat{u}_m, \quad \text{and} \quad |\hat{u}_m - t_{k^*-1}^*| < \Delta/4 \quad (\text{S2.29})$$

We consider the case of $\hat{u}_m > t_{k^*-1}^*$, the symmetric case is similar. The majority of the following arguments mirror those used for the index group \mathcal{G}_{k^*} . We omit the detailed explanations for similar part and focus on highlighting the differences.

Step 1 Naturally, we set

$$u_{\hat{h}}^* = \cdots = u_m^* = t_{k^*-1}^*. \quad (\text{S2.30})$$

Considering the backward recursive process (S2.4), under event (S2.7), we have verified in (S2.10) that

$$\hat{u}_{\hat{h}_+} = \cdots = \hat{u}_{m_+} = \hat{t}_{\hat{k}}.$$

By endpoint $\hat{t}_{\hat{k}}$, we can obtain that \mathcal{Q} -functions are

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{Q}_m(\hat{u}_m, \hat{t}_{\hat{k}}) &= \mathcal{F}(\hat{u}_m; \tilde{\Theta}(m)) + \mathcal{L}(\hat{u}_m, \hat{t}_{\hat{k}}; \tilde{\Theta}_{\hat{h}_+}), \\ \mathcal{Q}_m(u_m^*, \hat{t}_{\hat{k}}) &= \mathcal{F}(u_m^*; \tilde{\Theta}(m)) + \mathcal{L}(u_m^*, \hat{t}_{\hat{k}}; \tilde{\Theta}_{\hat{h}_+}). \end{aligned}$$

Now let's define

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{R}(\hat{u}_m) &= \mathcal{Q}_m(\hat{u}_m, \hat{t}_{\hat{k}}) - \mathcal{Q}_m(u_m^*, \hat{t}_{\hat{k}}), \\ \mathcal{S}(\hat{u}_m) &= \mathcal{R}(\hat{u}_m) + \gamma \left(\mathbb{I}(\hat{u}_m \neq \hat{t}_{\hat{k}}) - \mathbb{I}(u_m^* \neq \hat{t}_{\hat{k}}) \right), \end{aligned}$$

Thus, given that u_m^* is fixed, it holds that

$$\hat{u}_m = \arg \min_{u_m \leq \hat{t}_{\hat{k}}} \mathcal{S}(u_m), \quad \text{and} \quad \mathcal{S}(\hat{u}_m) \leq 0. \quad (\text{S2.31})$$

Step 2. Replacing the endpoint n in Step 2 of the index group \mathcal{G}_{k^*} with $\hat{t}_{\hat{k}}$, we establish the following with probability at least $1 - n^{-5}$:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{S}(\hat{u}_m) &= \mathcal{R}(\hat{u}_m) + \gamma \left(\mathbb{I}(\hat{u}_m \neq \hat{t}_{\hat{k}}) - \mathbb{I}(u_m^* \neq \hat{t}_{\hat{k}}) \right) \\ &= \left(\mathcal{F}(\hat{u}_m; \tilde{\Theta}(m)) - \mathcal{F}(u_m^*; \tilde{\Theta}(m)) \right) + \left(\mathcal{L}(\hat{u}_m, \hat{t}_{\hat{k}}; \tilde{\Theta}_{\hat{h}_+}) - \mathcal{L}(u_m^*, \hat{t}_{\hat{k}}; \tilde{\Theta}_{\hat{h}_+}) \right) \\ &= \mathcal{L}(u_m^*, \hat{u}_m; \tilde{\Theta}_{\hat{h}}) - \mathcal{L}(u_m^*, \hat{u}_m; \tilde{\Theta}_{\hat{h}_+}), \end{aligned}$$

where the second equality follows from $|\hat{u}_m - t_{k^*-1}^*| \leq \Delta/4$ in (S2.29) and $|\hat{t}_{\hat{k}} - t_{k^*}^*| \leq C_\epsilon s \log(np) / \kappa_{k^*}^2 < \Delta/4$ in (S2.9), and the last equality is similar to (S2.24) and (S2.25). Thus, (S2.31) can be further rewritten as the following optimization problem, which plays a crucial role in the proof:

$$\hat{u}_m = \arg \min_{u_m \leq \hat{t}_{\hat{k}}} \mathcal{S}(u_m)$$

$$= \arg \min_{u_m \leq \hat{t}_{\hat{k}}} \left\{ \mathcal{L}(u_m^*, u_m; \tilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{\hat{h}}) - \mathcal{L}(u_m^*, u_m; \tilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{\hat{h}_+}) \right\}, \quad (\text{S2.32})$$

The rest of the proof strictly follows the recursive process outlined in Step 3 of the index group \mathcal{G}_{k^*} , and therefore, this part is omitted for brevity. This completes the proof of result (S2.28).

S2.1.4 THE REST INDEX GROUP $\mathcal{G}_{k^*-2}, \dots, \mathcal{G}_1$

Recall $\{u_j^*\}_{j=1}^{\hat{k}}$ defined in (S0.7). Note that from (S2.5) we have proved that

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{u}_{h(k^*+1)} &= \dots = \hat{u}_{m(k^*+1)} = n; \\ \hat{u}_{h(k^*)} &= \dots = \hat{u}_{m(k^*)} = \hat{t}_{\hat{k}}; \\ \hat{u}_{h(k^*-1)} &= \dots = \hat{u}_{m(k^*-1)} = \hat{t}_{\hat{k}-1}; \\ \hat{u}_{h(k^*-2)} &= \dots = \hat{u}_{m(k^*-2)} = \hat{t}_{\hat{k}-2}; \\ &\vdots \qquad \qquad \qquad \vdots \\ \hat{u}_{h(2)} &= \dots = \hat{u}_{m(2)} = \hat{t}_2; \\ \hat{u}_{h(1)} &= \dots = \hat{u}_{m(1)} = \hat{t}_1. \end{aligned}$$

For the index groups \mathcal{G}_{k^*-1} and \mathcal{G}_{k^*} , we have proved that (S2.6) holds for $j \in \{k^*, k^* - 1\}$ with probability at least $1 - n^{-5}$. When bounding $|\hat{u}_{m(j)} - t_j^*|$ for $j \in [k^* - 2]$, we refer to reasoning similar to (S2.27) and (S2.32). The k^* steps of the backward recursive process are expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{u}_{m(k^*)} &= \arg \min_{u_{m(k^*)} \leq n} \left\{ \mathcal{L}(u_{m(k^*)}^*, u_{m(k^*)}; \tilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{h(k^*)}) - \mathcal{L}(u_{m(k^*)}^*, u_{m(k^*)}; \tilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{h(k^*+1)}) \right\}, \text{ where } u_{m(k^*)}^* = t_{k^*}^*, \hat{u}_{m(k^*)} = \hat{t}_{\hat{k}}; \\ \hat{u}_{m(k^*-1)} &= \arg \min_{u_{m(k^*-1)} \leq \hat{u}_{m(k^*)}} \left\{ \mathcal{L}(u_{m(k^*-1)}^*, u_{m(k^*-1)}; \tilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{h(k^*-1)}) - \mathcal{L}(u_{m(k^*-1)}^*, u_{m(k^*-1)}; \tilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{h(k^*)}) \right\}, \\ &\qquad \qquad \qquad \text{where } u_{m(k^*-1)}^* = t_{k^*-1}^*, \hat{u}_{m(k^*-1)} = \hat{t}_{\hat{k}-1}; \\ \hat{u}_{m(k^*-2)} &= \arg \min_{u_{m(k^*-2)} \leq \hat{u}_{m(k^*-1)}} \left\{ \mathcal{L}(u_{m(k^*-2)}^*, u_{m(k^*-2)}; \tilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{h(k^*-2)}) - \mathcal{L}(u_{m(k^*-2)}^*, u_{m(k^*-2)}; \tilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{h(k^*-1)}) \right\}, \\ &\qquad \qquad \qquad \text{where } u_{m(k^*-2)}^* = t_{k^*-2}^*, \hat{u}_{m(k^*-2)} = \hat{t}_{\hat{k}-2}; \\ &\vdots \qquad \qquad \qquad \vdots \\ \hat{u}_{m(1)} &= \arg \min_{u_{m(1)} \leq \hat{u}_{m_2}} \left\{ \mathcal{L}(u_{m(1)}^*, u_{m(1)}; \tilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{h(1)}) - \mathcal{L}(u_{m(1)}^*, u_{m(1)}; \tilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{h(2)}) \right\}, \text{ where } u_{m(1)}^* = t_1^*, \hat{u}_{m(1)} = \hat{t}_1. \end{aligned}$$

Naturally, by repeatedly using conclusions similar to Lemma S2.3 in the above minimization problem, we can show that the desired result (S2.6) holds with probability at least $1 - n^{-5}$:

$$\begin{aligned}
 |\hat{u}_{m(k^*)} - u_{m(k^*)}^*| &\leq \frac{C_\epsilon s \log(np)}{\kappa_{k^*}^2}; \\
 |\hat{u}_{m(k^*-1)} - u_{m(k^*-1)}^*| &\leq \frac{C_\epsilon s \log(np)}{\kappa_{k^*-1}^2}; \\
 |\hat{u}_{m(k^*-2)} - u_{m(k^*-2)}^*| &\leq \frac{C_\epsilon s \log(np)}{\kappa_{k^*-2}^2}; \\
 &\vdots \\
 |\hat{u}_{m(1)} - u_{m(1)}^*| &\leq \frac{C_\epsilon s \log(np)}{\kappa_1^2}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence, the full proof of Theorem 4 (Main Paper) is concluded.

S2.2 Proof for Theorem 7

Recall the DP recursion in (14) (Main Paper) for any $v \in [n]$ and given candidate number $k \in [\hat{k}]$:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{F}^r(v; \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_1) &= \mathcal{L}(0, v; \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_1), \\
 \mathcal{F}^r(v; \hat{\boldsymbol{\Theta}}(k+1)) &= \min_{t < v} \left\{ \underbrace{\mathcal{F}^r(t; \hat{\boldsymbol{\Theta}}(k)) + \mathcal{L}(t, v; \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{k+1})}_{\mathcal{Q}_k^r(t, v)} \right\}, \quad k \in [\hat{k}], \quad (\text{S2.33})
 \end{aligned}$$

Based on , we can obtain $\{\mathcal{F}^r(v; \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_1), v \in [n]\}$, $\{\mathcal{F}^r(v; \hat{\boldsymbol{\Theta}}(2)), v \in [n]\}$, \dots , and $\{\mathcal{F}^r(v; \hat{\boldsymbol{\Theta}}(\hat{k}+1)), v \in [n]\}$, where \hat{k} is number of preliminary change point estimators. Then the *refined estimated locations* $\hat{\mathcal{T}}_k^r = \{\hat{t}_j^r\}_{j=1}^{\hat{k}} \in \mathbb{T}_{\hat{k}}(n)$ results from solving the following optimization problem by a simplified DP procedure:

$$\hat{t}_j^r = \arg \min_{t < \hat{t}_{j+1}^r} \mathcal{Q}_j^r(t, \hat{t}_{j+1}^r), \quad j \in [\hat{k}]^-, \quad (\text{S2.34})$$

where $\mathcal{Q}_j^r(t, v)$ defined in (S2.33).

By Theorem 4 (Main Paper) , under Assumptions 1-3 (Main Paper) and the corresponding assumptions for different model examples (Assumptions 4-5, Appendix), the event (19) holds with probability at least $1 - n^{-5}$. Consequently, all subsequent discussions are conducted under the assumption that the event (19) holds, i.e., $\mathbb{P}\{\hat{k} = k^*\} \rightarrow 1$ as $n, p \rightarrow \infty$. From this point on, we do not distinguish between \hat{k} and k^* . In this section, our primary goal is to establish the following result with high probability: for any $j \in [k^*]$,

$$|\hat{t}_j^r - t_j^*| = O_p(1/\kappa_j^2) \quad (\text{S2.35})$$

In the remaining part of this section, we will sequentially verify the validity of (S2.35) according to the reverse index $[k^*]^-$. Since the recursive process (S2.34) operates in reverse, we first analyze the case for $j = k^*$.

S2.2.1 INDEX k^*

It is also worth noting that the estimate satisfies $|\hat{t}_k^r - t_{k^*}^*| \leq \Delta/4$ from Proposition 35 (Appendix).

Step 1: conversion to single change point minimization. By considering the reverse iteration procedure (S2.34), it follows that

$$\hat{t}_k^r = \arg \min_{t < n} \mathcal{Q}_k^r(t, n).$$

We define

$$\mathcal{R}^r(\hat{t}_k^r) = \mathcal{Q}_k^r(\hat{t}_k^r, n) - \mathcal{Q}_k^r(t_{k^*}^*, n),$$

where

$$\text{Estimated } \mathcal{Q}^r\text{-function:} \quad \mathcal{Q}_{\hat{k}}^r(\hat{t}_k^r, n) = \mathcal{F}^r(\hat{t}_k^r; \hat{\Theta}(\hat{k})) + \mathcal{L}(\hat{t}_k^r, n; \hat{\theta}_{\hat{k}+1}),$$

$$\text{Oracle } \mathcal{Q}^r\text{-function:} \quad \mathcal{Q}_{\hat{k}}^r(t_{k^*}^*, n) = \mathcal{F}^r(t_{k^*}^*; \hat{\Theta}(\hat{k})) + \mathcal{L}(t_{k^*}^*, n; \hat{\theta}_{\hat{k}+1}).$$

Since $t_{k^*}^*$ is fixed, it follows from the definition (S2.34) that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{R}^r(\hat{t}_k^r) &= \mathcal{Q}_{\hat{k}}^r(\hat{t}_k^r, n) - \mathcal{Q}_{\hat{k}}^r(t_{k^*}^*, n) \\ &= \mathcal{F}^r(\hat{t}_k^r; \hat{\Theta}(\hat{k})) - \mathcal{F}^r(t_{k^*}^*; \hat{\Theta}(\hat{k})) + \mathcal{L}(\hat{t}_k^r, n; \hat{\theta}_{\hat{k}+1}) - \mathcal{L}(t_{k^*}^*, n; \hat{\theta}_{\hat{k}+1}) \\ &\leq 0 \end{aligned}$$

Step 2: Risk function $\mathcal{R}^r(\cdot)$ simplification We first consider the case of $\hat{t}_k^r \geq t_{k^*}^*$. It can be verified that the following equalities hold with probability at least $1 - n^{-5}$.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{F}^r(\hat{t}_k^r; \hat{\Theta}(\hat{k})) &= \min_{\mathcal{T} \in \mathbb{T}_{\hat{k}-1}(\hat{t}_k^r)} \sum_{j=1}^{\hat{k}} \mathcal{L}(t_{j-1}, t_j; \hat{\theta}_j) \\ &= \min_{0 < t_1 < \dots < t_{\hat{k}-1} < \hat{t}_k^r} \left\{ \sum_{j=1}^{\hat{k}-1} \mathcal{L}(t_{j-1}, t_j; \hat{\theta}_j) + \mathcal{L}(t_{\hat{k}-1}, \hat{t}_k^r; \hat{\theta}_{\hat{k}}) \right\} \\ &= \min_{0 < t_1 < \dots < t_{\hat{k}-1} < \hat{t}_k^r} \left\{ \sum_{j=1}^{\hat{k}-1} \mathcal{L}(t_{j-1}, t_j; \hat{\theta}_j) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \mathcal{L}(t_{\hat{k}-1}, t_{k^*}^*; \hat{\theta}_{\hat{k}}) + \mathcal{L}(t_{k^*}^*, \hat{t}_k^r; \hat{\theta}_{\hat{k}}) \right\} \end{aligned} \tag{S2.36}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \min_{0 < t_1 < \dots < t_{\hat{k}-1} < t_{k^*}^*} \left\{ \sum_{j=1}^{\hat{k}-1} \mathcal{L}(t_{j-1}, t_j; \hat{\theta}_j) + \mathcal{L}(t_{\hat{k}-1}, t_{k^*}^*; \hat{\theta}_{\hat{k}}) \right\} \\ &\quad + \mathcal{L}(t_{k^*}^*, \hat{t}_k^r; \hat{\theta}_{\hat{k}}) \end{aligned} \tag{S2.37}$$

$$= \mathcal{F}^r(t_{k^*}^*; \hat{\Theta}(\hat{k})) + \mathcal{L}(t_{k^*}^*, \hat{t}_k^r; \hat{\theta}_{\hat{k}}). \tag{S2.38}$$

Here, we examine why (S2.36) holds: based on Proposition 35 (Appendix), the solution $\{\hat{t}_j^r\}_{j=1}^{\hat{k}-1}$ of $\mathcal{F}^r(\hat{t}_k^r; \hat{\Theta}(\hat{k}))$ cannot fall into the interval $(t_{k^*}^*, \hat{t}_k^r]$, which in turn allows the loss

term $\mathcal{L}(t_{\hat{k}-1}, \hat{t}_{\hat{k}}^r; \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{\hat{k}})$ to be decomposed into two parts. Since the solutions to (S2.37) satisfies $0 < t_1 < \dots < t_{\hat{k}-1} < t_{\hat{k}}^* < \hat{t}_{\hat{k}}^r$ and $|t_{\hat{k}-1} - t_{\hat{k}^*-1}^*| < \Delta/4$, the last solution is required to lie before the right endpoint, with emphasis on the relation between $t_{\hat{k}-1}$ and $t_{\hat{k}}^*$ rather than between $t_{\hat{k}-1}$ and $\hat{t}_{\hat{k}}^r$, which directly leads to (S2.37).

It is worth noting that if $\hat{t}_{\hat{k}}^r < t_{\hat{k}}^*$, then we have

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{F}^r(t_{\hat{k}}^*; \hat{\boldsymbol{\Theta}}(\hat{k})) &= \min_{\mathcal{T} \in \mathbb{T}_{\hat{k}-1}^r(\hat{t}_{\hat{k}}^r)} \sum_{j=1}^{\hat{k}} \mathcal{L}(t_{j-1}, t_j; \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_j) \\ &= \min_{0 < t_1 < \dots < t_{\hat{k}-1} < t_{\hat{k}}^*} \left\{ \sum_{j=1}^{\hat{k}-1} \mathcal{L}(t_{j-1}, t_j; \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_j) + \mathcal{L}(t_{\hat{k}-1}, t_{\hat{k}}^*; \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{\hat{k}}) \right\} \\ &= \min_{0 < t_1 < \dots < t_{\hat{k}-1} < t_{\hat{k}}^*} \left\{ \sum_{j=1}^{\hat{k}-1} \mathcal{L}(t_{j-1}, t_j; \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_j) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \mathcal{L}(t_{\hat{k}-1}, \hat{t}_{\hat{k}}^r; \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{\hat{k}}) + \mathcal{L}(\hat{t}_{\hat{k}}^r, t_{\hat{k}}^*; \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{\hat{k}}) \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S2.39})$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \min_{0 < t_1 < \dots < t_{\hat{k}-1} < \hat{t}_{\hat{k}}^r} \left\{ \sum_{j=1}^{\hat{k}-1} \mathcal{L}(t_{j-1}, t_j; \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_j) + \mathcal{L}(t_{\hat{k}-1}, \hat{t}_{\hat{k}}^r; \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{\hat{k}}) \right\} \\ &\quad + \mathcal{L}(\hat{t}_{\hat{k}}^r, t_{\hat{k}}^*; \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{\hat{k}}) \\ &= \mathcal{F}^r(\hat{t}_{\hat{k}}^r; \hat{\boldsymbol{\Theta}}(\hat{k})) + \mathcal{L}(\hat{t}_{\hat{k}}^r, t_{\hat{k}}^*; \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{\hat{k}}). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S2.40})$$

The validity of (S2.39) follows from Proposition 35'. In (S2.40), the last solution is restricted less than $\hat{t}_{\hat{k}}^r$.

Under the case that $\hat{t}_{\hat{k}}^r \geq t_{\hat{k}}^*$, combining (S2.38) with the fact

$$\mathcal{L}(\hat{t}_{\hat{k}}^r, n; \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{\hat{k}+1}) - \mathcal{L}(t_{\hat{k}}^*, n; \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{\hat{k}+1}) = -\mathcal{L}(t_{\hat{k}}^*, \hat{t}_{\hat{k}}^r; \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{\hat{k}+1}),$$

it holds uniformly with at least probability $1 - n^{-5}$ that

$$\mathcal{R}^r(\hat{t}_{\hat{k}}^r) = \mathcal{L}(t_{\hat{k}}^*, \hat{t}_{\hat{k}}^r; \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{\hat{k}}) - \mathcal{L}(t_{\hat{k}}^*, \hat{t}_{\hat{k}}^r; \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{\hat{k}+1}) \leq 0 \quad (\text{S2.41})$$

Similarly, if we consider the case that $\hat{t}_{\hat{k}}^r < t_{\hat{k}}^*$, combining

$$\mathcal{F}^r(t_{\hat{k}}^*; \hat{\boldsymbol{\Theta}}(\hat{k})) = \mathcal{F}^r(\hat{t}_{\hat{k}}^r; \hat{\boldsymbol{\Theta}}(\hat{k})) + \mathcal{L}(t_{\hat{k}}^*, \hat{t}_{\hat{k}}^r; \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{\hat{k}})$$

and

$$\mathcal{L}(\hat{t}_{\hat{k}}^r, n; \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{\hat{k}+1}) - \mathcal{L}(t_{\hat{k}}^*, n; \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{\hat{k}+1}) = \mathcal{L}(\hat{t}_{\hat{k}}^r, t_{\hat{k}}^*; \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{\hat{k}+1}),$$

we have the following relation holding with probability at least $1 - n^{-5}$,

$$\mathcal{R}^r(\hat{t}_{\hat{k}}^r) = \mathcal{L}(\hat{t}_{\hat{k}}^r, t_{\hat{k}}^*; \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{\hat{k}+1}) - \mathcal{L}(\hat{t}_{\hat{k}}^r, t_{\hat{k}}^*; \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{\hat{k}}) \leq 0$$

Step 3: locating \hat{t}_k^r via function $\mathcal{Q}^r(\cdot)$. In this step, we denote

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{t}^r &= \hat{t}_{\hat{k}}^r, \quad t^* = t_{k^*}^*, \\ \hat{\theta}_- &= \hat{\theta}_{\hat{k}}, \quad \hat{\theta} = \hat{\theta}_{\hat{k}+1}, \quad \theta_-^* = \theta_{k^*}^* \quad \text{and} \quad \theta^* = \theta_{k^*+1}^*\end{aligned}$$

Denote $r = \hat{t}^r - t^*$. Without loss of generality, suppose $r \geq 0$; the alternative case is similar. From the equation (S2.41), we have

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{R}^r(\hat{t}^r) &= \mathcal{L}(t^*, \hat{t}^r; \hat{\theta}_-) - \mathcal{L}(t^*, \hat{t}^r; \hat{\theta}) \\ &= \left\{ \mathcal{L}(t^*, \hat{t}^r; \hat{\theta}_-) - \mathcal{L}(t^*, \hat{t}^r; \theta_-^*) \right\} - \left\{ \mathcal{L}(t^*, \hat{t}^r; \hat{\theta}) - \mathcal{L}(t^*, \hat{t}^r; \theta^*) \right\} \\ &\quad + \left\{ \mathcal{L}(t^*, \hat{t}^r; \theta_-^*) - \mathcal{L}(t^*, \hat{t}^r; \theta^*) \right\} \\ &= I - II + III \leq 0\end{aligned}$$

Therefore, we have that

$$III \leq -I + II \leq |I| + |III|. \quad (\text{S2.42})$$

If $r \leq 1/\kappa_{k^*}^2$ or $r \leq 2$, then there is nothing to show. So for the rest of the argument, for contradiction, let us assume that

$$r \geq \frac{1}{\kappa_{k^*}^2} \quad \text{and} \quad r \geq 3.$$

Lemma 36 (Appendix) presents unified bounds for the quantities I , II , and III across various models. The corresponding proof is provided in Section S2.3. Therefore, from the equation (S2.42) and Lemma 36 (Appendix), we have uniformly for all $r \geq \kappa_{k^*}^{-2}$ that

$$Cr\kappa_{k^*}^2 \leq O_p\left(\sqrt{r\kappa_{k^*}^2} \{\log(r\kappa_{k^*}^2) + 1\}^2\right) + o_p(r\kappa_{k^*}^2) + o_p(\sqrt{r\kappa_{k^*}^2}) + o_p(1),$$

which implies that

$$r\kappa_{k^*}^2 = O_p(1).$$

and completes the proofs for the estimator \hat{t}_k^r .

S2.2.2 THE REST INDICES $[k^* - 1]^-$

We have proved (S2.35) that $j = k^*$. When considering bound of $|\hat{t}_j^r - t_j^*|$ for $j \in [k^* - 1]^-$, we refer to reasoning similar steps 1-3 in case that $j = k^*$, with the additional note that a different right endpoint is used. We can derive a result similar to (S2.41) (all cases listed below correspond to $\hat{t}_j^r \geq t_j^*$; the opposite case follows analogously).

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{R}^r(\hat{t}_k^r) &= \mathcal{L}(t_{k^*}^*, \hat{t}_k^r; \hat{\theta}_{\hat{k}}) - \mathcal{L}(t_{k^*}^*, \hat{t}_k^r; \hat{\theta}_{\hat{k}+1}) \leq 0; \\ \mathcal{R}^r(\hat{t}_{k-1}^r) &= \mathcal{L}(t_{k^*-1}^*, \hat{t}_{k-1}^r; \hat{\theta}_{\hat{k}-1}) - \mathcal{L}(t_{k^*-1}^*, \hat{t}_{k-1}^r; \hat{\theta}_{\hat{k}}) \leq 0; \\ &\vdots \\ \mathcal{R}^r(\hat{t}_1^r) &= \mathcal{L}(t_1^*, \hat{t}_1^r; \hat{\theta}_1) - \mathcal{L}(t_1^*, \hat{t}_1^r; \hat{\theta}_2) \leq 0.\end{aligned}$$

Naturally, by repeatedly using conclusions similar to Lemma 36 in the above equations, we can show that the desired result (S2.35) holds.

Hence, the full proof of Theorem 7 (Main Paper) is concluded.

S2.3 Proof for Lemma 36

Note that $\mathcal{I} \subset (t^*, \hat{t}^r]$ with $r \geq 3$. By Assumption 3a, we have that

$$\Delta \geq C_{snr} \Upsilon_n s \log(np) \kappa_{k^*}^{-2} \quad (\text{S2.43})$$

S2.3.1 CHANGES IN MEANS

Proof of result (i). We have that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}(t^*, \hat{t}^r; \hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_-) - \mathcal{L}(t^*, \hat{t}^r; \boldsymbol{\mu}_-^*) &= \sum_{i=t^*+1}^{t^*+r} \|\mathbf{X}_i - \hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_-\|_2^2 - \sum_{i=t^*+1}^{t^*+r} \|\mathbf{X}_i - \boldsymbol{\mu}_-^*\|_2^2 \\ &= \sum_{i=t^*+1}^{t^*+r} \|\hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_- - \boldsymbol{\mu}_-^*\|_2^2 - 2(\hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_- - \boldsymbol{\mu}_-^*)^\top \sum_{i=t^*+1}^{t^*+r} (\mathbf{X}_i - \boldsymbol{\mu}_-^*) \\ &= r \|\hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_- - \boldsymbol{\mu}_-^*\|_2^2 - 2r(\hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_- - \boldsymbol{\mu}_-^*)^\top (\boldsymbol{\mu}^* - \boldsymbol{\mu}_-^*) - 2(\hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_- - \boldsymbol{\mu}_-^*)^\top \sum_{i=t^*+1}^{t^*+r} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_i \\ &= I_1 - 2I_2 - 2I_3. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$|I_1| = r \|\hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_- - \boldsymbol{\mu}_-^*\|_2^2 = O_p\left(r \frac{s \log(np)}{\Delta}\right) = O_p(\Upsilon_n^{-1} r \kappa_{k^*}^2) = o_p(r \kappa_{k^*}^2),$$

where the second equality follows from Corollary 31 (Appendix) and the third equality follows from (S2.43). Moreover,

$$\begin{aligned} |I_2| &= \left| r(\hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_- - \boldsymbol{\mu}_-^*)^\top (\boldsymbol{\mu}^* - \boldsymbol{\mu}_-^*) \right| \leq r \|\hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_- - \boldsymbol{\mu}_-^*\|_1 \|\boldsymbol{\mu}^* - \boldsymbol{\mu}_-^*\|_\infty \\ &= O_p\left(r s \sqrt{\frac{\log(np)}{\Delta}} \kappa_{k^*}\right) = O_p\left(\Upsilon_n^{-1/2} \{r \kappa_{k^*}^2 s^{1/2}\}\right) = o_p(r \kappa_{k^*}^2), \end{aligned}$$

where the second equality follows from Corollary 31 (Appendix) and $\|\boldsymbol{\mu}^* - \boldsymbol{\mu}_-^*\|_\infty \leq \|\boldsymbol{\mu}^* - \boldsymbol{\mu}_-^*\|_2$, the penultimate equality follows from (S2.43) and the last equality follows from $\Upsilon_n \gg s \log^2(np)$.

For the term I_3 , we have

$$\begin{aligned} |I_3| &= \left| (\hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_- - \boldsymbol{\mu}_-^*)^\top \sum_{i=t^*+1}^{t^*+r} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_i \right| \leq \|\hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_- - \boldsymbol{\mu}_-^*\|_1 \left\| \sum_{i=t^*+1}^{t^*+r} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_i \right\|_\infty \\ &= O_p\left(s \sqrt{\frac{\log(np)}{\Delta}} (\sqrt{r \log(np)} + \log(np))\right) \\ &= O_p\left(\Upsilon_n^{-1/2} \left\{ \sqrt{r \kappa_{k^*}^2} \sqrt{s \log(np)} + s^{1/2} \log(np) \right\}\right) \\ &= o_p\left(\sqrt{r \kappa_{k^*}^2}\right) + o_p(1), \end{aligned}$$

where the second inequality follows from Corollary 31 (Appendix) and Lemma 21 (Appendix), the penultimate equality follows from (S2.43) and the last equality follows from $\Upsilon_n \gg s \log^2(np)$. Therefore,

$$|I| = o_p(r\kappa_{k^*}^2) + o_p\left(\sqrt{r\kappa_{k^*}^2}\right) + o_p(1).$$

Proof of result (ii). The same arguments for the term I lead to

$$|II| = o_p(r\kappa_{k^*}^2) + o_p\left(\sqrt{r\kappa_{k^*}^2}\right) + o_p(1).$$

Proof of result (iii). Observe that

$$\begin{aligned} III &= \mathcal{L}(t^*, \hat{t}^r; \boldsymbol{\mu}_-^*) - \mathcal{L}(t^*, \hat{t}^r; \boldsymbol{\mu}^*) = \sum_{i=t^*+1}^{t^*+r} \|\mathbf{X}_i - \boldsymbol{\mu}_-^*\|_2^2 - \sum_{i=t^*+1}^{t^*+r} \|\mathbf{X}_i - \boldsymbol{\mu}^*\|_2^2 \\ &= \sum_{i=t^*+1}^{t^*+r} \|\boldsymbol{\mu}_-^* - \boldsymbol{\mu}^*\|_2^2 - 2(\boldsymbol{\mu}_-^* - \boldsymbol{\mu}^*)^\top \sum_{i=t^*+1}^{t^*+r} (\mathbf{X}_i - \boldsymbol{\mu}^*) \\ &= r\|\boldsymbol{\mu}_-^* - \boldsymbol{\mu}^*\|_2^2 - 2(\boldsymbol{\mu}_-^* - \boldsymbol{\mu}^*)^\top \sum_{i=t^*+1}^{t^*+r} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_i \\ &= III_1 - III_2. \end{aligned}$$

For the term III_1 , we have that

$$III_1 \geq r\kappa_{k^*}^2.$$

Next, we consider the term III_2 . Define

$$Z_i = \frac{1}{c_0 \|\boldsymbol{\mu}_-^* - \boldsymbol{\mu}^*\|_2} (\boldsymbol{\mu}_-^* - \boldsymbol{\mu}^*)^\top \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_i,$$

where c_0 depends on σ_ε , ensuring its variance proxy is less than 1.

By the Lemma 22 (Appendix), $\kappa_{k^*} \leq C_\kappa$, and letting $\nu = \kappa_{k^*}^2$, we have that

$$|III_2| = O_p\left(\sqrt{r\kappa_{k^*}^2} \{\log(r\kappa_{k^*}^2) + 1\}^2\right).$$

Therefore, we have that

$$III \geq III_1 - |III_2| \geq r\kappa_{k^*}^2 - O_p\left(\sqrt{r\kappa_{k^*}^2} \{\log(r\kappa_{k^*}^2) + 1\}^2\right).$$

S2.3.2 CHANGES IN REGRESSION COEFFICIENTS

Proof of result (i). We have that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}(t^*, \hat{t}^r; \hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_-) - \mathcal{L}(t^*, \hat{t}^r; \boldsymbol{\beta}_-^*) &= \sum_{i=t^*+1}^{t^*+r} \left(y_i - \mathbf{X}_i^\top \hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_-\right)^2 - \sum_{i=t^*+1}^{t^*+r} \left(y_i - \mathbf{X}_i^\top \boldsymbol{\beta}_-^*\right)^2 \\ &= \sum_{i=t^*+1}^{t^*+r} \left(y_i - \mathbf{X}_i^\top \boldsymbol{\beta}_-^* + \mathbf{X}_i^\top \boldsymbol{\beta}_-^* - \mathbf{X}_i^\top \hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_-\right)^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & - \sum_{i=t^*+1}^{t^*+r} (y_i - \mathbf{X}_i^\top \boldsymbol{\beta}^* + \mathbf{X}_i^\top \boldsymbol{\beta}^* - \mathbf{X}_i^\top \boldsymbol{\beta}_-^*)^2 \\
 = & \sum_{i=t^*+1}^{t^*+r} \left(\mathbf{X}_i^\top (\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_- - \boldsymbol{\beta}^*) \right)^2 - \sum_{i=t^*+1}^{t^*+r} \left(\mathbf{X}_i^\top (\boldsymbol{\beta}_-^* - \boldsymbol{\beta}^*) \right)^2 - 2 \sum_{i=t^*+1}^{t^*+r} \varepsilon_i \mathbf{X}_i^\top (\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_- - \boldsymbol{\beta}_-^*) \\
 = & \sum_{i=t^*+1}^{t^*+r} \left(\mathbf{X}_i^\top (\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_- - \boldsymbol{\beta}_-^*) \right)^2 - 2 \sum_{i=t^*+1}^{t^*+r} (\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_- - \boldsymbol{\beta}_-^*)^\top \mathbf{X}_i \mathbf{X}_i^\top (\boldsymbol{\beta}^* - \boldsymbol{\beta}_-^*) \\
 & - 2 \sum_{i=t^*+1}^{t^*+r} \varepsilon_i \mathbf{X}_i^\top (\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_- - \boldsymbol{\beta}_-^*) \\
 = & I_1 - 2I_2 - 2I_3.
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned}
 |I_1| & = (\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_- - \boldsymbol{\beta}_-^*)^\top \left\{ \sum_{i=t^*+1}^{t^*+r} (\mathbf{X}_i \mathbf{X}_i^\top - \boldsymbol{\Sigma}) \right\} (\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_- - \boldsymbol{\beta}_-^*) \\
 & \quad + r (\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_- - \boldsymbol{\beta}_-^*)^\top \boldsymbol{\Sigma} (\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_- - \boldsymbol{\beta}_-^*) \\
 & = O_p \left(\frac{s \log(np)}{\Delta} \left(\sqrt{rs \log(np)} + s \log(np) + r \right) \right) \\
 & = O_p \left(\Upsilon_n^{-1} \left(\sqrt{r \kappa_{k^*}^2 s \log(np)} + s \log(np) + r \kappa_{k^*}^2 \right) \right) \\
 & = o_p(\sqrt{r \kappa_{k^*}^2}) + o_p(1) + o_p(r \kappa_{k^*}^2)
 \end{aligned}$$

where the second equality follows from Corollary 34 (Appendix) and Lemma 28 (Appendix), the third equality follows from (S2.43) and $\kappa_{k^*} \leq C_\kappa$ and the last equality follows from $\Upsilon_n \gg s \log^2(np)$.

For the term I_2

$$\begin{aligned}
 |I_2| & = \left| (\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_- - \boldsymbol{\beta}_-^*)^\top \sum_{i=t^*+1}^{t^*+r} \mathbf{X}_i \mathbf{X}_i^\top (\boldsymbol{\beta}^* - \boldsymbol{\beta}_-^*) \right| \\
 & \leq \left| (\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_- - \boldsymbol{\beta}_-^*)^\top \left\{ \sum_{i=t^*+1}^{t^*+r} (\mathbf{X}_i \mathbf{X}_i^\top - \boldsymbol{\Sigma}) \right\} (\boldsymbol{\beta}^* - \boldsymbol{\beta}_-^*) \right| + \left| r (\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_- - \boldsymbol{\beta}_-^*)^\top \boldsymbol{\Sigma} (\boldsymbol{\beta}^* - \boldsymbol{\beta}_-^*) \right| \\
 & \leq \left\| \hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_- - \boldsymbol{\beta}_-^* \right\|_1 \left\| \left\{ \sum_{i=t^*+1}^{t^*+r} (\mathbf{X}_i \mathbf{X}_i^\top - \boldsymbol{\Sigma}) \right\} (\boldsymbol{\beta}^* - \boldsymbol{\beta}_-^*) \right\|_\infty \\
 & \quad + r \bar{\rho}_x \left\| \hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_- - \boldsymbol{\beta}_-^* \right\|_2 \left\| \boldsymbol{\beta}^* - \boldsymbol{\beta}_-^* \right\|_2 \\
 & = O_p \left(s \sqrt{\frac{\log(np)}{\Delta}} \left(\sqrt{r \log(np)} + \log(np) \right) \left\| \boldsymbol{\beta}^* - \boldsymbol{\beta}_-^* \right\|_2 \right. \\
 & \quad \left. + r \bar{\rho}_x \sqrt{\frac{s \log(np)}{\Delta}} \left\| \boldsymbol{\beta}^* - \boldsymbol{\beta}_-^* \right\|_2 \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= O_p \left(\Upsilon_n^{-1/2} \left\{ \sqrt{r\kappa_{k^*}^2} \sqrt{s \log(np)} + s^{1/2} \log(np) + r\kappa_{k^*}^2 \right\} \right) \\
 &= o_p(\sqrt{r\kappa_{k^*}^2}) + o_p(1) + o_p(r\kappa_{k^*}^2),
 \end{aligned}$$

where the second equality follows from Corollary 34 (Appendix) and Lemma 27(ii) (Appendix), the penultimate equality follows from (S2.43) and $\kappa_{k^*} \leq C_\kappa$, and the last equality follows from $\Upsilon_n \gg s \log^2(np)$.

For the term I_3 , we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 |I_3| &= \left| \sum_{i=t^*+1}^{t^*+r} \varepsilon_i \mathbf{X}_i^\top (\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_- - \boldsymbol{\beta}_-^*) \right| \leq \left\| \sum_{i=t^*+1}^{t^*+r} \mathbf{X}_i \varepsilon_i \right\|_\infty \|\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_- - \boldsymbol{\beta}_-^*\|_1 \\
 &= O_p \left(s \sqrt{\frac{\log(np)}{\Delta}} (\sqrt{r \log(np)} + \log(np)) \right) \\
 &= O_p \left(\Upsilon_n^{-1/2} \left\{ \sqrt{r\kappa_{k^*}^2} \sqrt{s \log(np)} + s^{1/2} \log(np) \right\} \right) \\
 &= o_p(\sqrt{r\kappa_{k^*}^2}) + o_p(1),
 \end{aligned}$$

where the second inequality follows from Corollary 34 (Appendix) and Lemma 27(i) (Appendix), the penultimate equality follows from (S2.43) and $\kappa_{k^*} \leq C_\kappa$, and the last equality follows from $\Upsilon_n \gg s \log^2(np)$. Therefore,

$$|I| = o_p(r\kappa_{k^*}^2) + o_p(\sqrt{r\kappa_{k^*}^2}) + o_p(1).$$

Proof of result (ii). The same arguments for the term I lead to

$$|II| = o_p(r\kappa_{k^*}^2) + o_p(\sqrt{r\kappa_{k^*}^2}) + o_p(1).$$

Proof of result (iii). Observe that

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{L}(t^*, \hat{t}^r; \boldsymbol{\beta}_-^*) - \mathcal{L}(t^*, \hat{t}^r; \boldsymbol{\beta}^*) &= \sum_{i=t^*+1}^{t^*+r} (y_i - \mathbf{X}_i^\top \boldsymbol{\beta}_-^*)^2 - \sum_{i=t^*+1}^{t^*+r} (y_i - \mathbf{X}_i^\top \boldsymbol{\beta}^*)^2 \\
 &= \sum_{i=t^*+1}^{t^*+r} (\mathbf{X}_i^\top (\boldsymbol{\beta}_-^* - \boldsymbol{\beta}^*))^2 - 2 \sum_{i=t^*+1}^{t^*+r} \varepsilon_i \mathbf{X}_i^\top (\boldsymbol{\beta}_-^* - \boldsymbol{\beta}^*) \\
 &= r(\boldsymbol{\beta}_-^* - \boldsymbol{\beta}^*)^\top \boldsymbol{\Sigma} (\boldsymbol{\beta}_-^* - \boldsymbol{\beta}^*) + (\boldsymbol{\beta}_-^* - \boldsymbol{\beta}^*)^\top \left\{ \sum_{i=t^*+1}^{t^*+r} (\mathbf{X}_i \mathbf{X}_i^\top - \boldsymbol{\Sigma}) \right\} (\boldsymbol{\beta}_-^* - \boldsymbol{\beta}^*) \\
 &\quad - 2 \sum_{i=t^*+1}^{t^*+r} \varepsilon_i \mathbf{X}_i^\top (\boldsymbol{\beta}_-^* - \boldsymbol{\beta}^*) \\
 &= III_1 + III_2 - 2III_3.
 \end{aligned}$$

For the term III_1 , we have that

$$III_1 \geq r \underline{\rho}_x \kappa_{k^*}^2.$$

For the term III_2 , Define

$$Z_i = \frac{1}{c_0 \|\boldsymbol{\beta}_-^* - \boldsymbol{\beta}^*\|_2^2} (\boldsymbol{\beta}_-^* - \boldsymbol{\beta}^*)^\top \left\{ \sum_{i=t^*+1}^{t^*+r} (\mathbf{X}_i \mathbf{X}_i^\top - \boldsymbol{\Sigma}) \right\} (\boldsymbol{\beta}_-^* - \boldsymbol{\beta}^*),$$

where $c_0 > 0$ depends on σ_x , ensuring its variance proxy is less than 1. By the Lemma 22 (Appendix), $\kappa_{k^*} \leq C_\kappa$, and letting $\nu = \kappa_{k^*}^2$, we have that

$$|III_2| = O_p(\sqrt{r\kappa_{k^*}^2} \{\log(r\kappa_{k^*}^2) + 1\}^2).$$

Similarly, we consider the term III_3 . Let

$$Z_i = \frac{1}{c_1 \|\boldsymbol{\beta}_-^* - \boldsymbol{\beta}^*\|_2} \sum_{i=t^*+1}^{t^*+r} \varepsilon_i \mathbf{X}_i^\top (\boldsymbol{\beta}_-^* - \boldsymbol{\beta}^*),$$

where $c_1 > 0$ depends on σ_x and σ_ε , ensuring its variance proxy is less than 1. By the Lemma 22 (Appendix), $\kappa_{k^*} \leq C_\kappa$, and letting $\nu = \kappa_{k^*}^2$, we have that

$$|III_3| = O_p(\sqrt{r\kappa_{k^*}^2} \{\log(r\kappa_{k^*}^2) + 1\}^2).$$

Therefore, we have that

$$III \geq III_1 - |III_2| - 2|III_3| \geq r\kappa_{k^*}^2 - O_p(\sqrt{r\kappa_{k^*}^2} \{\log(r\kappa_{k^*}^2) + 1\}^2).$$

S3 Several prerequisite results

This section presents auxiliary results required for the proofs in Section F (Appendix). Let $\hat{\mathbf{u}}_{\tilde{k}}$ be the solution from (8) (Main Paper), and $\mathbf{u}_{\tilde{k}}^*$ denote the raw true locations as in (S0.7). According to the ℓ_0 -penalized optimization problem in (8) (Main Paper), we have

$$\Delta\text{TL}(\hat{\mathbf{u}}_{\tilde{k}}, \mathbf{u}_{\tilde{k}}^*) + \gamma(\hat{k} - k^*) \leq 0, \quad (\text{S3.1})$$

where the discrepancy function is given by

$$\Delta\text{TL}(\hat{\mathbf{u}}_{\tilde{k}}, \mathbf{u}_{\tilde{k}}^*) = \text{TL}(\hat{\mathbf{u}}_{\tilde{k}}, \tilde{\boldsymbol{\Theta}}(\tilde{k} + 1)) - \text{TL}(\mathbf{u}_{\tilde{k}}^*, \tilde{\boldsymbol{\Theta}}(\tilde{k} + 1)), \quad (\text{S3.2})$$

and $\text{TL}(\cdot, \cdot)$ is defined in (7) (Main Paper). We will show that if the estimated set $\hat{\mathbf{u}}_{\tilde{k}} = \{\hat{u}_j\}_{j=1}^{\tilde{k}} \in \mathbb{U}_{\tilde{k}}(n)$ fails to meet the conditions in Proposition 5 (Main Paper), it leads to a contradiction with (S3.1). Specifically, we observe

$$\begin{aligned} \text{TL}(\mathbf{u}_{\tilde{k}}^*, \tilde{\boldsymbol{\Theta}}(\tilde{k} + 1)) &= \text{TL}(\{u_{\hat{\mu}(j)}^*\}_{j=1}^{k^*}, \{\tilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{\hat{\mu}(j)}\}_{j=1}^{k^*+1}) \\ &= \text{TL}(\{u_{m(j)}^*\}_{j=1}^{k^*}, \{\tilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{\hat{\mu}(j)}\}_{j=1}^{k^*+1}). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S3.3})$$

In a similar manner, under event (19), the optimization problem (13) (Main Paper) implies that

$$\Delta\text{TL}(\hat{\mathcal{T}}_k^r, \boldsymbol{\tau}_{k^*}^*) = \text{TL}(\hat{\mathcal{T}}_k^r, \hat{\boldsymbol{\Theta}}(\hat{k} + 1)) - \text{TL}(\boldsymbol{\tau}_{k^*}^*, \hat{\boldsymbol{\Theta}}(\hat{k} + 1)) \leq 0, \quad (\text{S3.4})$$

where refined change point estimators $\widehat{\mathcal{T}}_k^r = \{\hat{t}_j^r\}_{j=1}^{\hat{k}} \in \mathbb{T}_{\hat{k}}(n)$.

The remainder of this section is organized as follows. In Section S3.1, we state the prerequisites for the proof of Theorem 4 (Main Paper), namely that the *marker* raw estimated location will fall within a reasonable neighborhood of the true change point. Section S3.2 is divided into three subsections to establish the required lemmas of Section S3.1 for different models. Similarly, the prerequisites required for the proof of Theorem 7 (Main Paper) are provided in Section S3.3, followed by Section S3.4, which presents the necessary lemmas for Section S3.3.

S3.1 Prerequisite results for optimization problem (8)

The key proposition (Proposition 5) established in this section provides the technical foundation for the proof of Theorem 4 (Main Paper). Specifically, the *raw estimated locations associated with marker indices* ($\{\hat{u}_j\}_{j \in \mathcal{M}}$) will be positioned near the corresponding change points, while the *non-marker raw estimated locations* ($\{\hat{u}_j\}_{j \notin \mathcal{M}}$) will merge rightward into the marker raw estimated locations. Notably, all arguments presented in this subsection are based on the assumptions required by Theorem 4. Recall that the solution $\{\hat{u}_j\}_{j=1}^{\hat{k}} \cup \{\hat{u}_{\hat{k}+1}\}$ can be expressed by $\{\hat{u}_{\hat{h}(1)}, \dots, \hat{u}_{m(1)}, \dots, \hat{u}_{\hat{h}(k^*+1)}, \dots, \hat{u}_{m(k^*+1)}\}$ from .

Proof [Proof of Proposition 5(i)] We define the event

$$\mathcal{A}_j := \left\{ \hat{u}_{m(j)} \in \mathcal{H}(0, \Delta/4; t_j^*) \right\}, \quad \text{for all } j \in [k^*],$$

where the neighborhood function $\mathcal{H}(\cdot, \cdot, \cdot)$ is specified in (30). Next, we use a recursive method to prove that the event $\bigcap_{j=1}^{k^*} \mathcal{A}_j$ holds. We start by proving through contradiction that $\bigcup_{j=1}^{k^*} \mathcal{A}_j^c$ is impossible. While it typically involves exhaustively examining all counterexamples, we will initially focus on the simplest case.

Step 1. There exists only one $j \in [k^*]$ such that $|\hat{u}_{m(j)} - t_j^*| > \Delta/4$ under the event

$$(\mathcal{A}_j^c) \cap \left(\bigcap_{j' \in [k^*] \setminus \{j\}} \mathcal{A}_{j'} \right). \quad (\text{S3.5})$$

While this case is not universal, as it cannot encompass all possible configurations of $\widehat{\mathcal{U}}_{\hat{k}}$, it has two advantages: i) it is intuitive and easy to understand, and ii) we will later demonstrate that any other cases is an extension of this simple case, all of which lead to a contradiction with (S3.1). Under the event (S3.5), we can see that $\hat{k} \geq k^* - 1$. This is because, aside from t_j^* , each of the other true change points has at least one raw estimated location nearby. Based on (S3.5) and the solution $\widehat{\mathcal{U}}_{\hat{k}}$ satisfying

$$0 < \hat{u}_{\hat{h}(1)} \leq \dots \leq \hat{u}_{m(j-1)} \leq \dots \leq \hat{u}_{m(j)} \leq \dots \leq \hat{u}_{m(j+1)} \leq \dots \leq n,$$

we conclude that

$$\hat{u}_{m(j)} \in [t_{j-1}^* - \Delta/4, t_j^* - \Delta/4) \cup (t_j^* + \Delta/4, t_{j+1}^* + \Delta/4].$$

Without loss of generality, let us consider the setting where $\hat{u}_{m(j)} \in (t_j^* + \Delta/4, t_{j+1}^* + \Delta/4]$; the alternative case is symmetric. The analysis proceeds with the following cases:

- (a) $\hat{u}_{m(j)} \in (t_j^* + \Delta/4, t_{j+1}^*]$.
 (b) $\hat{u}_{m(j)} \in (t_{j+1}^*, t_{j+1}^* + \Delta/4]$.

Case (a). It can verify that

$$\hat{u}_{m(j)} > t_j^* + \Delta/4, \quad (\text{S3.6})$$

as shown in Figure S3.6.

Figure S3.6: Intuitive explanation for **Case (a)**. The red triangles represent the true change points (u_j^* as defined in (S0.7)), while the blue rectangles represent the marker raw estimated locations $\{\hat{u}_j\}_{j \in \mathcal{M}}$. The brackets around the true change points $t_{j-1}^*, t_j^*, t_{j+1}^*$ represent the upper bound of a neighborhood with a radius of $\Delta/4$. The red solid horizontal braces represent the initial estimated parameters used in the total loss $\text{TL}(\mathcal{U}_k^*, \tilde{\Theta}(\tilde{k}+1))$ from (S3.3). The blue solid horizontal braces represent the parameter sets used in the total loss $\text{TL}(\hat{\mathcal{U}}_k, \tilde{\Theta}(\tilde{k}+1))$, where the parameter set applied to the corresponding large partitions constructed by blue rectangles. Since the large partitions may contain several non-marker raw estimated locations, the blue dashed waves indicate the specific sub-partitions. Only the part related to the index groups \mathcal{G}_j and \mathcal{G}_{j+1} are shown here.

Given that the elements of \mathcal{G}_j are bounded, there must exist at least one sub-interval \mathcal{J} in the interval set (the cyan part shown in Figure S3.6) generated by $\{t_j^*, \dots, \hat{u}_{m(j)}\}$ such that $|\mathcal{J}| \geq C_1 \Delta$, where C_1 is a absolute constant satisfying $C_1 > 0$. Note that we refer to the interval $\mathcal{J} \subset (t_j^*, \hat{u}_{m(j)}]$ as a **big signal interval**, because the loss difference (S3.2) over the interval \mathcal{J} is the difference between the loss function associated with the "adjacent" estimated parameters (i.e., the elements of $\{\tilde{\theta}_{\tilde{h}(j)}, \dots, \tilde{\theta}_{m(j)}\}$) and that associated with the "correct" estimated parameters $\tilde{\theta}_{\tilde{h}(j+1)}$. Therefore, with at least $1 - n^{-5}$, we have,

$$\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{J}, \tilde{\theta}_{\mathcal{J}}) - \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{J}, \tilde{\theta}_{\tilde{h}(j+1)}) \geq C_1 \Delta \kappa^2,$$

which derives from:

- Lemma S3.5(ii) under model (2);
- Lemma S3.7(ii) under model (3).

It should be noted that $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{\mathcal{J}}$ comes from one of $\{\tilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{\hat{m}(j)}, \dots, \tilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{m(j)}\}$, whereas the "correct" estimated parameter must be $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{\hat{m}(j+1)}$, due to the construction of $\{u_j^*\}_{j=1}^{\tilde{k}}$ (i.e., (S3.3)). The quantity $\Delta\text{TL}(\hat{u}_k, \mathbf{u}_k^*)$ measures the loss differences across several intervals, which are determined by sorting the set $\{0\} \cup \hat{u}_k \cup \mathbf{u}_k^*$ in ascending order. Thus, for absolute constants $C_1, C_2, C_3, C_4 > 0$ depending only on \tilde{k} and k , we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \Delta\text{TL}(\hat{u}_k, \mathbf{u}_k^*) + \gamma(\hat{k} - k^*) \\ & \geq C_1 \Delta \kappa^2 - C_2 s \log(np) - C_3 \Delta_n^{-1} \lambda_1^2 s + C_4 \gamma \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S3.7})$$

$$> 0, \quad (\text{S3.8})$$

where the last inequality by Assumption 3a and $c_\gamma \Delta \kappa^2 \geq \gamma \geq C_\gamma \Delta_n^{-1} \lambda_1^2 s$. To justify why (S3.7) holds, we note that $\text{TL}(\mathbf{u}_k^*, \hat{\boldsymbol{\Theta}}(\hat{k} + 1))$ captures the total loss when employing the "correct" estimated parameters. Therefore, $\Delta\text{TL}(\hat{u}_k, \mathbf{u}_k^*)$ indicates that the loss difference within each true change point interval $\{(t_{j-1}^*, t_j^*)\}_{j=1}^{k^*+1}$ involves only two possible cases "similar difference" and "signal difference", as specified in Lemma S3.5(i)(ii) under model (2) (or Lemma S3.7(i)(ii) under model (3)). Of course, these two cases are necessarily finite, which leads to the absolute constants $C_1, C_2, C_3, C_4 > 0$ in the inequality. Expression (S3.8) contradicts inequality (S3.1) for sufficiently large C_{snr} . It is worth noting that in the special setting, where $|\mathcal{G}_j| = 1$ holds for all $j \in [k^* + 1]$, we have $\gamma(\hat{k} - k^*) = 0$ or $\gamma(\hat{k} - k^*) = -\gamma$ (i.e., $\hat{u}_{m(j)} = \hat{u}_{m(j+1)}$), and expression (S3.8) still holds. In the extreme case where $\gamma(\hat{k} - k^*) = -\gamma$, the technical condition $\gamma \leq c_\gamma \Delta \kappa^2$ becomes necessary for (S3.8) to hold.

Case (b). If (S3.6) further satisfies

$$\hat{u}_{m(j)} \in (t_{j+1}^*, t_{j+1}^* + \Delta/4],$$

then the total loss difference (S3.2) over the interval $(t_j^*, \hat{u}_{m(j)}]$ results in three effects:

- Lemma S3.5(iii) under model (2) (or Lemma S3.7(iii) under model (3)), describing the "misplaced difference" in the interval $(t_{j+1}^*, \hat{u}_{m(j)}]$;
- Lemma S3.5(ii) under model (2) (or Lemma S3.7(ii) under model (3)), which highlights the "signal difference" within the big "signal interval" $\mathcal{J} \subset (t_j^*, t_{j+1}^*]$ such that $|\mathcal{J}| \geq c_1 \Delta$, where c_1 is a absolute constant satisfying $c_1 > 0$;
- and Lemma S3.5(i) under model (2) (or Lemma S3.7(i) under model (3)) describing the "similar difference" in the interval $(t_j^*, t_{j+1}^*]$.

Naturally, expression (S3.7) also holds, though with slightly different constant terms. In other words, when $\hat{u}_{m(j)}$ is positioned to the right of t_{j+1}^* , the "misplaced difference" will necessarily be accompanied by a "signal difference." Under the SNR assumption, this sufficiently large "signal difference" guarantees that (S3.8) always holds. Similarly, in the

extreme setting where $k^* - 1 \leq \hat{k} \leq k^*$, and due to $\Delta\kappa^2 \geq C_5\gamma$, expression (S3.7) also holds. This establishes that event (S3.5) cannot hold with probability at least $1 - n^{-5}$.

Step 2. There exist two distinct indices j_1, j_2 such that $j_1 < j_2$ and $1 \leq j_1 \neq j_2 \leq k^* + 1$, under the event

$$(\mathcal{A}_{j_1}^c \cup \mathcal{A}_{j_2}^c) \cap \left(\bigcap_{j' \in [k^*+1] \setminus \{j_1, j_2\}} \mathcal{A}_{j'} \right). \quad (\text{S3.9})$$

Under the event (S3.9), we can see that $\hat{k} \geq k^* - 2$. This holds because, aside from $t_{j_1}^*$ and $t_{j_2}^*$, each true change point is accompanied by at least one raw estimated location nearby. We begin with a specific case where the two indices are non-adjacent, i.e., $j_2 \neq j_1 + 1$. The proof is almost identical to Step 1, with the only difference being the existence of at least two "signal intervals". Analogous to equation (S3.7), it holds that with a probability at least $1 - n^{-5}$,

$$\Delta\text{TL}(\hat{u}_{\hat{k}}, \mathbf{u}_{\hat{k}}^*) + \gamma(\hat{k} - k^*) > 0.$$

Now, consider the case $j_2 = j_1 + 1$, leading to four possible scenarios:

- $\hat{u}_{m(j_1)} > t_{j_1}^* + \Delta/4$ and $\hat{u}_{m(j_2)} > t_{j_2}^* + \Delta/4$;
- $\hat{u}_{m(j_1)} < t_{j_1}^* - \Delta/4$ and $\hat{u}_{m(j_2)} < t_{j_2}^* - \Delta/4$;
- $\hat{u}_{m(j_1)} > t_{j_1}^* + \Delta/4$ and $\hat{u}_{m(j_2)} < t_{j_2}^* - \Delta/4$;
- $\hat{u}_{m(j_1)} < t_{j_1}^* - \Delta/4$ and $\hat{u}_{m(j_2)} > t_{j_2}^* + \Delta/4$.

Similar to Step 1, as long as a big "signal interval" can be identified, expression (S3.1) is inevitably violated. We point out that the big "signal interval" \mathcal{J} for the four scenarios corresponds to the following intervals, respectively:

- $(t_{j_1}^*, \hat{u}_{m(j_1)}] \cup (t_{j_2}^*, \hat{u}_{m(j_2)}]$;
- $(\hat{u}_{m(j_1)}, t_{j_1}^*] \cup (\hat{u}_{m(j_2)}, t_{j_2}^*]$;
- $(t_{j_1}^*, \hat{u}_{m(j_1)}] \cup (\hat{u}_{m(j_2)}, t_{j_2}^*]$;
- $(\hat{u}_{m(j_1)}, t_{j_1}^*] \cup (t_{j_2}^*, \hat{u}_{m(j_2)}]$.

When we extend this to the extreme setting where $k^* - 2 \leq \hat{k} \leq k^*$, the analysis remains exactly the same. The only exception is when $\hat{k} = k^* - 2$, in which case \mathcal{J} must come from the interval $(t_{j_1}^*, t_{j_2}^*]$. This establishes that event (S3.9) cannot hold with probability at least $1 - n^{-5}$.

Step 3. In the first two steps, we have already ruled out the possibility of "exactly one \mathcal{A}_j^c occurring while all others occur" and "exactly two events $\mathcal{A}_{j_1}^c \cup \mathcal{A}_{j_2}^c$ occurring while all others occur". Next, for any m satisfying $3 \leq m \leq k^*$, suppose there exists a set $\{j_1, \dots, j_m\} \subseteq [k^*]$ such that

$$(\mathcal{A}_{j_1}^c \cup \dots \cup \mathcal{A}_{j_m}^c) \cap \left(\bigcap_{j' \in [k^*+1] \setminus \{j_1, \dots, j_m\}} \mathcal{A}_{j'} \right). \quad (\text{S3.10})$$

Clearly, through a more tedious yet entirely similar discussion to Step 2, we establish that event (S3.10) cannot hold with probability at least $1 - n^{-5}$.

Following the same logic, we can sequentially eliminate the cases where $m = 4, 5, \dots, k^*$. Since k^* is finite, this elimination process completes within a finite number of steps. As a result, all scenarios where " $1 \leq m \leq k^*$ events $\mathcal{A}_{j_1}^c, \dots, \mathcal{A}_{j_m}^c$ occur simultaneously while all others occur" have been ruled out one by one. Therefore, none of the subcases within $\bigcup_{j=1}^{k^*} \mathcal{A}_j^c$ are possible. According to De Morgan's law, it follows that the entire union does not exist, implying

$$\left(\bigcup_{j=1}^{k^*} \mathcal{A}_j^c \right)^c = \bigcap_{j=1}^{k^*} \mathcal{A}_j,$$

must hold, which is exactly the conclusion we aimed to prove. ■

Proof [Proof of Proposition 5(ii)] We define the collection

$$\mathcal{K}_j = \left\{ \tilde{j} \in \{h(j), \dots, m(j)\} \mid \hat{u}_{\tilde{j}} \neq \hat{u}_{\tilde{j}-1} \right\} \text{ for } j \in [k^* + 1].$$

We naturally assume, without loss of generality, that $|\mathcal{G}_j| \geq |\mathcal{K}_j|$, where $\mathcal{G}_j = \{h(j), \dots, m(j)\}$ is defined in (S0.5). From Proposition 5(i), we know that $\hat{u}_{m(j)} \in \mathcal{H}(0, \Delta/4; t_j^*)$ for every $j \in [k^*]$. This directly implies that $\hat{k} \geq k^*$. We further denote the event

$$\mathcal{B}_j = \left\{ \hat{u}_{h(j)} = \dots = \hat{u}_{m(j)} \right\} \text{ for } j \in [k^* + 1].$$

By the definitions of \mathcal{K}_j and \mathcal{B}_j , we have

$$\mathcal{B}_j \text{ holds} \iff |\mathcal{K}_j| = 1 \iff \mathcal{K}_j = \{h(j)\}. \quad (\text{S3.11})$$

Note that if the event

$$\left(\bigcap_{j=1}^{k^*} \mathcal{A}_j \right) \cap \left(\bigcap_{j=1}^{k^*+1} \mathcal{B}_j \right)$$

holds with high probability, it implies that $\hat{k} = k^*$. We have already proven that $\bigcap_{j=1}^{k^*} \mathcal{A}_j$ holds. Next, we also use a recursive method to prove that the event $\bigcap_{j=1}^{k^*+1} \mathcal{B}_j$ holds. We start by proving through contradiction that $\bigcup_{j=1}^{k^*+1} \mathcal{B}_j^c$ is impossible. First we will initially focus on the simplest setting.

Step 1. There exists only one $j \in [k^* + 1]$ such that $|\mathcal{K}_j| > 1$ under the event

$$(\mathcal{B}_j^c) \cap \left(\bigcap_{j' \in \{1, \dots, j-1, j+1, \dots, k+1\}} \mathcal{B}_{j'} \right). \quad (\text{S3.12})$$

Let us consider the setting where $|\mathcal{K}_j| = 2$; the alternative case is similar. According to expression (S3.11), the condition $|\mathcal{K}_j| = 2$ implies that, apart from the index $h(j)$, there exists an index $\tilde{j}' \in \{h(j) + 1, \dots, m(j)\}$ such that $\hat{u}_{\tilde{j}'} \neq \hat{u}_{\tilde{j}'-1}$. The specific details are shown in Figure S3.7.

Figure S3.7: Intuitive explanation for case $\mathcal{K}_j = \{h(j), j'\}$. The red triangles represent the true change points (u_j^* as defined in (S0.7)), while the blue rectangles represent the raw estimated locations (repeated locations are displayed in small brackets above the line). The brackets around the true change points $t_{j-1}^*, t_j^*, t_{j+1}^*$ represent the upper bound of a neighborhood with a radius of $\Delta/4$. The red solid horizontal braces represent the parameters used in the total loss $\text{TL}(u_k^*, \tilde{\Theta}(\tilde{k} + 1))$. The blue solid horizontal braces represent the parameters used in total loss $\text{TL}(\hat{u}_k, \tilde{\Theta}(\tilde{k} + 1))$. Only the part related to the index groups \mathcal{G}_{j-1} , \mathcal{G}_j and \mathcal{G}_{j+1} are shown here.

Similar to the proof of **Step 1** in Proposition 5(i), it holds with probability at least $1 - n^{-5}$ that

$$\Delta \text{TL}(\hat{u}_k, u_k^*) + \gamma(\hat{k} - k^*) \geq -C_1 \Delta_n^{-1} \lambda_1^2 s - C_2 s \log(np) + \gamma > 0, \quad (\text{S3.13})$$

where the first inequality follows from

- Lemma S3.5(i)(ii) under model (2);
- Lemma S3.7(i)(ii) under model (3),

the last inequality follows from the fact $\gamma \geq C_\gamma \Delta_n^{-1} \lambda_1^2 s$ with sufficiently large constant $C_\gamma > 0$. As a result, when $|\mathcal{K}_j| = 2$, it directly leads to a contradiction with inequality (S3.1). The remaining cases, where $|\mathcal{K}_j| > 2$, follow similar and even simpler arguments, and are thus omitted. The only necessary changes for (S3.13) are $(\hat{k} - k^*)\gamma = (|\mathcal{K}_j| - 1)\gamma$ and the constants C_1 and C_2 , which have no impact on the final discussions. This establishes that event (S3.12) cannot hold with probability at least $1 - n^{-5}$.

Step 2. There exist two distinct indices j_1, j_2 such that $j_1 < j_2$ and $1 \leq j_1 \neq j_2 \leq k^* + 1$, under the event

$$(\mathcal{B}_{j_1}^c \cup \mathcal{B}_{j_2}^c) \cap \left(\bigcap_{j' \in [k^* + 1] \setminus \{j_1, j_2\}} \mathcal{B}_{j'} \right). \quad (\text{S3.14})$$

Under the event (S3.14), we can see that

$$\hat{k} - k^* = (|\mathcal{K}_{j_1}| - 1) + (|\mathcal{K}_{j_2}| - 1) > 0,$$

where the last inequality follows from $|\mathcal{K}_{j_1}| \geq 2$ and $|\mathcal{K}_{j_2}| \geq 2$ under event (S3.14). Analogous to equation (S3.13), it holds that with a probability at least $1 - n^{-5}$,

$$\Delta \text{TL}(\widehat{\mathbf{u}}_{\widehat{k}}, \mathbf{u}_{\widehat{k}}^*) + \gamma(\widehat{k} - k^*) > -C_1 \Delta_n^{-1} \lambda_1^2 s - C_2 s \log(np) + C_3 \gamma > 0.$$

This establishes that event (S3.14) cannot hold with probability at least $1 - n^{-5}$. Next, for any m satisfying $3 \leq m \leq k^* + 1$, suppose there exists a set $\{j_1, \dots, j_m\} \subseteq [k^*]$ such that

$$(\mathcal{B}_{j_1}^c \cup \dots \cup \mathcal{B}_{j_m}^c) \cap \left(\bigcap_{j' \in [k^*+1] \setminus \{j_1, \dots, j_m\}} \mathcal{B}_{j'} \right). \quad (\text{S3.15})$$

Clearly, through a more tedious yet entirely similar discussion to Step 1, we establish that event (S3.15) cannot hold with probability at least $1 - n^{-5}$. Following the same logic, we can sequentially eliminate the cases where $m = 4, 5, \dots, k^* + 1$. Since k^* is finite, this elimination process terminates after a finite number of steps. As a result, all scenarios in which "the events $\mathcal{B}_{j_1}^c, \dots, \mathcal{B}_{j_m}^c$ occur simultaneously for $1 \leq m \leq k^* + 1$ while all other events hold" are ruled out one by one. Consequently, none of the subcases within $\bigcup_{j=1}^{k^*+1} \mathcal{B}_j^c$ are possible. By De Morgan's law, it follows that the complement of the entire union does not exist, implying that

$$\left(\bigcup_{j=1}^{k^*+1} \mathcal{B}_j^c \right)^c = \bigcap_{j=1}^{k^*+1} \mathcal{B}_j,$$

must hold, which is precisely the conclusion we aimed to prove. ■

Generalization of Proposition 5 We now introduce a natural generalization of Proposition 5. For a given endpoint $t_{\mathbb{k}}^*$ with $\mathbb{k} \in [k^*]$, and unlike Expression (8) (Main Paper), the input data and initial estimated parameters are replaced by $\mathcal{Z}_0^{t_{\mathbb{k}}^*}$ and $\widetilde{\Theta}(m(\mathbb{k}))$, respectively. The ℓ_0 -regularized problem is thus formulated as follows:

$$\widehat{\mathbf{u}}_{m(\mathbb{k})-1} = \arg \min_{\mathbf{u} \in \mathbb{U}_{m(\mathbb{k})-1}(t_{\mathbb{k}}^*)} \left\{ \text{TL}(\mathbf{u}, \widetilde{\Theta}(m(\mathbb{k}))) + \gamma \sum_{\bar{j}=1}^{m(\mathbb{k})-1} \mathbb{I}(u_{\bar{j}-1} \neq u_{\bar{j}}) \right\}. \quad (\text{S3.16})$$

As the number of initial estimated parameters is $m(\mathbb{k})$, the output consists of $m(\mathbb{k}) - 1$ raw estimated locations. In other words, we will remove the data after the endpoint $t_{\mathbb{k}}^*$ and discard the initial estimated parameters whose indices lie in $\mathcal{G}_{\mathbb{k}+1} \cup \dots \cup \mathcal{G}_{k^*+1}$. This choice is justified, as the true parameters $\boldsymbol{\theta}_{\mathbb{k}+1}^*, \boldsymbol{\theta}_{\mathbb{k}+2}^*, \dots, \boldsymbol{\theta}_{k^*+1}^*$ beyond the endpoint have been eliminated.

Consequently, their associated initial estimated parameters $\{\widetilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{\bar{j}}\}_{\bar{j}=\mathfrak{h}(\mathbb{k}+1)}^{m(\mathbb{k}+1)}, \{\widetilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{\bar{j}}\}_{\bar{j}=\mathfrak{h}(\mathbb{k}+2)}^{m(\mathbb{k}+2)}, \dots, \{\widetilde{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{\bar{j}}\}_{\bar{j}=\mathfrak{h}(k^*+1)}^{m(k^*+1)}$ are excluded, ensuring consistency between the input data and the optimization framework.

Then, by filtering duplicate raw locations through (12) (Main Paper), we have

$$\widehat{\mathbb{k}} - 1 = \left| \text{Unique}(\widehat{\mathbf{u}}_{m(\mathbb{k})-1}) \right|.$$

Proposition 5' (endpoint $t_{\mathbb{k}}^*$) Let $\widehat{\mathbf{u}}_{m(\mathbb{k})-1} = \{\widehat{u}_{\bar{j}}\}_{\bar{j}=1}^{m(\mathbb{k})-1} \in \mathbb{U}_{m(\mathbb{k})-1}(t_{\mathbb{k}}^*)$ be the solution to (S3.16) and $\widehat{\mathbb{k}} = |\text{Unique}(\widehat{\mathbf{u}}_{\mathbb{k}})|$. Then with probability at least $1 - n^{-5}$, the following conditions holds.

(i) For any $j \in [\mathbb{k} - 1]$, it must be the case that

$$\hat{u}_{m(j)} \in \mathcal{H}(0, \Delta/4; t_j^*).$$

(ii) In addition, for all $j \in [\mathbb{k}]$, it holds that

$$\hat{u}_{\hat{m}(j)} = \cdots = \hat{u}_{m(j)}.$$

In other words, it follows that $\hat{\mathbb{k}} = \mathbb{k}$.

Proof It should be noted that, since the endpoint satisfies $u_{m(\mathbb{k})}^* = t_{\mathbb{k}}^*$, the data $\mathcal{Z}_0^{t_{\mathbb{k}}^*}$ contains only $\mathbb{k} - 1$ true change points. Thus, it is sufficient to ensure that the intersection of events $\bigcap_{j=1}^{\mathbb{k}} \mathcal{A}_j$ and $\bigcap_{j=1}^{\mathbb{k}} \mathcal{B}_j$ hold with high probability. The rest of the proof is similar to the proof of Proposition 5 and is omitted for brevity. \blacksquare

S3.2 Proof of Lemmas in Section S3.1

Throughout this subsection, we assume that all the conditions in Theorem 4 (Main Paper) hold.

S3.2.1 CHANGES IN MEANS

Lemma S3.4 *Suppose Assumption 4 (Appendix). Let $j_1 \in [k^* + 1]$ and $j_2 \in [k^* + 1] \setminus \{j_1 - 1, j_1, j_1 + 1\}$. Then*

$$\|\boldsymbol{\mu}_{j_1}^* - \boldsymbol{\mu}_{j_2}^*\|_2 \leq C_k C_\kappa,$$

for some absolute constant C_k .

Proof It suffices to consider $j_1 = 1$ and $j_2 = k^* + 1$ as the general case is similar. Observe that

$$\|\boldsymbol{\mu}_1^* - \boldsymbol{\mu}_{k^*+1}^*\|_2 \leq \sum_{j=1}^{k^*} \|\boldsymbol{\mu}_j^* - \boldsymbol{\mu}_{j+1}^*\|_2 \leq k^* C_\kappa.$$

By Assumption 4d (Appendix), both C_κ and k^* are bounded. \blacksquare

The following lemma implies that, over a sufficiently long interval ($\Delta/4$) without change points, the loss function associated with "adjacent" estimated parameters (i.e., $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_{\tilde{j}_\pm}$ for $\tilde{j}_\pm \in \mathcal{G}_{j-1} \cup \mathcal{G}_{j+1}$) exceeds that of the "correct" estimated parameters (i.e., $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_{\tilde{j}}$ for $\tilde{j} \in \mathcal{G}_j$) by $C\Delta\kappa^2$. Moreover, when the loss function employs "incorrect" estimated parameters (i.e., $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_{\tilde{j}_\times}$ for $\tilde{j}_\times \notin \mathcal{G}_{j-1} \cup \mathcal{G}_j \cup \mathcal{G}_{j+1}$), it becomes necessary to establish an lower bound for the difference between this loss function and the one using the "correct" estimated parameters.

Lemma S3.5 *Under the same conditions as stated in Theorem 4 for model (2), and considering a sub-interval $\mathcal{I} \subseteq (t_{j-1}^*, t_j^*]$ for $j \in [k^* + 1]$, the following results hold uniformly for any fixed $\tilde{j} \in \mathcal{G}_j$ with probability at least $1 - n^{-5}$.*

(i) (Similar difference) For any $\tilde{j}' \in \mathcal{G}_j \setminus \{\tilde{j}\}$, it holds that for absolute constant $C > 0$,

$$\left| \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{I}, \tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_{\tilde{j}'}) - \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{I}, \tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_{\tilde{j}}) \right| \leq C \Delta_n^{-1} \lambda_1^2 s.$$

(ii) (Signal difference) For any $\tilde{j}_{\pm} \in \mathcal{G}_{j-1} \cup \mathcal{G}_{j+1}$, it holds that for absolute constant $C > 0$,

$$\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{I}, \tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_{\tilde{j}_{\pm}}) - \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{I}, \tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_{\tilde{j}}) \geq -Cs \log(np).$$

Furthermore, for any sub-interval satisfying $|\mathcal{I}| \geq C_d \Delta$, it holds that

$$\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{I}, \tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_{\tilde{j}_{\pm}}) - \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{I}, \tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_{\tilde{j}}) \geq C \Delta \kappa^2,$$

where $C_d > 0$ is absolute constant.

(iii) (Misplaced difference) For any $\tilde{j}_{\times} \in [\tilde{k} + 1] \setminus \{\mathcal{G}_{j-1} \cup \mathcal{G}_j \cup \mathcal{G}_{j+1}\}$, it holds that for absolute constant $C > 0$,

$$\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{I}, \tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_{\tilde{j}_{\times}}) - \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{I}, \tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_{\tilde{j}}) > -Cs \log(np).$$

Proof [Proof of Lemma S3.5(i)] In this proof, we denote

$$\boldsymbol{\mu}^* = \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\tilde{j}}, \quad \tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}} = \tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_{\tilde{j}}, \quad \text{and} \quad \tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}' = \tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_{\tilde{j}'}$$

It can verify that

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{I}, \tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}') - \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{I}, \tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}) \right| = \left| \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \left\| \mathbf{X}_i - \tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}' \right\|_2^2 - \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \left\| \mathbf{X}_i - \tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}} \right\|_2^2 \right| \\ &= \left| \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \left\| \mathbf{X}_i - \boldsymbol{\mu}^* + \boldsymbol{\mu}^* - \tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}' \right\|_2^2 - \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \left\| \mathbf{X}_i - \boldsymbol{\mu}^* + \boldsymbol{\mu}^* - \tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}} \right\|_2^2 \right| \\ &= \left| -2 \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_i^\top (\tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}' - \tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}) + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \left\| \tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}' - \boldsymbol{\mu}^* \right\|_2^2 - \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \left\| \tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}} - \boldsymbol{\mu}^* \right\|_2^2 \right| \\ &\leq \left| 2 \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_i^\top (\tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}' - \tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}) \right| + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \left\| \tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}' - \boldsymbol{\mu}^* \right\|_2^2 + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \left\| \tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}} - \boldsymbol{\mu}^* \right\|_2^2 \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S3.17})$$

Case 1 ($|\mathcal{I}| \geq C_I s \log(np)$). By applying Corollary 30 (Appendix), it holds with probability at least $1 - n^{-5}$ that

$$\begin{aligned} \left\| \tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}' - \boldsymbol{\mu}^* \right\|_2^2 &\leq C_1 \lambda_1^2 s / d_{\min}, \quad \left\| \tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}} - \boldsymbol{\mu}^* \right\|_2^2 \leq C_1 \lambda_1^2 s / d_{\min}, \\ \left\| \tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}' - \boldsymbol{\mu}^* \right\|_1 &\leq C_2 \lambda_1 s / d_{\min}^{1/2}, \quad \left\| \tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}} - \boldsymbol{\mu}^* \right\|_1 \leq C_2 \lambda_1 s / d_{\min}^{1/2}. \end{aligned}$$

Then, it holds with probability at least $1 - n^{-5}$ that

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_i^\top (\tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}' - \tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}) \right| &\leq \left\| \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_i \right\|_\infty \left\| \tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}' - \tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}} \right\|_1 \\ &\leq C_3 \sqrt{|\mathcal{I}| \log(np)} \left(\left\| \tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}' - \boldsymbol{\mu}^* \right\|_1 + \left\| \tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}} - \boldsymbol{\mu}^* \right\|_1 \right) \\ &\leq C_4 \sqrt{|\mathcal{I}| \log(np)} \lambda_1 s / d_{\min}^{1/2} \\ &\leq C_5 \lambda_1^2 s \sqrt{n / d_{\min}}, \end{aligned}$$

where the second inequality follows from Lemma 20 (Appendix) and the last inequality follows from $\lambda_1 \geq C\sqrt{\log(np)}$ and $|\mathcal{I}| < n$. Therefore, it holds with probability $1 - n^{-5}$

$$(S3.17) \leq 2C_1\lambda_1^2s(n/d_{\min}) + C_5\lambda_1^2s\sqrt{n/d_{\min}} \leq C_6\lambda_1^2s(n/\Delta).$$

Case 2 ($|\mathcal{I}| < C_I s \log(np)$). By the Lemma 20 (Appendix), it holds with probability at least $1 - n^{-5}$

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \varepsilon_i^\top (\tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}' - \tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}) \right| \leq \left\| \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \varepsilon_i \right\|_\infty \|\tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}' - \tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}\|_1 \\ & \leq C_7 \left(\sqrt{|\mathcal{I}| \log(np)} + \log(np) \right) \Upsilon_n^{-\iota^*} \sqrt{s} \kappa \\ & \leq C_8 \left(s \log(np) + \sqrt{s} \log(np) \right) \Upsilon_n^{-\iota^*} \kappa \\ & \leq C_9 s \log(np) \Upsilon_n^{-\iota^*}, \end{aligned}$$

where the second inequality follows from Corollary 30 (Appendix), the third inequality follows from $|\mathcal{I}| < C_I s \log(np)$, and the last inequality follows from the facts that $\kappa \leq C_\kappa$.

Therefore, for the case where $|\mathcal{I}| < C_I s \log(np)$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} (S3.17) & \leq 2C_9 s \log(np) \Upsilon_n^{-\iota^*} + 2C_1 \kappa^2 \Upsilon_n^{-2\iota^*} C_I s \log(np) \\ & \leq C_{10} s \log(np) \Upsilon_n^{-\iota^*} \ll C_{11} \lambda_1^2 s \leq C_{11} \lambda_1^2 s(n/\Delta), \end{aligned}$$

where the second inequality follows from $\kappa \leq C_\kappa$.

This completes the proof of result (i). ■

Proof [Proof of Lemma S3.5(ii)] In this proof, we denote

$$\begin{aligned} \boldsymbol{\mu}^* &= \boldsymbol{\mu}_j^*, & \tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}} &= \hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_j; \\ \boldsymbol{\mu}_\pm^* &= \boldsymbol{\mu}_{j-1}^* \mathbb{I}(\tilde{j}_\pm \in \mathcal{G}_{j-1}) + \boldsymbol{\mu}_{j+1}^* \mathbb{I}(\tilde{j}_\pm \in \mathcal{G}_{j+1}), & \tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_\pm &= \tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_{\tilde{j}_\pm}, \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\boldsymbol{\Psi}^* = \boldsymbol{\mu}_\pm^* - \boldsymbol{\mu}^*, \quad \tilde{\boldsymbol{\Psi}} = \tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_\pm - \tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}, \quad \tilde{\boldsymbol{\delta}} = \tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}} - \boldsymbol{\mu}^*.$$

We also denote

$$\kappa_\pm = \|\boldsymbol{\Psi}^*\|_2 = \|\boldsymbol{\mu}_\pm^* - \boldsymbol{\mu}^*\|_2.$$

Note that

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{I}, \tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_\pm) - \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{I}, \tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}) = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \left\| \mathbf{X}_i - \tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_\pm \right\|_2^2 - \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \left\| \mathbf{X}_i - \tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}} \right\|_2^2 \\ & = |\mathcal{I}| \|\tilde{\boldsymbol{\Psi}}\|_2^2 + 2|\mathcal{I}| \tilde{\boldsymbol{\Psi}}^\top \tilde{\boldsymbol{\delta}} - 2 \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \varepsilon_i^\top \tilde{\boldsymbol{\Psi}} \\ & = |\mathcal{I}| \left\| \boldsymbol{\Psi}^* + (\tilde{\boldsymbol{\Psi}} - \boldsymbol{\Psi}^*) \right\|_2^2 + 2|\mathcal{I}| \tilde{\boldsymbol{\Psi}}^\top \tilde{\boldsymbol{\delta}} - 2 \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \varepsilon_i^\top \tilde{\boldsymbol{\Psi}} \\ & \geq |\mathcal{I}| \|\boldsymbol{\Psi}^*\|_2^2 + 2|\mathcal{I}| (\boldsymbol{\Psi}^*)^\top (\tilde{\boldsymbol{\Psi}} - \boldsymbol{\Psi}^*) + 2|\mathcal{I}| \tilde{\boldsymbol{\Psi}}^\top \tilde{\boldsymbol{\delta}} - 2 \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \varepsilon_i^\top \tilde{\boldsymbol{\Psi}} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\geq |\mathcal{I}| \|\Psi^*\|_2^2 - 2|\mathcal{I}| \|\Psi^*\|_2 \|\tilde{\Psi} - \Psi^*\|_2 - 2|\mathcal{I}| \|\tilde{\Psi}\|_2 \|\tilde{\delta}\|_2 - 2 \left\| \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \varepsilon_i \right\|_\infty \|\tilde{\Psi}\|_1 \quad (\text{S3.18}) \\
 &= I - II - III - IV,
 \end{aligned}$$

where the last inequality follows from the Cauchy-Schwartz inequality. Next, we aim to bound the four terms above.

Step 1 (Bounding the first three terms). Suppose all the good events in Corollary 30 (Appendix) holds, we have the following relations with probability $1 - n^{-5}$,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \|\tilde{\Psi} - \Psi^*\|_2 &\leq \|\tilde{\mu} - \mu^*\|_2 + \|\tilde{\mu}_\pm - \mu_\pm^*\|_2 \leq 2C_1 \mathcal{Y}_n^{-\iota^*} \kappa_\pm, \\
 \|\tilde{\Psi} - \Psi^*\|_1 &\leq 4\sqrt{s} \|\tilde{\mu} - \mu^*\|_2 + 4\sqrt{s} \|\tilde{\mu}_\pm - \mu_\pm^*\|_2 \leq 8C_1 \mathcal{Y}_n^{-\iota^*} \sqrt{s} \kappa_\pm,
 \end{aligned}$$

where the second inequality of the first expression follows from $\kappa \leq \kappa_\pm$, and the first inequality of the second expression follows from $\|(\tilde{\mu} - \mu^*)_{S^c}\|_1 \leq 3\|(\tilde{\mu} - \mu^*)_S\|_1$ and $\|(\tilde{\mu}_\pm - \mu_\pm^*)_{S^c}\|_1 \leq 3\|(\tilde{\mu}_\pm - \mu_\pm^*)_S\|_1$ in turn implies that $\|\tilde{\mu} - \mu^*\|_1 \leq 4\sqrt{s} \|\tilde{\mu} - \mu^*\|_2$ and $\|\tilde{\mu}_\pm - \mu_\pm^*\|_1 \leq 4\sqrt{s} \|\tilde{\mu}_\pm - \mu_\pm^*\|_2$, respectively. In addition, with probability at least $1 - n^{-5}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 \|\tilde{\Psi}\|_2 &\leq \|\tilde{\Psi} - \Psi^*\|_2 + \|\Psi^*\|_2 \leq 2C_1 \mathcal{Y}_n^{-\iota^*} \kappa_\pm + \kappa_\pm \leq \frac{3}{2} \kappa_\pm, \\
 \|\tilde{\Psi}\|_1 &\leq \|\tilde{\Psi} - \Psi^*\|_1 + \|\Psi^*\|_1 \leq 8C_1 \mathcal{Y}_n^{-\iota^*} \sqrt{s} \kappa_\pm + k^* \sqrt{s} \kappa_\pm \leq \frac{3}{2} C_k \sqrt{s} \kappa_\pm,
 \end{aligned}$$

where the last inequality of the second expression follows from that $\mathcal{Y}_n^{-\iota^*} = o(1)$ and $k^* < C_k$ with a absolute constant $1 \leq C_k < \infty$. Thus, we can verify that

$$I - II - III \geq |\mathcal{I}| \kappa_\pm^2 - 4C_1 \mathcal{Y}_n^{-\iota^*} |\mathcal{I}| \kappa_\pm^2 - 3C_1 \mathcal{Y}_n^{-\iota^*} |\mathcal{I}| \kappa_\pm^2 \geq \frac{|\mathcal{I}| \kappa_\pm^2}{2}.$$

Step 2 (Bounding the last term). By Lemma 20 (Appendix) and $\|\tilde{\Psi}\|_1 \leq C_2 \sqrt{s} \kappa_\pm$, It holds with probability at least $1 - n^{-5}$ that

$$IV \leq \begin{cases} 3C_k \sqrt{|\mathcal{I}| s \log(np)} \kappa_\pm, & \text{for } |\mathcal{I}| \geq C_I s \log(np), \\ 3C_k \left(\sqrt{|\mathcal{I}| \log(np)} + \log(np) \right) \sqrt{s} \kappa_\pm, & \text{for } |\mathcal{I}| < C_I s \log(np). \end{cases}$$

where $C_I > 0$ is a sufficiently large constant. If $|\mathcal{I}| \geq C_I s \log(np)$, it can verify that

$$\begin{aligned}
 I - II - III - IV &\geq \frac{|\mathcal{I}| \kappa_\pm^2}{2} - 3C_k \sqrt{|\mathcal{I}| s \log(np)} \kappa_\pm \quad (\text{S3.19}) \\
 &\geq \frac{|\mathcal{I}| \kappa_\pm^2}{2} \left(1 - 6C_k \sqrt{\frac{s \log(np)}{|\mathcal{I}| \kappa_\pm^2}} \right) \\
 &\geq \frac{|\mathcal{I}| \kappa_\pm^2}{4} > 0
 \end{aligned}$$

where the third inequality follows from the fact that $|\mathcal{I}| \geq C_I s \log(np)$ with sufficiently large constant C_I . Clearly, when $|\mathcal{I}| \geq C_d \Delta \gg C_I s \log(np)$, we obtain

$$I - II - III - IV \geq \frac{|\mathcal{I}| \kappa_\pm^2}{4} \geq C_1 \Delta \kappa_\pm^2.$$

On the other hand, if $|\mathcal{I}| < C_I s \log(np)$, it can verify that

$$\begin{aligned}
 I - II - III - IV &\geq \frac{|\mathcal{I}|\kappa_{\pm}^2}{2} - 3C_k \left(\sqrt{|\mathcal{I}| \log(np)} + \log(np) \right) \sqrt{s}\kappa_{\pm} \\
 &\geq -3C_k \left(\sqrt{|\mathcal{I}| \log(np)} + \log(np) \right) \sqrt{s}\kappa_{\pm} \\
 &\geq -3C_k \left(C_I^{1/2} s \log(np) + \sqrt{s} \log(np) \right) \kappa_{\pm} \\
 &\geq -Cs \log(np),
 \end{aligned}$$

where the third inequality follows from $|\mathcal{I}| < C_I s \log(np)$ and the last inequality follows from $\kappa_{\pm} \leq C_{\kappa}$. \blacksquare

Proof [Proof of Lemma S3.5(iii)] We prepare to show **(iii)**. Following the notation used in the proof of Lemma S3.5(ii), we denote

$$\boldsymbol{\mu}_{\times}^* = \sum_{j' \in [k^*+1] \setminus \{j-1, j, j+1\}} \boldsymbol{\mu}_{j'}^* \mathbb{I}(\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_{\times} \in \mathcal{G}_{j'}), \quad \tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_{\times} = \tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_{\tilde{\mathcal{J}}_{\times}},$$

and

$$\boldsymbol{\Psi}_{\times}^* = \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\times}^* - \boldsymbol{\mu}^*, \quad \tilde{\boldsymbol{\Psi}}_{\times} = \tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_{\times} - \tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}.$$

Let's first consider the extreme case where $\|\boldsymbol{\Psi}_{\times}^*\|_2 = 0$, meaning $\boldsymbol{\mu}_{\times}^* = \boldsymbol{\mu}^*$. It is worth noting that a similar yet simpler argument as in **(i)** suffices to complete the proof.

Next, for a sufficiently large constant $C_I > 0$, we discuss the following two cases in two steps: $|\mathcal{I}| \|\boldsymbol{\Psi}_{\times}^*\|_2^2 \geq C_I s \log(np)$ and $|\mathcal{I}| \|\boldsymbol{\Psi}_{\times}^*\|_2^2 < C_I s \log(np)$. Based on Lemma S3.4, it follows that $c_0 \leq \|\boldsymbol{\Psi}_{\times}^*\|_2^2 \leq C_0$, where c_0 and C_0 are positive absolute constants.

Step 1. Consider case that $|\mathcal{I}| \|\boldsymbol{\Psi}_{\times}^*\|_2^2 \geq C_I s \log(np)$. Similar to the arguments in (S3.18), we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{I}, \tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_{\times}) - \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{I}, \tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}) \\
 &= \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \|\mathbf{X}_i - \tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_{\times}\|_2^2 - \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \|\mathbf{X}_i - \tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}\|_2^2 \\
 &\geq |\mathcal{I}| \|\boldsymbol{\Psi}_{\times}^*\|_2^2 - 2|\mathcal{I}| \|\boldsymbol{\Psi}_{\times}^*\|_2 \|\tilde{\boldsymbol{\Psi}}_{\times} - \boldsymbol{\Psi}_{\times}^*\|_2 - 2|\mathcal{I}| \|\tilde{\boldsymbol{\Psi}}_{\times}\|_2 \|\tilde{\boldsymbol{\delta}}\|_2 - 2 \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_i^{\top} \tilde{\boldsymbol{\Psi}}_{\times} \\
 &= I_{\times} - II_{\times} - III_{\times} - IV_{\times}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Note that the following relations hold with probability with $1 - n^{-5}$,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \|\tilde{\boldsymbol{\Psi}}_{\times} - \boldsymbol{\Psi}_{\times}^*\|_2 &\leq 2C_1 \mathcal{Y}_n^{-\iota^*} \kappa, \\
 \|\tilde{\boldsymbol{\Psi}}_{\times} - \boldsymbol{\Psi}_{\times}^*\|_1 &\leq 8C_1 \mathcal{Y}_n^{-\iota^*} \sqrt{s}\kappa, \\
 \|\tilde{\boldsymbol{\Psi}}_{\times}\|_2 &\leq 2C_1 \mathcal{Y}_n^{-\iota^*} \kappa + \|\boldsymbol{\Psi}_{\times}^*\|_2, \\
 \|\tilde{\boldsymbol{\Psi}}_{\times}\|_1 &\leq 8C_1 \mathcal{Y}_n^{-\iota^*} \sqrt{s}\kappa + C_k \sqrt{s} \|\boldsymbol{\Psi}_{\times}^*\|_2,
 \end{aligned} \tag{S3.20}$$

where the above four inequalities are derived using arguments similar to those in proof of part(ii). Therefore, with probability at least $1 - n^{-5}$,

$$I_{\times} - II_{\times} - III_{\times} - IV_{\times}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\geq |\mathcal{I}| \|\Psi_{\times}^*\|_2^2 - 4C_1 \mathcal{Y}_n^{-\iota^*} \kappa |\mathcal{I}| \|\Psi_{\times}^*\|_2 - 2|\mathcal{I}| \left(2C_1 \mathcal{Y}_n^{-\iota^*} \kappa + \|\Psi_{\times}^*\|_2 \right) C_1 \mathcal{Y}_n^{-\iota^*} \kappa \\
 &\quad - 2 \left\| \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \varepsilon_i \right\|_{\infty} \left(8C_1 \mathcal{Y}_n^{-\iota^*} \sqrt{s} \kappa + C_k \sqrt{s} \|\Psi_{\times}^*\|_2 \right) \\
 &\geq |\mathcal{I}| \|\Psi_{\times}^*\|_2^2 \left(1 - \frac{6C_1 C_{\kappa}}{\mathcal{Y}_n^{\iota^*} \|\Psi_{\times}^*\|_2} - \frac{4C_1 C_{\kappa}^2}{\mathcal{Y}_n^{2\iota^*} \|\Psi_{\times}^*\|_2^2} \right) \\
 &\quad - 2\sqrt{s} \|\Psi_{\times}^*\|_2 \left\| \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \varepsilon_i \right\|_{\infty} \left(\frac{8C_1 C_{\kappa}}{\mathcal{Y}_n^{\iota^*} \|\Psi_{\times}^*\|_2} + C_k \right) \\
 &\geq \frac{1}{2} |\mathcal{I}| \|\Psi_{\times}^*\|_2^2 - 3C_k \sqrt{s} \|\Psi_{\times}^*\|_2 \left\| \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \varepsilon_i \right\|_{\infty} \\
 &\geq \frac{1}{2} |\mathcal{I}| \|\Psi_{\times}^*\|_2^2 \left(1 - 6C_k \sqrt{\frac{s \log(np)}{|\mathcal{I}| \|\Psi_{\times}^*\|_2^2}} \right) \\
 &\geq C_2 s \log(np),
 \end{aligned}$$

where the first inequality follows from the statements (S3.20), the second inequality follows from that $\kappa \leq C_{\kappa}$, the third inequality follows from the observation that $\mathcal{Y}_n^{-\iota^*} = o(1)$, the penultimate and the final inequalities hold by the choice of $|\mathcal{I}| \|\Psi_{\times}^*\|_2^2 \geq C_I s \log(np)$ for a sufficiently large absolute constant $C_I > 0$.

Step 2. As for $|\mathcal{I}| \|\Psi_{\times}^*\|_2^2 < C_I s \log(np)$, we consider the upper bound for $|\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{I}, \tilde{\mu}_{\times}) - \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{I}, \tilde{\mu})|$. With probability at least $1 - n^{-5}$, it holds that

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\left| \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{I}, \tilde{\mu}_{\times}) - \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{I}, \tilde{\mu}) \right| \\
 &\leq |\mathcal{I}| \|\tilde{\Psi}_{\times}\|_2^2 + 2|\mathcal{I}| \left| \tilde{\Psi}_{\times}^{\top} \tilde{\delta} \right| + 2 \left| \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \varepsilon_i^{\top} \tilde{\Psi}_{\times} \right| \\
 &\leq |\mathcal{I}| \left\| \Psi_{\times}^* + (\tilde{\Psi}_{\times} - \Psi_{\times}^*) \right\|_2^2 + 2|\mathcal{I}| \left| \tilde{\Psi}_{\times}^{\top} \tilde{\delta} \right| + 2 \left| \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \varepsilon_i^{\top} \tilde{\Psi}_{\times} \right| \\
 &\leq |\mathcal{I}| \|\Psi_{\times}^*\|_2^2 + 2|\mathcal{I}| \|\Psi_{\times}^*\|_2 \|\tilde{\Psi}_{\times} - \Psi_{\times}^*\|_2 + |\mathcal{I}| \|\tilde{\Psi}_{\times} - \Psi_{\times}^*\|_2^2 \\
 &\quad + 2|\mathcal{I}| \|\tilde{\Psi}_{\times}\|_2 \|\tilde{\delta}\|_2 + 2 \left\| \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \varepsilon_i \right\|_{\infty} \|\tilde{\Psi}_{\times}\|_1 \\
 &\leq |\mathcal{I}| \|\Psi_{\times}^*\|_2^2 + 4C_1 \mathcal{Y}_n^{-\iota^*} \kappa |\mathcal{I}| \|\Psi_{\times}^*\|_2 + 4C_1^2 \mathcal{Y}_n^{-2\iota^*} \kappa^2 |\mathcal{I}| + 2|\mathcal{I}| \left(2C_1 \mathcal{Y}_n^{-\iota^*} \kappa + \|\Psi_{\times}^*\|_2 \right) C_1 \mathcal{Y}_n^{-\iota^*} \kappa \\
 &\quad + 2 \left\| \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \varepsilon_i \right\|_{\infty} \left(8C_1 \mathcal{Y}_n^{-\iota^*} \sqrt{s} \kappa + C_k \sqrt{s} \|\Psi_{\times}^*\|_2 \right) \\
 &\leq |\mathcal{I}| \|\Psi_{\times}^*\|_2^2 \left(1 + \frac{6C_1 C_{\kappa}}{\mathcal{Y}_n^{\iota^*} \|\Psi_{\times}^*\|_2} + \frac{8C_1 C_{\kappa}^2}{\mathcal{Y}_n^{2\iota^*} \|\Psi_{\times}^*\|_2^2} \right) + 2\sqrt{s} \|\Psi_{\times}^*\|_2 \left\| \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \varepsilon_i \right\|_{\infty} \left(\frac{8C_1 C_{\kappa}}{\mathcal{Y}_n^{\iota^*} \|\Psi_{\times}^*\|_2} + C_k \right) \\
 &\leq \frac{3}{2} |\mathcal{I}| \|\Psi_{\times}^*\|_2^2 + 3C_k \sqrt{s} \|\Psi_{\times}^*\|_2 \left\| \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \varepsilon_i \right\|_{\infty} \\
 &\leq C_4 s \log(np) + C_5 \sqrt{s} \|\Psi_{\times}^*\|_2 \left(\sqrt{|\mathcal{I}| \log(np)} + \log(np) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\leq C_6 s \log(np),$$

where the first to the sixth inequalities follows from a similar argument to **Step 1**, the penultimate inequality follows from Lemma 20 (Appendix) and the last inequality holds by the choice of $|\mathcal{I}| \|\Psi_\times^*\|_2^2 < C_I s \log(np)$ for a sufficiently large absolute constant $C_I > 0$. This completes the proof. \blacksquare

S3.2.2 CHANGES IN REGRESSION COEFFICIENTS

Lemma S3.6 *Suppose Assumption 5 (Appendix). Let $j_1 \in [k^* + 1]$ and $j_2 \in [k^* + 1] \setminus \{j_1 - 1, j_1, j_1 + 1\}$. Then*

$$\|\beta_{j_1}^* - \beta_{j_2}^*\|_2 \leq C_k C_\kappa,$$

for some absolute constant C_k .

Proof It suffices to consider $j_1 = 1$ and $j_2 = k^* + 1$ as the general case is similar. Observe that

$$\|\beta_1^* - \beta_{k^*+1}^*\|_2 \leq \sum_{j=1}^{k^*} \|\beta_j^* - \beta_{j+1}^*\|_2 \leq k^* C_\kappa.$$

By Assumption 5d (Appendix), both C_κ and k^* are bounded. \blacksquare

Lemma S3.7 *Under the same conditions as stated in Theorem 4 for model (3), and considering a sub-interval $\mathcal{I} \subseteq (t_{j-1}^*, t_j^*]$ for $j \in [k^* + 1]$, the following results hold uniformly for any fixed $\tilde{j} \in \mathcal{G}_j$ with probability at least $1 - n^{-5}$.*

(i) *(Similar difference) For any $\tilde{j}' \in \mathcal{G}_j \setminus \{\tilde{j}\}$, it holds that for absolute constant $C > 0$,*

$$\left| \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{I}, \tilde{\beta}_{\tilde{j}'}) - \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{I}, \tilde{\beta}_{\tilde{j}}) \right| \leq C \Delta_n^{-1} \lambda_1^2 s.$$

(ii) *(Signal difference) For any $\tilde{j}_\pm \in \mathcal{G}_{j-1} \cup \mathcal{G}_{j+1}$, it holds that for absolute constant $C > 0$,*

$$\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{I}, \tilde{\beta}_{\tilde{j}_\pm}) - \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{I}, \tilde{\beta}_{\tilde{j}}) \geq -C s \log(np).$$

Furthermore, for any sub-interval satisfying $|\mathcal{I}| \geq C_d \Delta$, it holds that

$$\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{I}, \tilde{\beta}_{\tilde{j}_\pm}) - \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{I}, \tilde{\beta}_{\tilde{j}}) \geq C \Delta \kappa^2,$$

where $C_d > 0$ is absolute constant.

(iii) *(Misplaced difference) For any $\tilde{j}_\times \in [\tilde{k} + 1] \setminus \{\mathcal{G}_{j-1} \cup \mathcal{G}_j \cup \mathcal{G}_{j+1}\}$, it holds that for absolute constant $C > 0$,*

$$\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{I}, \tilde{\beta}_{\tilde{j}_\times}) - \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{I}, \tilde{\beta}_{\tilde{j}}) > -C s \log(np).$$

Proof [Proof of Lemma S3.7(i)] In this proof, we denote

$$\boldsymbol{\beta}^* = \boldsymbol{\beta}_j^*, \quad \tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}} = \tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_j, \quad \text{and} \quad \tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}}' = \tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_{j'}.$$

We also denote

$$\tilde{\boldsymbol{\delta}} = \tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}} - \boldsymbol{\beta}^*, \quad \text{and} \quad \tilde{\boldsymbol{\delta}}' = \tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}}' - \boldsymbol{\beta}^*.$$

It can verify that

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{I}, \tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}}') - \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{I}, \tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}}) \right| = \left| \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (y_i - \mathbf{X}_i^\top \tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}}')^2 - \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (y_i - \mathbf{X}_i^\top \tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}})^2 \right| \\ &= \left| \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (y_i - \mathbf{X}_i^\top \boldsymbol{\beta}^* + \mathbf{X}_i^\top \boldsymbol{\beta}^* - \mathbf{X}_i^\top \tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}}')^2 - \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (y_i - \mathbf{X}_i^\top \boldsymbol{\beta}^* + \mathbf{X}_i^\top \boldsymbol{\beta}^* - \mathbf{X}_i^\top \tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}})^2 \right| \\ &= \left| -2 \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \varepsilon_i \mathbf{X}_i^\top (\tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}}' - \tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}}) + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (\mathbf{X}_i^\top \tilde{\boldsymbol{\delta}}')^2 - \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (\mathbf{X}_i^\top \tilde{\boldsymbol{\delta}})^2 \right| \\ &\leq \left| 2 \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \varepsilon_i \mathbf{X}_i^\top (\tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}}' - \tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}}) \right| + \left| \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (\mathbf{X}_i^\top \tilde{\boldsymbol{\delta}}')^2 \right| + \left| \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (\mathbf{X}_i^\top \tilde{\boldsymbol{\delta}})^2 \right|. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S3.21})$$

Case 1 ($|\mathcal{I}| \geq C_I s \log(np)$). It holds with probability at least $1 - n^{-5}$ that

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \varepsilon_i \mathbf{X}_i^\top (\tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}}' - \tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}}) \right| &\leq \left\| \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \varepsilon_i \mathbf{X}_i \right\|_\infty \|\tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}}' - \tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}}\|_1 \\ &\leq C_1 \sqrt{|\mathcal{I}| \log(np)} \left(\|\tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}}' - \boldsymbol{\beta}^*\|_1 + \|\tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}} - \boldsymbol{\beta}^*\|_1 \right) \\ &\leq C_2 \sqrt{|\mathcal{I}| \log(np)} \lambda_1 s / d_{\min}^{1/2} \\ &\leq C_3 \lambda_1^2 s \sqrt{n / d_{\min}}, \end{aligned}$$

where the second inequality follows from Lemma 25(i) (Appendix), the third inequality follows from Corollary 33 (Appendix) and the last inequality follows from $\lambda_1 \geq C \sqrt{\log(np)}$ and $|\mathcal{I}| < n$.

Moreover, it follows from Lemma 26(ii) (Appendix) that with probability at least $1 - n^{-5}$,

$$\left| \frac{1}{|\mathcal{I}|} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (\mathbf{X}_i^\top \tilde{\boldsymbol{\delta}}')^2 - (\tilde{\boldsymbol{\delta}}')^\top \boldsymbol{\Sigma} \tilde{\boldsymbol{\delta}}' \right| \leq C_4 \|\tilde{\boldsymbol{\delta}}'\|_2^2 \sqrt{\frac{s \log(np)}{|\mathcal{I}|}}.$$

The above display gives

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \frac{1}{|\mathcal{I}|} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (\mathbf{X}_i^\top \tilde{\boldsymbol{\delta}}')^2 \right| &\leq \bar{\rho}_x \|\tilde{\boldsymbol{\delta}}'\|_2^2 + C_4 \|\tilde{\boldsymbol{\delta}}'\|_2^2 \sqrt{\frac{s \log(np)}{|\mathcal{I}|}} \\ &\leq \bar{\rho}_x \|\tilde{\boldsymbol{\delta}}'\|_2^2 + C_4 \|\tilde{\boldsymbol{\delta}}'\|_2^2 \sqrt{\frac{s \log(np)}{C_I s \log(np)}} \\ &\leq C_5 \lambda_1^2 s / d_{\min}, \end{aligned}$$

where the second inequality follows from the assumption that $|\mathcal{I}| \geq C_I s \log(np)$, and the last inequality follows from Corollary 33 (Appendix). The analysis of the last term of (S3.21) is similar to the second term of (S3.21), and thus omitted. Therefore, it holds with probability $1 - n^{-5}$

$$(S3.21) \leq 2C_5 \lambda_1^2 s(n/d_{\min}) + 2C_3 \lambda_1^2 s \sqrt{n/d_{\min}} \leq C_6 \lambda_1^2 s(n/\Delta).$$

Case 2 ($|\mathcal{I}| < C_I s \log(np)$). Note that

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \varepsilon_i \mathbf{X}_i^\top (\tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}}' - \tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}}) \right| &\leq \left\| \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \varepsilon_i \mathbf{X}_i \right\|_\infty \|\tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}}' - \tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}}\|_1 \\ &\leq C_7 \left(\sqrt{|\mathcal{I}| \log(np)} + \log(np) \right) \Upsilon_n^{-\iota^*} \sqrt{s} \kappa \\ &\leq C_8 \left(s \log(np) + \sqrt{s} \log(np) \right) \Upsilon_n^{-\iota^*} \kappa \\ &\leq C_9 s \log(np) \Upsilon_n^{-\iota^*}, \end{aligned}$$

where the second inequality follows from Lemma 25(i) (Appendix) and Corollary 33 (Appendix), the third inequality follows from $|\mathcal{I}| < C_I s \log(np)$, and the last inequality follows from the facts that $\kappa \leq C_\kappa$.

Moreover, it follows from Lemma 26(i) (Appendix) that with probability at least $1 - n^{-5}$,

$$\left| \frac{1}{|\mathcal{I}|} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (\mathbf{X}_i^\top \tilde{\boldsymbol{\delta}}')^2 - (\tilde{\boldsymbol{\delta}}')^\top \boldsymbol{\Sigma} \tilde{\boldsymbol{\delta}}' \right| \leq C_{10} \|\tilde{\boldsymbol{\delta}}'\|_2^2 \left(\sqrt{\frac{s \log(np)}{|\mathcal{I}|}} + \frac{s \log(np)}{|\mathcal{I}|} \right).$$

The above display gives

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (\mathbf{X}_i^\top \tilde{\boldsymbol{\delta}}')^2 \right| &\leq |\mathcal{I}| \bar{\rho}_x \|\tilde{\boldsymbol{\delta}}'\|_2^2 + C_{10} \|\tilde{\boldsymbol{\delta}}'\|_2^2 \left(\sqrt{|\mathcal{I}| s \log(np)} + s \log(np) \right) \\ &\leq C_{11} \|\tilde{\boldsymbol{\delta}}'\|_2^2 s \log(np) + C_{12} \|\tilde{\boldsymbol{\delta}}'\|_2^2 s \log(np) \\ &\leq C_{13} s \log(np) \Upsilon_n^{-2\iota^*}, \end{aligned}$$

where the second inequality follows from $|\mathcal{I}| < C_I s \log(np)$ and the last inequality follows from Corollary 33 (Appendix) and $\kappa \leq C_\kappa$. The analysis of the last term of (S3.21) is similar to the second term of (S3.21) in this case, and thus omitted.

Therefore, for the case where $|\mathcal{I}| < C_I s \log(np)$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} (S3.21) &\leq C_9 s \log(np) \Upsilon_n^{-\iota^*} + 2C_{13} s \log(np) \Upsilon_n^{-2\iota^*} \\ &\ll C_{14} \lambda_1^2 s \leq C_{14} \lambda_1^2 s(n/\Delta). \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof of result (i). ■

Proof [Proof of Lemma S3.7(ii)] In this proof, we denote

$$\begin{aligned} \boldsymbol{\beta}^* &= \boldsymbol{\beta}_j^*, & \tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}} &= \tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_j; \\ \boldsymbol{\beta}_\pm^* &= \boldsymbol{\beta}_{j-1}^* \mathbb{I}(\tilde{j}_\pm \in \mathcal{G}_{j-1}) + \boldsymbol{\beta}_{j+1}^* \mathbb{I}(\tilde{j}_\pm \in \mathcal{G}_{j+1}), & \tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_\pm &= \tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_{\tilde{j}_\pm}, \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\Psi^* = \beta_{\pm}^* - \beta^*, \quad \tilde{\Psi} = \tilde{\beta}_{\pm} - \tilde{\beta}, \quad \tilde{\delta} = \tilde{\beta} - \beta^*, \quad \tilde{\delta}_{\pm} = \tilde{\beta}_{\pm} - \beta_{\pm}^*.$$

We also denote

$$\kappa_{\pm} = \|\Psi^*\|_2 = \|\beta_{\pm}^* - \beta^*\|_2.$$

Note that

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{I}, \tilde{\beta}_{\pm}) - \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{I}, \tilde{\beta}) = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (y_i - \mathbf{X}_i^{\top} \tilde{\beta}_{\pm})^2 - \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (y_i - \mathbf{X}_i^{\top} \tilde{\beta})^2 \\ &= \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (y_i - \mathbf{X}_i^{\top} \beta^* + \mathbf{X}_i^{\top} \beta^* - \mathbf{X}_i^{\top} \tilde{\beta}_{\pm})^2 - \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (y_i - \mathbf{X}_i^{\top} \beta^* + \mathbf{X}_i^{\top} \beta^* - \mathbf{X}_i^{\top} \tilde{\beta})^2 \\ &= -2 \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \varepsilon_i \mathbf{X}_i^{\top} \tilde{\Psi} + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (\mathbf{X}_i^{\top} (\tilde{\beta}_{\pm} - \beta^*))^2 - \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (\mathbf{X}_i^{\top} \tilde{\delta})^2 \\ &= \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (\mathbf{X}_i^{\top} \tilde{\Psi})^2 + 2 \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \tilde{\Psi}^{\top} \mathbf{X}_i \mathbf{X}_i^{\top} \tilde{\delta} - 2 \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \varepsilon_i \mathbf{X}_i^{\top} \tilde{\Psi} \\ &\geq \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (\mathbf{X}_i^{\top} \tilde{\Psi})^2 - 2 \left| \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \tilde{\Psi}^{\top} \mathbf{X}_i \mathbf{X}_i^{\top} \tilde{\delta} \right| - 2 \left| \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \varepsilon_i \mathbf{X}_i^{\top} \tilde{\Psi} \right| \\ &= I - 2II - 2III. \end{aligned}$$

Next, we aim to bound the three terms above.

Suppose all the good events in Corollary 33 (Appendix) holds, we have the following relations with probability $1 - n^{-5}$,

$$\begin{aligned} \|\tilde{\Psi} - \Psi^*\|_2 &\leq \|\tilde{\delta}\|_2 + \|\tilde{\delta}_{\pm}\|_2 \leq 2C\Upsilon_n^{-\iota^*} \kappa \leq 2C\Upsilon_n^{-\iota^*} \kappa_{\pm}, \\ \|\tilde{\Psi} - \Psi^*\|_1 &\leq 4\sqrt{s}\|\tilde{\delta}\|_2 + 4\sqrt{s}\|\tilde{\delta}_{\pm}\|_2 \leq 8C\Upsilon_n^{-\iota^*} \sqrt{s}\kappa_{\pm}, \end{aligned} \tag{S3.22}$$

In addition, with probability at least $1 - n^{-5}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \|\tilde{\Psi}\|_2 &\leq \|\tilde{\Psi} - \Psi^*\|_2 + \|\Psi^*\|_2 \leq 2C\Upsilon_n^{-\iota^*} \kappa_{\pm} + \kappa_{\pm} \leq \frac{3}{2}\kappa_{\pm}, \\ \|\tilde{\Psi}\|_1 &\leq \|\tilde{\Psi} - \Psi^*\|_1 + \|\Psi^*\|_1 \leq 8C\Upsilon_n^{-\iota^*} \sqrt{s}\kappa_{\pm} + C_k \sqrt{s}\kappa_{\pm} \leq \frac{3}{2}C_k \sqrt{s}\kappa_{\pm}, \end{aligned} \tag{S3.23}$$

where the last inequality of both expressions follows from that $\Upsilon_n^{-\iota^*} = o(1)$.

Step 1: the term I. It can verify that

$$\begin{aligned} I &= \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (\mathbf{X}_i^{\top} \Psi^*)^2 + 2 \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (\Psi^*)^{\top} \mathbf{X}_i \mathbf{X}_i^{\top} (\tilde{\Psi} - \Psi^*) + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (\mathbf{X}_i^{\top} (\tilde{\Psi} - \Psi^*))^2 \\ &\geq \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (\mathbf{X}_i^{\top} \Psi^*)^2 - 2 \left| \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (\Psi^*)^{\top} \mathbf{X}_i \mathbf{X}_i^{\top} (\tilde{\Psi} - \Psi^*) \right| \\ &\geq \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (\mathbf{X}_i^{\top} \Psi^*)^2 - 2 \left\{ \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (\mathbf{X}_i^{\top} \Psi^*)^2 \right\}^{1/2} \left\{ \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (\mathbf{X}_i^{\top} (\tilde{\Psi} - \Psi^*))^2 \right\}^{1/2} \\ &= I_1 - 2I_2^{1/2} I_3^{1/2}, \end{aligned}$$

where the second inequality follows from Cauchy-Schwartz inequality. Therefore, by Lemma 25(iii) (Appendix), we have

$$\begin{aligned} I_1 &\geq \underline{\rho}_x |\mathcal{I}| \kappa_{\pm}^2 - C_1 (\sqrt{|\mathcal{I}| \log(np)} + \log(np)) \kappa_{\pm}^2, \\ I_2 &\leq \bar{\rho}_x |\mathcal{I}| \kappa_{\pm}^2 + C_1 (\sqrt{|\mathcal{I}| \log(np)} + \log(np)) \kappa_{\pm}^2, \end{aligned}$$

with at least probability $1 - n^{-5}$. If $|\mathcal{I}| \geq C_I s \log(np)$ with a sufficiently large constant, we have

$$\begin{aligned} I_1 &\geq \underline{\rho}_x |\mathcal{I}| \kappa_{\pm}^2 - C_1 \sqrt{|\mathcal{I}| \log(np)} \kappa_{\pm}^2 \\ &\geq \underline{\rho}_x |\mathcal{I}| \kappa_{\pm}^2 \left(1 - \frac{C_1}{\underline{\rho}_x} \sqrt{\frac{\log(np)}{|\mathcal{I}|}}\right) \geq \frac{1}{2} \underline{\rho}_x |\mathcal{I}| \kappa_{\pm}^2. \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, it holds that $I_2 \leq 3/2 \bar{\rho}_x |\mathcal{I}| \kappa_{\pm}^2$. Moreover, by Lemma 26(iii) (Appendix), it follows with probability at least $1 - n^{-5}$,

$$\begin{aligned} I_3 &\leq C_2 (\|\tilde{\Psi} - \Psi^*\|_2^2 + \frac{1}{s} \|\tilde{\Psi} - \Psi^*\|_1^2) \left\{ \sqrt{|\mathcal{I}| s \log(np)} + s \log(np) + |\mathcal{I}| \bar{\rho}_x \right\} \\ &\leq C_2 (4C^2 \Upsilon_n^{-2\iota^*} \kappa_{\pm}^2 + 64C^2 \Upsilon_n^{-2\iota^*} \kappa_{\pm}^2) \left\{ \sqrt{|\mathcal{I}| s \log(np)} + s \log(np) + |\mathcal{I}| \bar{\rho}_x \right\} \\ &\leq C_3 \Upsilon_n^{-2\iota^*} \kappa_{\pm}^2 \left\{ \sqrt{|\mathcal{I}| s \log(np)} + s \log(np) + |\mathcal{I}| \right\}, \end{aligned}$$

where the second inequality follows from (S3.22).

Step 2: the term II . Some algebra shows that

$$\begin{aligned} II &\leq \left| \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (\tilde{\Psi} - \Psi^*)^\top \mathbf{X}_i \mathbf{X}_i^\top \tilde{\delta} \right| + \left| \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (\Psi^*)^\top \mathbf{X}_i \mathbf{X}_i^\top \tilde{\delta} \right| \\ &\leq \left\{ \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (\mathbf{X}_i^\top (\tilde{\Psi} - \Psi^*))^2 \right\}^{1/2} \left\{ \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (\mathbf{X}_i^\top \tilde{\delta})^2 \right\}^{1/2} \\ &\quad + \left\{ \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (\mathbf{X}_i^\top \Psi^*)^2 \right\}^{1/2} \left\{ \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (\mathbf{X}_i^\top \tilde{\delta})^2 \right\}^{1/2} \\ &= II_1^{1/2} \cdot II_2^{1/2} + II_3^{1/2} \cdot II_2^{1/2}, \end{aligned}$$

where the second inequality follows from Cauchy-Schwartz inequality. By Lemma 25(iii) (Appendix) and Lemma 26(i)(iii) (Appendix), it follows with probability at least $1 - n^{-5}$,

$$\begin{aligned} II_1 &\leq C_3 \Upsilon_n^{-2\iota^*} \kappa_{\pm}^2 \left\{ \sqrt{|\mathcal{I}| s \log(np)} + s \log(np) + |\mathcal{I}| \right\}, \\ II_2 &\leq C_4 \Upsilon_n^{-2\iota^*} \kappa_{\pm}^2 \left\{ \sqrt{|\mathcal{I}| s \log(np)} + s \log(np) + |\mathcal{I}| \right\}, \\ II_3 &\leq \bar{\rho}_x |\mathcal{I}| \kappa_{\pm}^2 + C_1 (\sqrt{|\mathcal{I}| \log(np)} + \log(np)) \kappa_{\pm}^2, \end{aligned}$$

where the all inequalities is similar to the arguments of **Step 1**.

Step 3: the term III . Note that for a absolute constant $C > 0$, with probability at least $1 - n^{-5}$, it holds that

$$III \leq \left\| \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \varepsilon_i \mathbf{X}_i^\top \right\|_\infty \left\| \tilde{\Psi} \right\|_1 \leq \frac{3}{2} C C_k \left(\sqrt{|\mathcal{I}| \log(np)} + \log(np) \right) \sqrt{s \kappa_\pm},$$

where the last inequality follows from Lemma 25(i) (Appendix) and (S3.23).

Step 4. We now discuss lower bounds for I, II, III under two cases.

Case 1: $|\mathcal{I}| \geq C_I s \log(np)$. It holds with probability at least $1 - n^{-5}$,

$$\begin{aligned} I &\geq I_1 - 2I_2^{1/2} I_3^{1/2} \\ &\geq \frac{\rho_x}{2} |\mathcal{I}| \kappa_\pm^2 - 2 \left\{ \frac{3}{2} \bar{\rho}_x |\mathcal{I}| \kappa_\pm^2 \right\}^{1/2} \left\{ C_3 |\mathcal{I}| \Upsilon_n^{-2\iota^*} \kappa_\pm^2 \right\}^{1/2} \\ &\geq \frac{\rho_x}{4} |\mathcal{I}| \kappa_\pm^2, \end{aligned} \tag{S3.24}$$

$$\begin{aligned} II &\leq II_1^{1/2} \cdot II_2^{1/2} + II_3^{1/2} \cdot II_2^{1/2} \\ &\leq \left\{ C_3 |\mathcal{I}| \Upsilon_n^{-2\iota^*} \kappa_\pm^2 \right\}^{1/2} \left\{ C_4 |\mathcal{I}| \Upsilon_n^{-2\iota^*} \kappa_\pm^2 \right\}^{1/2} + \left\{ \frac{3}{2} \bar{\rho}_x |\mathcal{I}| \kappa_\pm^2 \right\}^{1/2} \left\{ C_4 |\mathcal{I}| \Upsilon_n^{-2\iota^*} \kappa_\pm^2 \right\}^{1/2} \\ &\leq \sqrt{C_3 C_4} \Upsilon_n^{-2\iota^*} |\mathcal{I}| \kappa_\pm^2 + \sqrt{\frac{3}{2} \bar{\rho}_x} C_4 \Upsilon_n^{-\iota^*} |\mathcal{I}| \kappa_\pm^2 \\ &\leq C_5 \Upsilon_n^{-2\iota^*} |\mathcal{I}| \kappa_\pm^2, \end{aligned} \tag{S3.25}$$

$$III \leq C_6 \sqrt{|\mathcal{I}| s \log(np)} \kappa_\pm, \tag{S3.26}$$

where the second inequalities of I, II follow from the fact that C_I is a sufficiently large constant and relations $s \log(np) \leq \sqrt{|\mathcal{I}| s \log(np)} \leq |\mathcal{I}|$, and the last inequality of I follows from $\Upsilon_n^{-\iota^*} = o(1)$. Combining (S3.24), (S3.25) and (S3.26), it follows with probability at least $1 - n^{-5}$,

$$\begin{aligned} I - 2II - 2III &\geq \frac{\rho_x}{4} |\mathcal{I}| \kappa_\pm^2 - 2C_5 \Upsilon_n^{-2\iota^*} |\mathcal{I}| \kappa_\pm^2 - 2C_6 \sqrt{|\mathcal{I}| s \log(np)} \kappa_\pm \\ &\geq C_7 |\mathcal{I}| \kappa_\pm^2 - 2C_6 \sqrt{|\mathcal{I}| s \log(np)} \kappa_\pm \\ &\geq C_7 |\mathcal{I}| \kappa_\pm^2 \left(1 - \frac{2C_6}{C_7} \sqrt{\frac{s \log(np)}{|\mathcal{I}| \kappa_\pm^2}} \right) \geq \frac{C_7}{2} |\mathcal{I}| \kappa_\pm^2 > 0, \end{aligned} \tag{S3.27}$$

where the fourth inequality follows from the fact that $|\mathcal{I}| \geq C_I s \log(np)$ with sufficiently large constant C_I . Clearly, when $|\mathcal{I}| \geq C_d \Delta \gg C_I s \log(np)$, we obtain $I - 2II - 2III \geq C_8 \Delta \kappa_\pm^2$.

Case 2: $|\mathcal{I}| < C_I s \log(np)$. It holds with probability at least $1 - n^{-5}$,

$$\begin{aligned} II &\leq II_1^{1/2} \cdot II_2^{1/2} + II_3^{1/2} \cdot II_2^{1/2} \\ &\leq \sqrt{C_3 C_4} \Upsilon_n^{-2\iota^*} \kappa_\pm^2 \left\{ \sqrt{|\mathcal{I}| s \log(np)} + s \log(np) + |\mathcal{I}| \right\} \\ &\quad + \left\{ C_4 \Upsilon_n^{-2\iota^*} \kappa_\pm^2 \left\{ \sqrt{|\mathcal{I}| s \log(np)} + s \log(np) + |\mathcal{I}| \right\} \right\}^{1/2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \cdot \left\{ \bar{\rho}_x |\mathcal{I}| \kappa_{\pm}^2 + C_1 (\sqrt{|\mathcal{I}| \log(np)} + \log(np)) \kappa_{\pm}^2 \right\}^{1/2} \\
 & \leq C_9 \Upsilon_n^{-2\iota^*} \max \left\{ \sqrt{|\mathcal{I}| s \log(np)}, s \log(np), |\mathcal{I}| \right\} \\
 & \quad + C_{10} \Upsilon_n^{-\iota^*} \left(\max \left\{ |\mathcal{I}|, \sqrt{|\mathcal{I}| \log(np)}, \log(np) \right\} \right)^{1/2} \\
 & \quad \cdot \left(\max \left\{ \sqrt{|\mathcal{I}| s \log(np)}, s \log(np), |\mathcal{I}| \right\} \right)^{1/2}, \tag{S3.28}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$III \leq C_{11} \sqrt{s} \max \left\{ \sqrt{|\mathcal{I}| \log(np)}, \log(np) \right\}, \tag{S3.29}$$

where the last inequalities of *II*, *III* follow from the fact $\kappa_{\pm} \leq C_{\kappa}$. Combining (S3.28) and (S3.29), it follows with probability at least $1 - n^{-5}$,

$$\begin{aligned}
 & I - 2II - 2III \geq -2II - 2III \\
 & \geq \begin{cases} -2C_9 C_I \Upsilon_n^{-2\iota^*} s \log(np) - 2C_{10} C_I \Upsilon_n^{-\iota^*} s \log(np) \\ \quad - 2C_{11} C_I^{1/2} s \log(np), & \text{for } s \log(np) \leq |\mathcal{I}| < C_I s \log(np), \\ -2C_9 \Upsilon_n^{-2\iota^*} s \log(np) - 2C_{10} \Upsilon_n^{-\iota^*} s \log(np) \\ \quad - 2C_{11} s \log(np), & \text{for } \log(np) \leq |\mathcal{I}| < s \log(np), \\ -2C_9 \Upsilon_n^{-2\iota^*} s \log(np) - 2C_{10} \Upsilon_n^{-\iota^*} \sqrt{s} \log(np) \\ \quad - 2C_{11} \sqrt{s} \log(np), & \text{for } |\mathcal{I}| < \log(np), \end{cases} \\
 & \geq -C_{12} s \log(np),
 \end{aligned}$$

where the last inequality follows from $\Upsilon_n^{-\iota^*} = o(1)$.

This completes the proof of result (ii). ■

Proof [Proof of Lemma S3.7(iii)] We denote

$$\begin{aligned}
 \boldsymbol{\beta}^* &= \boldsymbol{\beta}_j^*, & \tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}} &= \hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_j; \\
 \boldsymbol{\beta}_{\times}^* &= \sum_{j' \in [k^*+1] \setminus \{j-1, j, j+1\}} \boldsymbol{\beta}_{j'}^* \mathbb{I}(\tilde{j}_{\times} \in \mathcal{G}_{j'}), & \tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_{\times} &= \tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_{\tilde{j}_{\times}},
 \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\boldsymbol{\Psi}_{\times}^* = \boldsymbol{\beta}_{\times}^* - \boldsymbol{\beta}^*, \quad \tilde{\boldsymbol{\Psi}}_{\times} = \tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_{\times} - \tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}}, \quad \tilde{\boldsymbol{\delta}} = \tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}} - \boldsymbol{\beta}^*, \quad \tilde{\boldsymbol{\delta}}_{\times} = \tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_{\times} - \boldsymbol{\beta}_{\times}^*.$$

Let's first consider the extreme case where $\|\boldsymbol{\Psi}_{\times}^*\|_2 = 0$, meaning $\boldsymbol{\beta}_{\times}^* = \boldsymbol{\beta}^*$. It is worth noting that a similar yet simpler argument as in part(i) suffices to complete the proof.

Next, for a sufficiently large constant $C_I > 0$, we discuss the following two cases: $|\mathcal{I}| \|\boldsymbol{\Psi}_{\times}^*\|_2^2 \geq C_I s \log(np)$ and $|\mathcal{I}| \|\boldsymbol{\Psi}_{\times}^*\|_2^2 < C_I s \log(np)$. Based on Lemma S3.6, it follows that $c_0 \leq \|\boldsymbol{\Psi}_{\times}^*\|_2^2 \leq C_0$, where c_0 and C_0 are positive absolute constants. Note that

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{I}, \tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_{\times}) - \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{I}, \tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}}) &= \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (y_i - \mathbf{X}_i^{\top} \tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_{\times})^2 - \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (y_i - \mathbf{X}_i^{\top} \tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}})^2 \\
 &= \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (y_i - \mathbf{X}_i^{\top} \boldsymbol{\beta}^* + \mathbf{X}_i^{\top} \boldsymbol{\beta}^* - \mathbf{X}_i^{\top} \tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_{\times})^2 - \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (y_i - \mathbf{X}_i^{\top} \boldsymbol{\beta}^* + \mathbf{X}_i^{\top} \boldsymbol{\beta}^* - \mathbf{X}_i^{\top} \tilde{\boldsymbol{\beta}})^2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= -2 \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \varepsilon_i \mathbf{X}_i^\top \tilde{\Psi}_\times + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (\mathbf{X}_i^\top \tilde{\delta}_\times)^2 - \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (\mathbf{X}_i^\top \tilde{\delta})^2 \\
 &= \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (\mathbf{X}_i^\top \tilde{\Psi}_\times)^2 + 2 \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \tilde{\Psi}_\times^\top \mathbf{X}_i \mathbf{X}_i^\top \tilde{\delta} - 2 \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \varepsilon_i \mathbf{X}_i^\top \tilde{\Psi}_\times \\
 &\geq \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (\mathbf{X}_i^\top \tilde{\Psi}_\times)^2 - 2 \left| \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \tilde{\Psi}_\times^\top \mathbf{X}_i \mathbf{X}_i^\top \tilde{\delta} \right| - 2 \left| \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \varepsilon_i \mathbf{X}_i^\top \tilde{\Psi}_\times \right| \\
 &= I - 2II - 2III.
 \end{aligned}$$

Next, we aim to bound the three terms above.

Following similar arguments as in (S3.22) and (S3.23), we can verify that the following relations hold with probability at least $1 - n^{-5}$,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \|\tilde{\Psi}_\times - \Psi_\times^*\|_2 &\leq 2C\Upsilon_n^{-\iota^*} \kappa, & \|\tilde{\Psi}_\times - \Psi_\times^*\|_1 &\leq 8C\Upsilon_n^{-\iota^*} \sqrt{s\kappa}, \\
 \|\tilde{\Psi}_\times\|_2 &\leq 2C\Upsilon_n^{-\iota^*} \kappa + \|\Psi_\times^*\|_2, & \|\tilde{\Psi}_\times\|_1 &\leq 8C\Upsilon_n^{-\iota^*} \sqrt{s\kappa} + C_k \sqrt{s} \|\Psi_\times^*\|_2.
 \end{aligned} \tag{S3.30}$$

Following similar arguments as in Steps 1-3 of Lemma S3.7(ii)'s proof, we present the corresponding **Steps 1-3** below.

Step 1: the term I . It can verify that

$$\begin{aligned}
 I &\geq \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (\mathbf{X}_i^\top \Psi_\times^*)^2 - 2 \left\{ \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (\mathbf{X}_i^\top \Psi_\times^*)^2 \right\}^{1/2} \left\{ \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (\mathbf{X}_i^\top (\tilde{\Psi}_\times - \Psi_\times^*))^2 \right\}^{1/2} \\
 &= I_1 - 2I_2^{1/2} I_3^{1/2},
 \end{aligned}$$

where the second inequality follows from Cauchy-Schwartz inequality. Therefore, by Lemma 25(iii) (Appendix), we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_1 &\geq \underline{\rho}_x |\mathcal{I}| \|\Psi_\times^*\|_2^2 - C_1 (\sqrt{|\mathcal{I}| \log(np)} + \log(np)) \|\Psi_\times^*\|_2^2, \\
 I_2 &\leq \bar{\rho}_x |\mathcal{I}| \|\Psi_\times^*\|_2^2 + C_1 (\sqrt{|\mathcal{I}| \log(np)} + \log(np)) \|\Psi_\times^*\|_2^2,
 \end{aligned}$$

with at least probability $1 - n^{-5}$. Moreover, by Lemma 26(iii) (Appendix), it follows with probability at least $1 - n^{-5}$,

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_3 &\leq C_2 (\|\tilde{\Psi}_\times - \Psi_\times^*\|_2^2 + \frac{1}{s} \|\tilde{\Psi}_\times - \Psi_\times^*\|_1^2) \left\{ \sqrt{|\mathcal{I}| s \log(np)} + s \log(np) \right\} \\
 &\leq C_2 (4C^2 \Upsilon_n^{-2\iota^*} \kappa^2 + 64C^2 \Upsilon_n^{-2\iota^*} \kappa^2) \left\{ \sqrt{|\mathcal{I}| s \log(np)} + s \log(np) \right\} \\
 &\leq C_3 \Upsilon_n^{-2\iota^*} \kappa^2 \left\{ \sqrt{|\mathcal{I}| s \log(np)} + s \log(np) + |\mathcal{I}| \right\},
 \end{aligned}$$

where the second inequality follows from (S3.30).

Step 2: the term II . Some algebra shows that

$$\begin{aligned}
 II &\leq \left\{ \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (\mathbf{X}_i^\top (\tilde{\Psi}_\times - \Psi_\times^*))^2 \right\}^{1/2} \left\{ \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (\mathbf{X}_i^\top \tilde{\delta})^2 \right\}^{1/2} \\
 &\quad + \left\{ \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (\mathbf{X}_i^\top \Psi_\times^*)^2 \right\}^{1/2} \left\{ \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} (\mathbf{X}_i^\top \tilde{\delta})^2 \right\}^{1/2}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$= II_1^{1/2} \cdot II_2^{1/2} + II_3^{1/2} \cdot II_2^{1/2},$$

where the second inequality follows from Cauchy-Schwartz inequality. By Lemma 25(iii) (Appendix), Lemma 26(i)(iii) and (S3.30), it follows with probability at least $1 - n^{-5}$,

$$\begin{aligned} II_1 &\leq C_3 \Upsilon_n^{-2\iota^*} \kappa^2 \left\{ \sqrt{|\mathcal{I}|s \log(np)} + s \log(np) + |\mathcal{I}| \right\}, \\ II_2 &\leq C_4 \Upsilon_n^{-2\iota^*} \kappa^2 \left\{ \sqrt{|\mathcal{I}|s \log(np)} + s \log(np) + |\mathcal{I}| \right\}, \\ II_3 &\leq \bar{\rho}_x |\mathcal{I}| \|\Psi_{\times}^*\|_2^2 + C_1 (\sqrt{|\mathcal{I}| \log(np)} + \log(np)) \|\Psi_{\times}^*\|_2^2, \end{aligned}$$

where the all inequalities is similar to the arguments of **Step 1**.

Step 3: the term III. Note that, with probability at least $1 - n^{-5}$, it holds that

$$\begin{aligned} III &\leq \left\| \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \varepsilon_i \mathbf{X}_i^\top \right\|_{\infty} \|\tilde{\Psi}_{\times}\|_1 \\ &\leq C_5 \left(\sqrt{|\mathcal{I}| \log(np)} + \log(np) \right) \left\{ 8C \Upsilon_n^{-\iota^*} \sqrt{s} \kappa + C_k \sqrt{s} \|\Psi_{\times}^*\|_2 \right\}, \end{aligned}$$

where the last inequality follows from Lemma 25(i) (Appendix) and (S3.30).

Step 4. We now discuss lower bounds for I, II, III under two cases.

Case 1: $|\mathcal{I}| \|\Psi_{\times}^*\|_2^2 \geq C_I s \log(np)$. It holds with probability at least $1 - n^{-5}$,

$$\begin{aligned} I &\geq I_1 - 2I_2^{1/2} I_3^{1/2} \\ &\geq \frac{\rho_x}{2} |\mathcal{I}| \|\Psi_{\times}^*\|_2^2 - 2 \left\{ \frac{3}{2} \bar{\rho}_x |\mathcal{I}| \|\Psi_{\times}^*\|_2^2 \right\}^{1/2} \left\{ C_3 |\mathcal{I}| \Upsilon_n^{-2\iota^*} \kappa^2 \right\}^{1/2} \\ &\geq \frac{\rho_x}{2} |\mathcal{I}| \|\Psi_{\times}^*\|_2^2 - \sqrt{6 \bar{\rho}_x C_3} \Upsilon_n^{-\iota^*} |\mathcal{I}| \kappa \|\Psi_{\times}^*\|_2, \end{aligned} \tag{S3.31}$$

$$\begin{aligned} II &\leq II_1^{1/2} \cdot II_2^{1/2} + II_3^{1/2} \cdot II_2^{1/2} \\ &\leq \left\{ C_3 |\mathcal{I}| \Upsilon_n^{-2\iota^*} \kappa^2 \right\}^{1/2} \left\{ C_4 |\mathcal{I}| \Upsilon_n^{-2\iota^*} \kappa^2 \right\}^{1/2} + \left\{ \frac{3}{2} \bar{\rho}_x |\mathcal{I}| \|\Psi_{\times}^*\|_2^2 \right\}^{1/2} \left\{ C_4 |\mathcal{I}| \Upsilon_n^{-2\iota^*} \kappa^2 \right\}^{1/2} \\ &\leq \sqrt{C_3 C_4} \Upsilon_n^{-2\iota^*} |\mathcal{I}| \kappa^2 + \sqrt{\frac{3}{2} \bar{\rho}_x C_4} \Upsilon_n^{-\iota^*} |\mathcal{I}| \kappa \|\Psi_{\times}^*\|_2, \end{aligned} \tag{S3.32}$$

$$III \leq C_7 \|\Psi_{\times}^*\|_2 \sqrt{|\mathcal{I}|s \log(np)} \left\{ \frac{8\kappa C}{\Upsilon_n^{\iota^*}} + C_k \right\}, \tag{S3.33}$$

where the second inequalities of I, II follow from the fact that C_I is a sufficiently large constant and relations $s \log(np) \leq \sqrt{|\mathcal{I}|s \log(np)} \leq |\mathcal{I}|$. Combining (S3.31), (S3.32) and (S3.33), it follows with probability at least $1 - n^{-5}$,

$$\begin{aligned} I - 2II - 2III &\geq \frac{\rho_x}{2} |\mathcal{I}| \|\Psi_{\times}^*\|_2^2 - C_8 \Upsilon_n^{-\iota^*} |\mathcal{I}| \kappa \|\Psi_{\times}^*\|_2 - C_9 \Upsilon_n^{-2\iota^*} |\mathcal{I}| \kappa^2 \\ &\quad - 2C_7 \|\Psi_{\times}^*\|_2 \sqrt{|\mathcal{I}|s \log(np)} \left\{ \frac{8\kappa C}{\Upsilon_n^{\iota^*}} + C_k \right\} \\ &\geq \frac{\bar{\rho}_x}{2} |\mathcal{I}| \|\Psi_{\times}^*\|_2^2 \left(1 - \frac{2C_8 C_{\kappa}}{\bar{\rho}_x \Upsilon_n^{\iota^*} \|\Psi_{\times}^*\|_2} - \frac{2C_9 C_{\kappa}^2}{\bar{\rho}_x \Upsilon_n^{2\iota^*}} \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & -2C_7 \|\Psi_{\times}^*\|_2 \sqrt{|\mathcal{I}|s \log(np)} \left\{ \frac{8CC_{\kappa}}{\Upsilon_n^{\iota^*}} + C_k \right\} \\
 & \geq \frac{\bar{\rho}_x}{4} |\mathcal{I}| \|\Psi_{\times}^*\|_2^2 - 3C_7 C_k \|\Psi_{\times}^*\|_2 \sqrt{|\mathcal{I}|s \log(np)} \\
 & \geq \frac{\bar{\rho}_x}{4} |\mathcal{I}| \|\Psi_{\times}^*\|_2^2 \left(1 - \frac{12C_7 C_k}{\bar{\rho}_x} \sqrt{\frac{s \log(np)}{|\mathcal{I}| \|\Psi_{\times}^*\|_2^2}} \right) \\
 & \geq 0,
 \end{aligned}$$

where the second inequality follows from $\kappa \leq C_{\kappa}$, the third inequality follows from $\Upsilon_n^{-\iota^*} = o(1)$, and the last inequality follows from the fact that $|\mathcal{I}| \geq C_I s \log(np)$ with sufficiently large constant C_I .

Case 2: $|\mathcal{I}| \|\Psi_{\times}^*\|_2^2 < C_I s \log(np)$. It holds with probability at least $1 - n^{-5}$,

$$\begin{aligned}
 II & \leq II_1^{1/2} \cdot II_2^{1/2} + II_3^{1/2} \cdot II_2^{1/2} \\
 & \leq \sqrt{C_3 C_4 \Upsilon_n^{-2\iota^*} \kappa^2} \left\{ \sqrt{|\mathcal{I}|s \log(np)} + s \log(np) + |\mathcal{I}| \right\} \\
 & \quad + \left\{ C_4 \Upsilon_n^{-2\iota^*} \kappa^2 \left\{ \sqrt{|\mathcal{I}|s \log(np)} + s \log(np) + |\mathcal{I}| \right\} \right\}^{1/2} \\
 & \quad \cdot \left\{ \bar{\rho}_x |\mathcal{I}| \|\Psi_{\times}^*\|_2^2 + C_1 (\sqrt{|\mathcal{I}| \log(np)} + \log(np)) \|\Psi_{\times}^*\|_2^2 \right\}^{1/2} \\
 & \leq C_{10} \Upsilon_n^{-2\iota^*} \max \left\{ \sqrt{|\mathcal{I}|s \log(np)}, s \log(np), |\mathcal{I}| \right\} \\
 & \quad + C_{11} \Upsilon_n^{-\iota^*} \left(\max \left\{ |\mathcal{I}|, \sqrt{|\mathcal{I}| \log(np)}, \log(np) \right\} \right)^{1/2} \\
 & \quad \cdot \left(\max \left\{ \sqrt{|\mathcal{I}|s \log(np)}, s \log(np), |\mathcal{I}| \right\} \right)^{1/2}, \tag{S3.34}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$III \leq C_{12} \sqrt{s} \max \left\{ \sqrt{|\mathcal{I}| \log(np)}, \log(np) \right\}, \tag{S3.35}$$

where the last inequalities of II, III follow from the fact $\kappa \leq C_{\kappa}$ and $\|\Psi_{\times}^*\|_2 \leq C_0$. Combining (S3.34) and (S3.35), it follows with probability at least $1 - n^{-5}$,

$$\begin{aligned}
 & I - 2II - 2III \geq -2II - 2III \\
 & \geq \begin{cases} -2C_{10} C_I c_0^{-1} \Upsilon_n^{-2\iota^*} s \log(np) - 2C_{11} C_I c_0^{-1} \Upsilon_n^{-\iota^*} s \log(np) \\ \quad - 2C_{12} C_I^{1/2} c_0^{-1/2} s \log(np), & \text{for } s \log(np) \leq |\mathcal{I}| < C_I / c_0 s \log(np), \\ -2C_{10} \Upsilon_n^{-2\iota^*} s \log(np) - 2C_{11} \Upsilon_n^{-\iota^*} s \log(np) \\ \quad - 2C_{12} s \log(np), & \text{for } \log(np) \leq |\mathcal{I}| < s \log(np), \\ -2C_{10} \Upsilon_n^{-2\iota^*} s \log(np) - 2C_{11} \Upsilon_n^{-\iota^*} \sqrt{s} \log(np) \\ \quad - 2C_{12} \sqrt{s} \log(np), & \text{for } |\mathcal{I}| < \log(np), \end{cases} \\
 & \geq -C_{13} s \log(np),
 \end{aligned}$$

where the last inequality follows from $\Upsilon_n^{-\iota^*} = o(1)$.

This completes the proof of result (iii). ■

S3.3 Prerequisite results for optimization problem (13)

The prerequisite propositions established in this section provide the technical foundation for the proof of Theorem 7 (Main Paper). Specifically, under the event (19), the elements in $\mathcal{T}_k^r \in \mathbb{T}_{\hat{k}}(n)$ will lie within a scale of Δ around the true change points, ensuring that the multiple change point problem can be reduced to a single change point problem. Notably, all arguments in this subsection rely on the assumptions required by Theorem 7 (Main Paper). Recall that the solution is $\hat{\mathcal{T}}_k^r = \{\hat{t}_j^r\}_{j=1}^{\hat{k}}$. In this subsection, we have largely omitted detailed proofs and statements, except for those of critical importance. This simplification is justified since Proposition 35 (Appendix) is simpler and more intuitive than Proposition 5 (Main Paper), owing to the convergence $\mathbb{P}\{\hat{k} = k^*\} \rightarrow 1$ as $n, p \rightarrow \infty$. We now present the detailed proof of Proposition 35 (Appendix).

Proof [Proof of Proposition 35] We denote the event

$$\mathcal{A}_j^r = \left\{ \hat{t}_j^r \in \mathcal{H}(0, \Delta/4; t_j^*) \right\} \quad \text{for } j \in [k^*].$$

Next, we use a recursive method to prove that the event $\bigcap_{j=1}^{k^*} \mathcal{A}_j^r$ holds. We start by proving through contradiction that $\bigcup_{j=1}^{k^*} (\mathcal{A}_j^r)^c$ is impossible.

Step 1. There exists only one $j \in [k^*]$ such that $|\hat{t}_j^r - t_j^*| > \Delta/4$ under the event

$$(\mathcal{A}_j^r)^c \cap \left(\bigcap_{j' \in [k^*] \setminus \{j\}} \mathcal{A}_{j'}^r \right). \quad (\text{S3.36})$$

Under (S3.36), it can verify that

$$\hat{t}_j^r \in [t_{j-1}^* - \Delta/4, t_j^* - \Delta/4) \cup (t_j^* + \Delta/4, t_{j+1}^* + \Delta/4].$$

Without loss of generality, let us consider the setting where $\hat{t}_j^r \in (t_j^* + \Delta/4, t_{j+1}^* + \Delta/4]$; the alternative case is symmetric. The analysis proceeds with the following cases:

- (a) $\hat{t}_j^r \in (t_j^* + \Delta/4, t_{j+1}^*]$.
- (b) $\hat{t}_j^r \in (t_{j+1}^*, t_{j+1}^* + \Delta/4]$.

Case (a). It can verify that

$$\hat{t}_j^r > t_j^* + \Delta/4, \quad (\text{S3.37})$$

The existence of a **big signal interval** $\mathcal{J} = (t_j^*, \hat{t}_j^r]$ with $|\mathcal{J}| \geq C_1 \Delta$ for $C_1 > 1/4$ follows directly from:

- Lemma S3.8(i) under model (2);
- Lemma S3.9(i) under model (3).

This interval satisfies with probability exceeding $1 - n^{-5}$:

$$\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{J}, \hat{\theta}_j) - \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{J}, \hat{\theta}_{j+1}) \geq C_1 \Delta \kappa^2. \quad (\text{S3.38})$$

Define $\Delta\text{TL}(\widehat{\mathcal{T}}_k^r, \mathcal{T}_{k^*}^*)$ through (S3.4) as the total loss discrepancy over ordered intervals generated by $\{0\} \cup \{\hat{t}_j^r\}_{j=1}^k \cup \{t_j^*\}_{j=1}^{k^*}$. Under Assumption 3 (Main Paper), there exist absolute constants $C_2 > 0$ such that:

$$\Delta\text{TL}(\widehat{\mathcal{T}}_k^r, \mathcal{T}_{k^*}^*) \geq C_1 \Delta \kappa^2 - C_2 s \log(np) > 0. \quad (\text{S3.39})$$

To justify why the first inequality holds, we note that $\text{TL}(\mathcal{T}_{k^*}^*, \widehat{\Theta}(\hat{k} + 1))$ captures the total loss when employing the "correct" estimated parameters. The lower bound arises from partitioning each true interval $(t_{j-1}^*, t_j^*]$ into two regimes via Lemma S3.8(i) under model (2) (or Lemma S3.9(i) under model (3)):

- **Big signal difference:** Contribute $\geq C_1 \Delta \kappa^2$ through (S3.38);
- **Small signal difference:** Generate bounded $\geq -C_2 s \log(np)$.

Of course, these second case is necessarily finite, which leads to the absolute constants $C_2 > 0$ in the inequality. Expression (S3.39) contradicts inequality (S3.4) for sufficiently large C_{snr} .

Case (b). If we have

$$\hat{u}_{m(j)} \in (t_{j+1}^*, t_{j+1}^* + \Delta/4],$$

then the total loss difference (S3.39) over the interval $(t_j^*, \hat{t}_j^r] = (t_j^*, t_{j+1}^*] \cup (t_{j+1}^*, \hat{t}_j^r]$ results in two effects:

- Lemma S3.8(ii) under model (2) (or Lemma S3.9(ii) under model (3)), describing the "misplaced difference" in the interval $(t_{j+1}^*, \hat{t}_{m(j)}^r]$;
- Lemma S3.8(i) under model (2) (or Lemma S3.9(i) under model (3)), which highlights the "signal difference" within the big "signal interval" $\mathcal{J} = (t_j^*, t_{j+1}^*]$ such that $|\mathcal{J}| \geq \Delta$.

Naturally, expression (S3.39) also holds, though with slightly different constant terms. In other words, when \hat{t}_j^r is located to the right of t_{j+1}^* , the "misplaced difference" will necessarily be accompanied by a **big signal difference**. Under the SNR assumption, this sufficiently large "signal difference" guarantees that (S3.39) always holds.

The proofs of **Step 2** and **Step 3** follow a similar but simpler arguments to that in the Proof of Proposition 5(i) and are thus omitted. \blacksquare

Generalization of Proposition 35 We extend Proposition 35 (Appendix) to handle partial segmentation. For any true change point $t_{\mathbb{k}}^*$ where $\mathbb{k} \in [k^*]$, consider a modified global refitted formulation that substitutes:

- The full dataset \mathcal{Z} with the truncated sequence $\mathcal{Z}_0^{t_{\mathbb{k}}^*}$;
- All parameter estimators $\widehat{\Theta}(\hat{k} + 1)$ with the partial set $\widehat{\Theta}(\mathbb{k})$.

This yields the constrained optimization:

$$\widehat{\mathcal{T}}_{\mathbb{k}-1}^r = \arg \min_{\mathcal{T} \in \mathbb{T}_{\mathbb{k}-1}(t_{\mathbb{k}}^*)} \text{TL}(\mathcal{T}, \widehat{\Theta}(\mathbb{k})) \quad (\text{S3.40})$$

producing $\mathbb{k} - 1$ refined estimates. The truncation discards post- $t_{\mathbb{k}}^*$ data $\mathcal{Z}_{t_{\mathbb{k}}^*}^n$ and estimators $\{\widehat{\theta}_j\}_{j=\mathbb{k}+1}^{\widehat{\mathbb{k}}+1}$, as their true counterparts $\{\theta_j^*\}_{j=\mathbb{k}+1}^{k^*+1}$ are excluded by design. This ensures methodological consistency: the optimization scope matches both available data and identifiable parameters.

Proposition 35' *Let $\widehat{\mathcal{T}}_{\mathbb{k}-1}^r = \{\widehat{t}_j^r\}_{j=1}^{\mathbb{k}-1}$ be the solution to (S3.40), then for all $j \in [\mathbb{k} - 1]$, we have the following results*

$$\widehat{t}_j^r \in \mathcal{H}(0, \Delta/4; t_j^*),$$

with probability at least $1 - n^{-5}$.

Proof Note that, since the endpoint is $t_{\mathbb{k}}^*$, the data $\mathcal{Z}_0^{t_{\mathbb{k}}^*}$ includes only $\mathbb{k} - 1$ true change points. Thus, it is sufficient to ensure that the intersection of events $\bigcap_{j=1}^{\mathbb{k}-1} \mathcal{A}_j^r$ holds with high probability. The rest of the proof parallels that of Proposition 35 (Appendix) and is omitted for brevity. \blacksquare

S3.4 Proof of Lemmas in Section S3.3

Throughout this subsection, we assume that all the conditions in Theorem 7 (Main Paper) hold.

S3.4.1 CHANGES IN MEANS

Lemma S3.8 *For the model (2), given any fixed $j \in [k^* + 1]$, let a subinterval $\mathcal{I} \subseteq (t_{j-1}^*, t_j^*)$. The following result holds with probability at least $1 - n^{-5}$.*

- (i) (Signal difference) *For any $j_{\pm} \in \{j - 1, j + 1\}$, it holds that for absolute constant $C > 0$,*

$$\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{I}, \widehat{\mu}_{j_{\pm}}) - \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{I}, \widehat{\mu}_j) \geq -Cs \log(np).$$

Furthermore, for any sub-interval satisfying $|\mathcal{I}| \geq C_d \Delta$, it holds that

$$\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{I}, \widehat{\mu}_{j_{\pm}}) - \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{I}, \widehat{\mu}_j) \geq C \Delta \kappa^2,$$

where $C_d > 0$ is absolute constant.

- (ii) (Misplaced difference) *For any $j_{\times} \in [k^* + 1] \setminus \{j - 1, j, j + 1\}$, it holds that for absolute constant $C > 0$,*

$$\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{I}, \widehat{\mu}_{j_{\times}}) - \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{I}, \widehat{\mu}_j) > -Cs \log(np).$$

Proof By Corollary 31 (Appendix), for any $j \in [k^* + 1]$, we have

$$\|\widehat{\mu}_j - \mu_j^*\|_2 \leq C_1 \sqrt{s \log(np) / \Delta} \leq C_2 \kappa \mathcal{Y}_n^{-1/2},$$

where the second inequality follows from Assumption 3. The remaining proof is similar to that of Lemma S3.5, with the rate $\kappa\mathcal{T}_n^{-\iota^*}$ adjusted to $\kappa\mathcal{T}_n^{-1/2}$. It is simpler and thus omitted. ■

S3.4.2 CHANGES IN REGRESSION COEFFICIENTS

Lemma S3.9 *For the model (3), given any fixed $j \in [k^* + 1]$, let a subinterval $\mathcal{I} \subseteq (t_{j-1}^*, t_j^*]$. The following result holds with probability at least $1 - n^{-5}$.*

(i) *(Signal difference) For any $j_{\pm} \in \{j - 1, j + 1\}$, it holds that for absolute constant $C > 0$,*

$$\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{I}, \hat{\beta}_{j_{\pm}}) - \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{I}, \hat{\beta}_j) \geq -Cs \log(np).$$

Furthermore, for any sub-interval satisfying $|\mathcal{I}| \geq C_d \Delta$, it holds that

$$\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{I}, \hat{\beta}_{j_{\pm}}) - \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{I}, \hat{\beta}_j) \geq C\Delta\kappa^2,$$

where $C_d > 0$ is absolute constant.

(ii) *(Misplaced difference) For any $j_{\times} \in [k^* + 1] \setminus \{j - 1, j, j + 1\}$, it holds that for absolute constant $C > 0$,*

$$\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{I}, \hat{\beta}_{j_{\times}}) - \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{I}, \hat{\beta}_j) > -Cs \log(np).$$

Proof By Corollary 34 (Appendix), for any $j \in [k^* + 1]$, we have

$$\|\hat{\beta}_j - \beta_j^*\|_2 \leq C_1 \sqrt{s \log(np) / \Delta} \leq C_2 \kappa \mathcal{T}_n^{-1/2},$$

where the second inequality follows from Assumption 3 (Main Paper). The remaining proof is similar to that of Lemma S3.7, with the rate $\kappa\mathcal{T}_n^{-\iota^*}$ adjusted to $\kappa\mathcal{T}_n^{-1/2}$. It is simpler and thus omitted. ■

References

- Sumanta Basu and George Michailidis. Regularized estimation in sparse high-dimensional time series models. *The Annals of Statistics*, 43(4):1535–1567, 2015.
- Po-Ling Loh and Martin J. Wainwright. High-dimensional regression with noisy and missing data: Provable guarantees with nonconvexity. *The Annals of Statistics*, 40(3):1637–1664, 2012.
- Alessandro Rinaldo, Daren Wang, Qin Wen, Rebecca Willett, and Yi Yu. Localizing Changes in High-Dimensional Regression Models. In *Proceedings of The 24th International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Statistics*, pages 2089–2097. PMLR, 2021.
- Roman Vershynin. *High-Dimensional Probability*. Cambridge University Press, 2018.
- Haotian Xu, Daren Wang, Zifeng Zhao, and Yi Yu. Change-point inference in high-dimensional regression models under temporal dependence. *The Annals of Statistics*, 52(3):999–1026, 2024.